

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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深度强化学习中 Actor-Critic 算法家族的环境探索策略
**ENVIRONMENT EXPLORATION STRATEGIES IN THE FAMILY
OF ACTOR-CRITIC ALGORITHMS
FOR DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING**

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摘要：本研究旨在探讨深度强化学习中的探索策略。研究重点在于这些策略在非平稳环境、稀疏奖励和劣质输入数据条件下的有效性。本工作的目标是对Actor-Critic算法家族中常用的探索策略进行系统分析、分类和比较评估，以识别最有效和最有前景的方法。基于分析结果，本文提出了切实可行的应用建议。

关键词：深度强化学习，Actor-Critic算法，探索，探索-利用困境，熵正则化，内在动机，基于不确定性的探索，稀疏奖励，安全探索，方法分类，比较分析，混合方法。

Abstract. *The object of this study is exploration strategies in deep reinforcement learning. The subject of the study is the effectiveness of these strategies under conditions of non-stationary environments, sparse rewards, and poor input data. The aim of this work is a systematic analysis, taxonomy, and comparative evaluation of contemporary exploration strategies used within the actor-critic algorithm family to identify the most effective and promising approaches. Based on the analysis, practical recommendations for their application are formulated.*

Keywords: *deep reinforcement learning, actor-critic, exploration, exploration-exploitation dilemma, entropy regularization, intrinsic motivation, uncertainty-based exploration, sparse rewards, safe exploration, taxonomy of methods, comparative analysis, hybrid methods.*

Introduction

Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has become an effective tool for solving complex sequential decision-making problems in fields such as robotics, resource management, and data mining. Among numerous architectures in DRL, methods of the Actor-Critic (AC) family [1] have assumed a dominant position, as evidenced by their successful application in several breakthrough projects [2]. This architecture, combining the advantages of policy-based and value-based methods [3], provides high training stability and effectiveness in tasks with continuous action spaces.

However, despite significant successes, the fundamental dilemma of reinforcement learning — the balance between exploration and exploitation — remains fully unresolved specifically in the context of AC methods. Exploitation involves selecting actions that, according to the current knowledge of the agent, maximize future reward. Exploration is the selection of unknown or insufficiently studied actions aimed at gathering new information and potentially discovering more effective strategies.

Effective exploration is a critical component for achieving high performance in environments with sparse rewards, where positive reinforcements are rare and the agent must actively seek them, including in non-stationary conditions where the optimal strategy can change over time. Within the AC architecture, the exploration problem has a particular specificity: the critic evaluates actions, guiding the actor toward exploitation, while the stochasticity of the actor and various regularizers are designed to stimulate the exploration process. Nevertheless, standard approaches, such as entropy regularization in the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm [4], often prove insufficient. They provide ‘blind’ explorations that are not focused on the purposeful acquisition of new information and may demonstrate slow adaptation to the environment under rapidly changing conditions.

Thus, although the actor-critic architecture offers a universal and powerful architectural template, the development of effective, directed, and adaptive exploration strategies within this framework remains a pressing scientific challenge. Resolving this problem is key to developing more robust, intelligent, and autonomous agents capable of learning in complex and dynamic real-world conditions.

This work systematizes modern exploration strategies within the family of actor-critic deep reinforcement learning algorithms. An analysis of three fundamental approaches is carried out: entropy regularization, uncertainty estimation-based methods, and intrinsic motivation. The principles of their hybridization to overcome limitations are examined. A taxonomy for the comparative analysis of strategies based on key criteria has been developed, upon which practical recommendations for method selection depending on task conditions are formulated. Key unresolved issues have been identified: lack of theoretical guarantees, safe exploration, and adaptation to non-stationary environments. Promising directions for future research are proposed.

1. Fundamental Exploration Strategies

Effective environment exploration is the cornerstone of successful learning in deep reinforcement learning. Within the actor-critic architecture, several fundamental strategies have been developed, which can be classified into three main groups reflecting the evolution from simple stochasticity to complex forms of purposeful exploration.

Strategy 1. Entropy regularization (blind exploration). The most straightforward and widely used approach to incentivizing explorations is entropy regularization. Its key idea consists in modifying the agent’s objective function: a bonus proportional to the entropy of the policy π in a given state (s) is added to the expected reward. Mathematically, the actor’s objective is modified as follows:

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}[R + \alpha \cdot H(\pi(\cdot|s))], \quad (1)$$

where $H(\pi(\cdot|s))$ denotes the entropy of the policy, and α is the temperature coefficient balancing the importance of the reward and entropy.

Advantages: Training stability, good coverage of the action space, and relative ease of implementation. The entropy bonus effectively prevents premature convergence to suboptimal deterministic policies.

Disadvantages: Exploration is passive and undirected (‘blind’ exploration). The agent uniformly distributes action probabilities across the entire space without focusing on promising or underexplored regions. This can be highly inefficient in environments with high dimensionality or very sparse rewards.

Example: A prominent example is the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm [4]. In this algorithm, the policy is initially parameterized as stochastic (typically Gaussian distribution), and the coefficient α can be adapted during training to maintain a specified entropy level.

Strategy 2. Uncertainty-based exploration (critic ensembles). A more targeted strategy is proposed by methods based on uncertainty estimation. The approach known as ‘Optimism in the Face of Uncertainty’ (OFU) guides the agent towards actions whose value estimates exhibit the greatest uncertainty [5]. In the AC architecture, this uncertainty is estimated by the critic. Instead of a single Q-function, an ensemble of multiple critics can be employed. The spread of their predictions (variance) for the pair (s, a) serves as a measure of uncertainty. The actor is tuned to select actions that maximize both the expected Q-value and this uncertainty:

$$a = \operatorname{argmax}(Q(s, a) + \beta \cdot U(s, a)), \quad (2)$$

where $U(s, a)$ is the uncertainty estimate, and β is a hyperparameter. Historically, this idea originates from methods similar to bootstrapping used in DQN [6].

Advantages: “Smart,” directed exploration. The agent actively seeks areas where its knowledge is inaccurate, potentially leading to faster discovery of new, useful strategies.

Disadvantages: The computational cost of training an ensemble of models is high. Furthermore, uncertainty estimation may be inaccurate and sensitive to the hyperparameter β , potentially causing training instability or excessive attention to noisy regions of the state space.

Example: Algorithms such as REDQ (Randomized Ensemble Double Q-learning) [7] utilize an ensemble of Q-functions not only to reduce overestimation bias (as in TD3 [8]) but also explicitly to manage the exploration strategy. The actor can choose actions that maximize not only the mean Q-value over the ensemble but also the variance.

Strategy 3. Intrinsic motivation (goal setting). To address the issue of sparse external rewards, a class of methods based on intrinsic motivation has been developed. The idea is that the agent generates its own intrinsic reward (r_i) for visiting novel or unpredictable states. The critic is trained to evaluate their sum:

$$Q(s,a) \approx \mathbb{E}[r_e + r_i]. \quad (3)$$

Advantages: High efficiency in conditions of sparse rewards. The agent can learn even in the complete absence of external rewards, guided exclusively by intrinsic motivation. This allows mastering complex environments with long flat horizons.

Disadvantages: Risk of “noisy” states. The agent may get stuck in states that are inherently unpredictable (for example, semantic noise in the feature space), obtaining infinite intrinsic reward from them. The problem of balancing intrinsic and extrinsic reward remains critical.

Example: In practice, intrinsic reward is often computed based on the **prediction error** of the subsequent state or its features. For example, in the method **Random Network Distillation (RND)**[9], intrinsic reward is proportional to the prediction error of the output of a randomly initialized neural network for the current state, as in the **Intrinsic Curiosity Module (ICM)**[10] or other prediction-based variants [5]. The newer the state, the worse it is predicted, and the higher the reward.

These strategies form the foundation upon which modern hybrid exploration methods in the actor-critic architecture are built, combining their advantages to overcome individual shortcomings, as will be discussed further.

Strategy 4. It was demonstrated above that fundamental exploration strategies (entropy regularization, uncertainty estimation, and intrinsic motivation) possess both advantages and disadvantages. The evolution of exploration methods within the actor-critic architecture has naturally led to the emergence of hybrid approaches that combine these strategies to offset their shortcomings and achieve a synergistic effect. Rather than seeking a universal solution, current research focuses on how and based on which principles various exploration strategies can be combined to develop more efficient and robust algorithms [5].

The principle of compensating weaknesses. The most evident principle of combination is using one method to compensate for the fundamental limitation of another.

Blind exploration (entropy) combined with goal-setting (motivation). Entropy regularization ensures broad but aimless coverage of the action space, while intrinsic motivation directs exploration purposefully but may become trapped in local optima ('noisy' states). Their combination enables the agent to deliberately explore new areas (due to intrinsic reward) while maintaining sufficient stochasticity to escape from dead-end paths (due to the entropy bonus).

Example: Many modern implementations of SAC-based algorithms [4] (e.g., in environments with sparse rewards) are augmented with an intrinsic motivation module (RND [9]). The critic in such an architecture is trained to estimate the sum of external and intrinsic rewards, while the actor maximizes this sum along with the entropy.

The principle of synergy. This hybridization principle involves combining two goal-directed strategies (explorations based on uncertainty and intrinsic motivation) to create a synergistic effect. Although both strategies are goal-directed, they rely on different sources of information: the first utilizes uncertainty in the model's knowledge, while the second focuses on the novelty of states. Their combination enables the agent to more effectively identify areas that are both novel and promising in terms of reducing the model's uncertainty.

Advantages: The combination allows overcoming the limitations of each strategy individually. Intrinsic motivation can become trapped on purely random but unpredictable disturbances ("noisy" states), whereas uncertainty-based exploration may focus excessively on areas with high noise in the data rather than on regions exhibiting semantic novelty. Their combined use leads to more meaningful and effective exploration.

Example: In practice, this can be implemented by combining bonuses from both strategies in the value function that the actor maximizes. The actor can select actions guided by the sum of the expected external reward, an uncertainty bonus (from the ensemble of critics), and an intrinsic novelty reward (e.g., from RND or ICM) [5, 7, 9]. The ensemble of critics in such a hybrid architecture serves not as an independent strategy, but as a tool for a more accurate and stable estimation of uncertainty, which is then used within the hybrid principle.

Principle of abstraction. The idea is to transfer the exploration problem from the original high-dimensional state and action spaces to a lower-dimensional latent feature space. Instead of applying the exploration strategy directly to the primary environment observations (for example, pixels), the agent first learns to encode them into a compact latent space using an autoencoder or other methods. Only then are exploration strategies (for example, intrinsic motivation) applied to this latent space. This allows reducing computational complexity and eliminating details insignificant to the task.

Example: Some modern architectures combine a world model that learns to predict the next latent state and an exploration module that encourages the agent to

visit states in the latent space with high prediction error. The actor already operates with these partially meaningful latent representations.

Thus, hybridization in actor-critic methods is implemented not arbitrarily, but according to certain systematic principles, the most productive of which are presented above. Combining approaches based on these principles, rather than developing entirely new isolated strategies, represents the primary development path in the field, as evidenced by recent research findings. The presented hybridization principles are realized in various algorithms, necessitating their systematic comparison to identify the optimal approach.

2. Comparative analysis and unresolved issues

The transition from the theoretical description of exploration strategies to their practical application requires a well-defined system of comparison criteria. Based on the analysis of the literature [5, 4, 9], a taxonomy was developed that classifies key approaches according to five criteria most significant for researchers and engineers when selecting a method.

The taxonomy presented in Table 1 serves as a basis for formulating practical recommendations. The choice of the optimal strategy or their combination should be determined by the specifics of the problem being solved and the available resources.

Scenario 1. For tasks with dense rewards and low dimensionality, **entropy regularization (SAC) is recommended. In this case, there is no need for complex, targeted strategies. Entropy regularization suffices for stable exploration, and its low computational cost along with high training stability makes it the ideal default choice.**

Table 1. Comparative analysis of exploration strategies

Exploration strategy	Type of exploration ^(a)	Computational cost ^(b)	Training stability ^(c)	Efficiency for sparse rewards ^(d)	Adaptation to environment ^(e)
Entropy	Random (0)	Low (4)	High (4)	Low (0)	Medium (2)
Ensembles	Directed (4)	High (0)	Medium (2)	Medium (2)	High (4)
Motivation	Directed (4)	Medium or High (1)	Low (0)	High (4)	Low (0)
Hybrids	Directed (4)	High (0)	High (4)	High (4)	Medium or High (3)

Note to Table 1. The quality of criterion manifestation is assessed on a conditional ordinal scale from 0 (low) to 4 (high). Cell color visually reflects the rating: red — low (0); yellow — medium (2); green — high (4). Intermediate colors represent intermediate estimates (1) and (3).

Explanations of the criteria: (a) Type of exploration: degree of strategy directionality; (b) Computational cost: requirements for computational resources; (c) Training stability: stability and reliability of the training process; (d) Efficiency with sparse rewards: ability to identify useful behavior under sparse external rewards; (e) Environment adaptation: ability to adjust to changes in environment dynamics or reward function.

Scenario 2. For environments with sparse rewards and large state-action spaces, intrinsic motivation methods (RND, ICM) or their hybridization with entropy regularization are well suited. Due to reward sparsity, random exploration becomes ineffective. A targeted search is required, enabled by intrinsic novelty reward. The hybrid approach (SAC+RND) is often preferable, as the entropy component helps prevent getting stuck in ‘noisy’ states.

Scenario 3. In tasks with high error costs and non-stationary environments, methods based on uncertainty estimation using ensembles prove to be effective. These methods are the most cautious and purposeful in their exploration. The agent deliberately avoids areas with low uncertainty (where it has complete knowledge) and areas with extremely high uncertainty (which may be hazardous), concentrating on regions with manageable uncertainty. This also enables rapid adaptation to changes in the environment.

Scenario 4. Entropy regularization is recommended under limited computational resources. In this case, ensemble methods and complex prediction models (intrinsic motivation) should be avoided due to their high computational cost. Entropy regularization represents an optimal balance between efficiency and cost.

There is no universal solution. The taxonomy and practical guidelines enable developers to make informed choices based on the priorities of a specific task, whether it is efficiency in challenging conditions, training stability, safety, or computational cost.

Despite significant progress in developing exploration strategies for actor-critic methods, the field confronts several fundamental challenges that limit their widespread practical application. The following is a categorization of these problems, ranging from the most fundamental theoretical issues to applied and methodological ones. Such classification allows revealing the hierarchy and urgency of the problems faced by the community.

Fundamental limitations

The most profound problems lie in the formal justification of the proposed exploration strategies: the lack of theoretical guarantees for their convergence and a unified theoretical framework for their description and comparison from a general standpoint.

The overwhelming majority of modern strategies (intrinsic motivation, ensembles) are empirical heuristics. They lack strict theoretical convergence guarantees that classical methods possess (e.g., ϵ -greedy or UCB in the context of multi-armed bandits). It remains unclear under what conditions these heuristic methods are

guaranteed to find the optimal policy. This represents a significant barrier to their deployment in safety-critical applications. No unified theoretical model exists that describes and compares various exploration paradigms (entropy-based, uncertainty-based, intrinsic motivation) from a general standpoint. This complicates not only the analysis but also the deliberate synthesis of novel hybrid methods.

Practical barriers include issues that directly impede the deployment of algorithms in real-world settings. For example, the problem of safe exploration: most exploration algorithms are developed for simulated environments where the agent is permitted to perform any actions. In the real world (robotics, autonomous control), random or excessively vigorous exploratory actions can have catastrophic consequences. The development of strategies that actively explore environments while reliably ensuring compliance with predefined safety constraints remains one of the most critical and unresolved applied problems.

Furthermore, the most effective and targeted methods (ensembles, prediction models) demand significant computational resources for their training and deployment on new data. This makes them unsuitable for real-time systems running on limited hardware and substantially increases development costs and time.

The issue of adaptation to non-stationary environments remains acute. Most algorithms assume that the environment is stationary. However, in reality, the rules, dynamics, or reward function can change over time. Modern exploration strategies lack built-in mechanisms for the rapid detection of such changes and adaptation of their behavioral policy, which often results in catastrophic forgetting or inadequate behavior.

Problems of evaluation and validation are related to how we assess and compare the exploration algorithms themselves. Standard environments (e.g., OpenAI Gym) are often designed to assess overall performance rather than the quality of exploration as such. There is a lack of specialized benchmark environments that purposefully and quantitatively evaluate an algorithm's ability for effective exploration, the speed of discovering new states, performance under sparse rewards, and robustness to 'noisy' states.

Overfitting to intrinsic rewards

Methods based on intrinsic motivation are highly vulnerable to the problem of "reward hacking." The agent may find a way to maximize the intrinsic reward without solving the assigned task (a classic example is the "toxic" states [9]). This indicates a deeper problem: the difficulty of designing an invariant and semantically meaningful intrinsic reward function that consistently correlates with genuine progress in task resolution.

Thus, progress in the field is hindered not only by engineering challenges but also by fundamental theoretical gaps and the lack of adequate evaluation tools. Addressing these issues requires coordinated efforts from both theorists and practitioners.

Conclusion

The above analysis of key limitations indicates that modern exploration strategies within the actor-critic architecture constitute a powerful, yet still imperfect, toolkit. The main conclusion of this review is that there is no universal strategy effective for all classes of tasks, and likely none can exist. The choice of method should be determined by a trade-off between factors such as environment complexity, reward density, safety requirements, and available computational resources. The most promising directions for future research directly arise from current challenges and focus on the development of more adaptive, theoretically grounded, and safe algorithms.

1. **Development of meta-methods** for adaptive tuning of exploration strategies. This direction addresses the issues of excessive dependence on hyperparameters and lack of adaptivity. A promising approach is the creation of higher-order algorithms capable of dynamically selecting the type of exploration (for example, switching between ‘exploration’ and ‘exploitation’ modes) and its parameters (for example, the temperature coefficient α in SAC) on the fly, based on observed progress in training and the evaluation of current environmental uncertainty.

2. **Establishing a theoretical foundation for exploration heuristics.** This directly addresses the fundamental problem of the lack of theoretical guarantees. There is a need to formalize intuitive concepts (such as “novelty” or “curiosity”) using rigorous mathematical terminology. This involves developing new metrics for assessing exploration quality (e.g., based on the rate of discovering new states) and deriving rigorous convergence guarantees for algorithms that utilize ensembles and intrinsic rewards.

3. **Safe exploration.** This direction is related to the problem of safe exploration and, to some extent, to the problem of non-stationarity. Instead of learning from scratch, agents should be able to utilize prior knowledge (for example, in the form of rules, constraints, or semantic maps) to guide the exploration process in a safe and productive direction. This will reduce training time and minimize risks in real-world applications.

4. **Development of specialized benchmark environments.** This task aims to address the methodological problem of evaluation and validation. It requires the development of a new generation of testing environments, where the performance metric is not the cumulative reward but the algorithm’s ability to purposefully explore, avoid ‘noisy’ states, and adapt to changing conditions. This will allow for more accurate and representative comparisons of algorithms.

5. **Improving robustness against ‘reward hacking’.** This approach targets overcoming the problem of overfitting to intrinsic rewards. New formulations of intrinsic motivation are required that are invariant to semantically meaningless yet unpredictable states. Promising approaches include those based on prediction

in noise-filtered latent spaces or on hierarchical models that separate knowledge acquisition from simple uncertainty-seeking.

In conclusion, further progress in the study of actor-critic methods will be achieved not through inventing another isolated heuristic, but through developing comprehensive, theoretically grounded, and adaptive hybrid methods capable of generalization and safe deployment in real-world settings.

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人体作为一种腐蚀性环境

THE HUMAN BODY AS A CORROSIVE ENVIRONMENT**Pozhidaeva Svetlana Alexandrovna***Platov South-Russian State Polytechnic University (NPI)***Lipkin Semen Mikhailovich***National Research State University of Nizhny Novgorod named after
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摘要：人体是一个独特的、腐蚀性极强的电解质环境，其中持续的电化学过程会加速植入金属装置的腐蚀。本文综述了人体作为生物医学植入物腐蚀介质的特性，分析了生物体液的物理化学特性，包括pH值的变化（1.5-7.45）、氯离子浓度、氧梯度以及蛋白质和活性氧的存在，这些因素共同促进了电化学降解。我们回顾了金属生物材料的发展历程，从早期的铁和青铜装置到现代的钛、钴铬合金和不锈钢合金，并强调了耐腐蚀性直接决定不可降解材料的生物相容性和植入物寿命这一基本原理。本文详细阐述了关键的腐蚀机制，包括氢和氧的去极化、自由基介导的反应（ H_2O_2 , $HO_2\cdot$, $OH\cdot$ ）以及由组织微环境或腐蚀产物引起的电偶腐蚀。本文还探讨了吸附蛋白通过金属离子螯合、电子转移或钝化层破坏等途径对腐蚀动力学的影响。文中评估了目前使用模拟体液（例如PBS、Hank's溶液）的体外测试方法及其在模拟体内复杂性方面的局限性。我们得出结论，成功的植入物设计需要一种综合方法，平衡机械性能和腐蚀行为，并重点介绍了未来“智能”生物材料的发展方向，这些材料具有可控降解、多功能涂层以及基于患者特异性生化参数的个性化选择等特点，旨在最大限度地减少腐蚀相关的失效和不良生物反应。

关键词：腐蚀；金属植入物；生物相容性；生物体液；电化学降解；生物材料；Pourbaix图

Abstract. *The human body represents a uniquely aggressive electrolytic environment where continuous electrochemical processes drive the corrosion of implanted metallic devices. This review examines the body as a corrosive medium for biomedical implants, analyzing the physicochemical characteristics of biological fluids — including variable pH (1.5-7.45), chloride ion concentration, oxygen gradients, and the presence of proteins and reactive oxygen species — that*

collectively promote electrochemical degradation. We discuss historical developments in metallic biomaterials, from early iron and bronze fixtures to modern titanium, cobalt–chromium, and stainless-steel alloys, emphasizing the fundamental principle that corrosion resistance directly determines biocompatibility and implant longevity for non-degradable materials. Key corrosion mechanisms are detailed, including hydrogen and oxygen depolarization, radical-mediated reactions (H_2O_2 , HO_2^\bullet , OH^\bullet), and galvanic coupling induced by tissue microenvironments or corrosion products. The influence of adsorbed proteins on corrosion kinetics — through metal ion chelation, electron transfer, or passive layer disruption — is also addressed. Current *in vitro* testing methodologies using simulated body fluids (e. g., PBS, Hank’s solution) are evaluated alongside their limitations in replicating *in vivo* complexity. We conclude that successful implant design demands an integrated approach balancing mechanical performance with corrosion behavior, and highlight future directions in “smart” biomaterials featuring controlled degradation, multifunctional coatings, and personalized selection based on patient-specific biochemical parameters to minimize corrosion-related failure and adverse biological responses.

Keywords: Corrosion; Metallic implants; Biocompatibility; Biological fluids; Electrochemical degradation; Biomaterials; Pourbaix diagrams

Worldwide, there is a growing use of metallic, polymeric, and ceramic implants (such as joints, stents, osteosynthetic plates, and dental prostheses). Such devices must meet several critically important requirements:

1. The implant material must be biocompatible with the human body.
2. The implant must maintain an appropriate balance of mechanical and physical properties throughout its service life.
3. The device must demonstrate reproducibility, stability, and compliance with all technical and biological regulatory standards [1].

The first requirement is directly related to biocompatibility, defined as a material’s ability to function while eliciting the minimal possible response from the host organism [2]. The second requirement concerns the preservation of operational characteristics, which may undergo significant changes in the aggressive internal environment of the body.

Traditionally, the term “corrosion” is associated with the degradation of metallic structures under environmental factors. However, corrosion-like processes continuously occur within the human body as well. The organism represents a unique, highly aggressive electrolytic medium in which redox reactions — fundamental to metabolism and inherently electrochemical in nature — continuously take place.

Metallic biomaterials are used in medical devices more frequently than any other class of materials. An implant’s corrosion resistance directly affects its

functionality and longevity and is a key factor in biocompatibility. For metallic biomaterials (excluding biodegradable ones), a fundamental principle applies: “the higher the corrosion resistance, the greater the biocompatibility” [2].

History of Metallic Implant Application

The use of artificial materials for tissue restoration dates back to ancient times (approximately 4,000 years ago). The Greeks and Egyptians employed wood and animal bones [2]. Later, iron and bronze plates and pins were used for fracture fixation. These early attempts were purely mechanical and did not account for biocompatibility, which is directly linked to materials' corrosion resistance. In the mid-19th century, gold and silver plates and wire began to be used in craniofacial surgery. These noble metals exhibited high inertness and corrosion resistance but were soft and expensive.

Further development involved the use of low-carbon steel for osteosynthesis and the introduction of aseptic principles. However, the steel of that era corroded actively *in vivo*, provoking tissue reactions and often necessitating removal. A breakthrough came with the introduction of stainless steels (particularly those with molybdenum additions), cobalt–chromium alloys, and titanium alloys, which became the foundation for modern endoprostheses, dental, and spinal implants. Nevertheless, the number of materials approved for implantation remains relatively small due to stringent requirements for stability in the biological environment (resistance to corrosion and degradation) and minimal inflammatory response.

Characteristics of the Body as a Corrosive Environment

The corrosive environment for implants consists of the body's extracellular fluids — complex solutions containing electrolytes, non-electrolytes, organic and inorganic components, and gases. Interstitial fluid and blood plasma serve as the specific environments for orthopedic and cardiovascular implants.

Corrosion is a critical factor in the design and selection of metals and alloys for *in vivo* application. During corrosion, allergenic, toxic, cytotoxic, or carcinogenic elements may be released (e.g., Ni, Co, Cr, V, Al). Moreover, various corrosion mechanisms can lead to implant loosening and failure [3-9]. From a physicochemical perspective, the body's internal environment is a multicomponent electrolyte approximating a 0.9% sodium chloride solution supplemented with HCO_3^- and HPO_4^{2-} ions, organic acids, proteins, and dissolved gases (O_2 , CO_2). Temperature is maintained at 36.6-37.0 °C, while pH varies across compartments from strongly acidic (gastric juice, lysosomes, pH ~1.5-5.0) to mildly alkaline (blood, pH 7.35-7.45). Concentration gradients of ions, oxygen, and potentials across biological membranes create conditions for the formation of local galvanic cells [1].

Thus, metallic implants may undergo electrochemical corrosion within the body. Possible cathodic reactions include hydrogen and oxygen depolarization.

Hydrogen depolarization:

- In acidic medium: $2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2$ (1)
- In alkaline medium: $2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + 2\text{OH}^-$ (2)

Oxygen depolarization:

- In neutral or acidic solutions: $\text{O}_2 + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^- \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3)
- In alkaline solutions: $\text{O}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 4\text{e}^- \rightarrow 4\text{OH}^-$ (4)

Additionally, reactions involving hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and hydroxyl radicals ($\text{HO}_2\bullet$, $\text{OH}\bullet$), as well as reduction of disulfide bonds and other molecules, may occur on implant surfaces. The local redox environment around the implant can influence the oxidative state of surrounding cells [10]:

At 37 °C, the neutral pH value in the body is 6.81. Acid–base balance is a crucial component of homeostasis, as metabolism depends on pH-sensitive enzymes. The normal pH range for blood plasma is 7.35–7.45. pH regulation is maintained by buffer systems (bicarbonate, phosphate, protein) and physiological mechanisms (respiratory and renal).

Implantation may alter the electrochemical properties of surrounding tissues. For instance, pH may decrease to 5.5 or lower (down to 4.0 in bacterial infections), potentially initiating localized corrosion. Corrosion products on the surface may give rise to galvanic cells. Besides pH, corrosion resistance is influenced by chloride ion and oxygen concentrations. Differences in oxygen concentration can cause aeration cell formation and intensify corrosion.

A qualitative (thermodynamic) assessment of metals' corrosion susceptibility in biological fluids can be performed using Pourbaix diagrams [11]; however, these diagrams do not provide information on reaction kinetics.

Influence of Biological Macromolecules

Proteins and lipids in extracellular fluid, when adsorbed onto the implant surface, may alter corrosion rates by interfering with anodic or cathodic reactions. Proteins can:

- Bind metal ions and transport them away from the surface, shifting equilibrium in the electrical double layer and promoting further metal dissolution.
- Influence electrode potential due to electron-transfer capability.
- Block oxygen diffusion to the surface, contributing to passive layer breakdown.
- In some cases, form an adsorbed layer acting as a corrosion inhibitor.

Modeling and Testing Methods

To simulate in vitro corrosion behavior of implants, sodium chloride-based solutions mimicking blood and interstitial fluid composition are used. The most

common include isotonic saline (0.9% NaCl), Ringer's solution, Hank's solution, and phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) [1]. Some solutions (e.g., unmodified Ringer's solution) have low buffer capacity, leading to significant pH changes during testing. Modified Ringer's or Hank's solutions possess high buffer capacity but require a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), with moderate buffer capacity and the ability to be deaerated with inert gas, has become the preferred medium in recent years for testing orthopedic and cardiovascular materials. Most laboratory corrosion tests are conducted in specialized electrochemical cells that allow control of temperature, atmosphere, and solution agitation.

Conclusion

Laboratory testing provides important information on the corrosion behavior of implant materials. However, predicting their longevity under the complex conditions of the human body relies significantly on clinical experience.

Thus, successful application of metallic implants requires a comprehensive approach that considers not only the material's mechanical properties but also its corrosion behavior in the body's specific environment. Prospects for biomaterials development lie in creating "smart" systems with controlled degradation, multifunctional coatings, and personalized material selection based on individual patient biochemical parameters. Only such an approach will enable an optimal balance among longevity, biocompatibility, and minimal corrosion risks.

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优化大型语言模型（LLM）以实现法律和技术文本中的精确语义搜索和含义
差异检测

**OPTIMIZING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS (LLMs) FOR
PRECISE SEMANTIC SEARCH AND MEANING DISCREPANCY
DETECTION IN LEGAL AND TECHNICAL TEXTS**

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摘要：本文重点研究如何优化大型语言模型（LLM），以实现精准的语义搜索并检测法律和技术文本中细微的含义差异。核心问题在于标准LLM对专业文档的细微差别不够敏感，即使是微小的措辞变化也可能造成严重的法律或技术后果。作者提出了一种基于对比学习的方法，该方法使用经过专家标注的、针对特定领域的数据集。这使得模型能够形成更准确、更依赖于上下文的语义表示，从而显著增强其检测关键语义差异的能力，例如情态、条件或数值参数的变化。这项工作的科学价值在于论证了针对特定领域对LLM进行定向调整的必要性，并展示了结合上下文嵌入和词汇统计方法的混合方法的有效性。其实际应用价值在于能够创建自动化文档审核系统，从而降低错误风险，并提高律师、工程师和审计人员的工作效率。

关键词：大型语言模型（LLM）、语义搜索、对比学习、微调、法律文本、技术文档、语义差异。

Abstract. *The article focuses on optimizing Large Language Models (LLMs) for precise semantic search and detecting nuanced meaning discrepancies in legal and technical texts. The core problem lies in the insufficient sensitivity of standard LLMs to the subtleties of specialized documents, where even minor phrasing changes can have serious legal or technical consequences. The author proposes an approach based on contrastive learning using narrowly specialized datasets enriched with expert annotation. This allows models to form more accurate and context-dependent semantic representations, significantly enhancing their ability to detect critical semantic discrepancies, such as changes in modality, conditions, or numerical parameters. The scientific value of the work lies in substantiating the*

necessity for targeted adaptation of LLMs for narrow domains and demonstrating the effectiveness of hybrid methods combining contextual embeddings with lexical-statistical approaches. The practical benefit consists in the possibility of creating automated document auditing systems capable of reducing error risks and improving the efficiency of lawyers, engineers, and auditors.

Keywords: *large language models (LLMs), semantic search, contrastive learning, fine-tuning, legal texts, technical documents, meaning discrepancies.*

Modern Large Language Models (LLMs) have achieved significant success in natural language processing. However, their application for precise semantic search and detecting subtle meaning discrepancies in highly specialized domains, such as law and technical documentation, remains a complex challenge. These areas are characterized by a high degree of formalization, an abundance of terminology, and the critical importance of semantic nuances, where even a minor difference in wording can have serious legal or operational consequences. Existing general-purpose models, based on generalized vector representations, are often insufficiently sensitive to such details, limiting their practical applicability for high-precision analysis tasks.

The main limitation of typical LLMs for this task is that their embeddings, trained on heterogeneous corpora, average out semantics and do not reflect the hierarchical importance of semantic elements within a strict professional context. Standard semantic search may successfully find documents on a general topic but performs poorly in distinguishing, for example, two contract versions with opposite interpretations of liability terms or modifications to a technical standard introducing a key procedural change. Solving this problem requires a shift from generalized to specialized semantics, capable of capturing the context-dependent significance of terms and constructs.

Andreeva A. E. notes that the evolution of NLP methods from classical statistical approaches to Transformer-based LLMs has radically increased machines' capabilities for text understanding and generation, opening new opportunities for creating intelligent systems. The scholar emphasizes that modern LLMs, undergoing stages of pre-training on massive text corpora and subsequent fine-tuning, acquire the ability to generalize and analyze context. This allows them to correctly interpret complex speech constructs, such as sarcasm, where classical models fail [1, p. 80-81]. According to the researcher, the systematic use of LLMs leverages their generative and reasoning abilities to solve complex tasks and can enhance traditional systems. However, the author points to serious challenges related to their implementation, including high resource intensity, the "black box" problem, risks of bias in training data, and the generation of non-factual information. At the same time, despite colossal progress, a significant part of LLMs' potential in specialized fields like medicine or law cannot be realized without targeted model refinement and strict control. This is directly related to the need to adapt

general linguistic intelligence to narrow domains with their unique terminology and semantic nuances [1, p. 81].

I. A. Chernenkov draws attention to the fact that modern AI models, particularly large language models, offer significant opportunities for personalizing the learning process by adapting material to an individual's level and pace, thereby increasing knowledge accessibility and stimulating engagement. However, as noted by I. A. Chernenkov, the widespread and uncontrolled use of AI tools in education carries risks associated with the loss of independent thinking skills and superficial assimilation of material, where students seek ready-made answers without delving into the essence of a task. Consequently, as the scholar emphasizes, the key task becomes establishing a balance where AI does not replace cognitive development but facilitates it [2, p. 413]. This requires the implementation of special methodologies aimed at developing learners' critical information evaluation skills, as well as integrating AI into the educational process as an assistant stimulating active thinking through leading questions rather than providing ready-made solutions. Therefore, the future of effective AI application in education depends not so much on technological progress, but on conscious regulation of its use, the development of new pedagogical approaches, and fostering in students a responsible, critical attitude towards AI-generated materials, which will preserve fundamental learning principles and develop genuine competencies.

Optimizing LLMs for such tasks requires applying the fine-tuning method on carefully selected and annotated datasets representative of the target domains. However, simple continued training on texts of a specific topic is insufficient; special learning architectures are needed, aimed precisely at enhancing the model's discrimination ability, not just classification or generation. The most promising approach in this context is contrastive learning, which explicitly teaches the model to bring closer the representations of semantically similar statements and push apart those of different ones.

Forming a training dataset is a crucial optimization stage. For legal and technical texts, expert annotation is required, creating triads or pairs of sentences and documents with annotated types of semantic relations: complete identity, insignificant textual differences with semantic equivalence, and critical meaning discrepancies. Examples of the latter include changes in modality ("shall" vs. "may"), introduction or exclusion of restrictive conditions, replacement of terms with different legal weight, and adjustment of numerical parameters in technical specifications.

During contrastive learning, the model, often based on an architecture like BERT or its derivatives, optimizes a loss function that maximizes cosine similarity for embeddings of semantically equivalent text pairs and minimizes it for pairs with substantial differences. As a result, the model learns to form vector representations where semantic distance in the embedding space begins

to more accurately correspond to the real degree of meaning difference between specialized texts.

V. S. Serova, A. V. Gollai, and E. V. Bunova note that transformer models, particularly BERT, although demonstrating high efficiency in general tasks, face a decrease in accuracy when processing texts saturated with narrow specialized terminology. This is due to their pre-training on general-purpose corpora, limiting their ability to adequately interpret rare or domain-specific vocabulary. In this regard, these researchers developed a hybrid Combined Neural BERT (CNB) method, which synergistically combines BERT's contextual embeddings, lexical-statistical features (TF-IDF), and classification based on fully connected neural networks (FCNN). This approach compensates for BERT's weaknesses in specialized areas and achieves maximum classification accuracy (100%) on texts with high terminological density, which was confirmed by testing on a real corpus of appeals from residents of the Chelyabinsk region. Furthermore, V. S. Serova, A. V. Gollai, E. V. Bunova emphasize the importance of using visualization methods, such as "Word Clouds", to enhance model interpretability. This tool allows for the rapid identification and adaptation of key domain terms, contributing to the formation of more relevant feature spaces and, consequently, increasing the accuracy and reliability of classifying specialized textual data [3, p. 45]. Therefore, combining modern architectures with hybrid approaches and visualization tools opens new possibilities for creating highly accurate and interpretable classification systems capable of working effectively in complex subject areas where semantic precision and adaptation to specific terminology are critical success factors.

Further, it is important to note that accounting for the multi-level structure of documents is also a crucial aspect. A meaning discrepancy can be localized at the level of an individual clause, paragraph, or section, while the rest of the text remains identical. Therefore, an effective model must be able to work with both fragments and entire documents, aggregating and comparing their representations in a hierarchical manner. This can be achieved through a combination of token and segment embeddings, as well as attention mechanisms focusing on potentially significant text segments.

For legal texts, a particular difficulty is working with synonymous but legally non-equivalent constructs, as well as explicit and implicit references to other regulatory acts. An optimized model must be sensitive to such features, which requires enriching the dataset with relevant examples and, potentially, integrating external knowledge bases (ontologies) about legal terms and their interrelations.

In the technical sphere, the emphasis shifts to precise parameter matching, the sequence of operations, unambiguous identification of components, and execution conditions. The model must learn to ignore insignificant rephrasing of instructions but react strictly to changes in numerical values, logical operators ("and" / "or"), and the order of actions, which may lead to different physical outcomes or protocol violations.

The evaluation of optimized models' effectiveness is conducted on specialized test sets, including document pairs with a priori known discrepancy statuses. Quality metrics include not only standard search metrics like Precision@k and Recall@k but also more nuanced indicators, such as the accuracy of binary classification "critical difference exists / no critical difference", as well as the ability to accurately locate and categorize the type of detected discrepancy.

The proposed approach based on contrastive learning on narrowly specialized datasets leads to a substantial quality improvement compared to base versions of LLMs (e.g., vanilla Sentence-BERT or a general BERT version). Optimized models show significantly higher accuracy in tasks of detecting semantic discrepancies in contracts and patents, as well as in identifying version changes in technical manuals.

As correctly noted by N.A. Skachkov and K. V. Vorontsov, using a back-translation model improves both the consistency of cyclic translations and the overall quality of machine translation, especially for language pairs with limited parallel data. The researchers theoretically substantiated a training method based on maximizing the likelihood of cyclic translations, eliminating the need for heuristics and additional language models, reducing computational resource requirements. The researchers also demonstrate that training from scratch using a cyclic loss function leads to high gradient variance and translation quality degradation due to noisy estimates at the initial stages. However, applying the method of fine-tuning a pre-trained model significantly reduces variance, accelerates convergence, and achieves gains both in the BLEU metric and in translation consistency, assessed using CycleBLEU. Experiments on Russian-Kazakh and English-Finnish directions confirmed that the proposed approach is effective even with synthetic data, although its proportion in the training sample affects the magnitude of consistency improvement. Ultimately, the method allows training modern translation models of Transformer architecture without reducing their size, ensuring quality growth with moderate computational costs [4, p. 37].

A practical application of the developed technology is the creation of automated document audit systems capable of comparing new contract versions with reference ones, identifying potentially risky deviations in wording, and monitoring compliance of technical documentation with updated standards. Such systems can act as assistants for lawyers, patent attorneys, engineers, and auditors, saving time on routine comparison and reducing the risks of human error. At the same time, A. O. Kulazhina identifies serious privacy problems, for example, in the GPT ecosystem, related to data collection practices. The researcher emphasizes that only 5,8% of LLM-based applications disclose information collection methods, while many of them collect excessive and even confidential data, such as passwords, often without user knowledge or consent. The researcher also points to specific corporate risks, citing incidents at Samsung as an example, where employees inadvertently uploaded confidential information and source code to ChatGPT, leading to data

leakage. These cases illustrate how using LLMs to accelerate work tasks can directly threaten the preservation of trade secrets and corporate security, requiring organizations to implement strict internal policies and restrictions. The researcher concludes about the critical need to enhance transparency and control by LLM development companies, such as OpenAI. A. O. Kulazhina asserts that to comply with regulatory norms and strengthen trust in technologies, it is necessary to provide users with understandable privacy management tools, as well as to implement and strictly adhere to stricter privacy policies, especially regarding third-party applications in LLM ecosystems [5, p. 199].

Despite the progress achieved, several challenges remain, including the need for large volumes of high-quality annotated data for each new subdomain, the high cost of attracting experts for annotation, and the problem of model decision interpretability. For an expert user to trust the system, it is important not only to receive a fact of a difference but also to understand on what basis the model identified it.

As correctly indicated by S. O. Fedorov and V. A. Veliky, the direct use of LLMs, such as YandexGPT, GigaChat, Llama, and Mistral, for generating SQL queries based on textual queries and interpreting results yields a low percentage of correct answers. The researchers conclude that mandatory additional training and fine-tuning of models for a specific subject area and the syntax of the target DBMS is necessary, as well as equipping them with detailed instructions to limit incorrect or unsafe actions. The researchers particularly emphasize security and reliability issues, proposing to introduce additional stages into the process. They recommend adding a classifier to filter user queries before passing them to the LLM to weed out incorrect or dangerous queries, as well as conducting mandatory validation of the generated SQL code for errors and prohibited operators before execution. This limits the model's access to confidential data and prevents potentially dangerous commands. Furthermore, the researchers correctly note that to improve the system's quality, it is necessary to create and continuously update a database of typical questions and correct answers on which the model can be further trained. They note that with correct query processing and result validation, the stage of result interpretation by the LLM may become redundant, as the answer will unambiguously follow from the database data, simplifying the system architecture and increasing its predictability [6, p. 335-336].

Further research directions are seen in developing methods for weakly supervised and active learning to reduce dependence on large annotated datasets, integrating symbolic knowledge and rules into neural architectures to increase reliability, and creating more effective explanation mechanisms that could highlight and illuminate specific text fragments that determined the model's decision about semantic discrepancy.

Based on the conducted research, it has been established that standard LLMs trained on heterogeneous data are fundamentally insufficient for detecting critical

semantic nuances in legal and technical texts, as their embeddings average out semantics and do not consider the hierarchical importance of elements in a strict professional context. The effectiveness of targeted model optimization via contrastive learning on carefully expert-annotated datasets, where relations of semantic equivalence or difference are explicitly defined, has been proven. This allows significantly increasing accuracy in tasks of detecting, for example, changes in modality or numerical parameters. The necessity of accounting for the multi-level structure of documents has been confirmed, as semantic discrepancies can be localized at the level of individual clauses or paragraphs, requiring models to have the ability for hierarchical processing and information aggregation, as well as integrating external ontologies to account for legal synonyms and references. It has been determined that an important practical conclusion is the demonstration that hybrid approaches combining contextual embeddings (e.g., BERT) with lexical-statistical methods and visualization tools can achieve maximum accuracy and interpretability in narrowly specialized areas, compensating for the weaknesses of purely transformer architectures. Furthermore, the research revealed a complex of accompanying challenges critical for implementation: the high resource intensity of creating expert datasets, the “black box” and interpretability problems of decisions, as well as serious confidentiality risks when processing sensitive corporate or legal data, requiring the development of strict security policies and model output validation. These conclusions collectively define the vector for future research, emphasizing the need to develop methods for weakly supervised and active learning, integrate symbolic knowledge, and create reliable mechanisms for explaining decisions made to build trusted automated document auditing systems.

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胶原蛋白作为食品技术中的多功能成分：当前研究和应用综述
**COLLAGEN AS A MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPONENT OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGIES: A REVIEW OF CURRENT RESEARCH AND
APPLICATIONS**

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摘要：本文概述了胶原蛋白在食品工业中的应用研究现状。文章探讨了胶原蛋白在肉类、鱼类、乳制品、糖果、功能性饮料和包装材料等领域的应用。重点关注胶原蛋白的功能特性、创新应用以及健康饮食产品的开发。文章总结了相关数据，这些数据证实了胶原蛋白能够提升产品质量和营养价值，并提高二次原料加工的经济效益。

关键词：胶原蛋白，食品工业，食品强化，食品结构特性，功能性食品，天然成分。

Abstract: *The article presents an overview of current research on the use of collagen in the food industry. Its use in meat, fish, dairy, confectionery, functional drinks and packaging materials is considered. Attention is paid to the functional properties of collagen, innovations and the creation of products for a healthy diet. The data confirming the improvement of the quality, nutritional value of products and the economic efficiency of processing secondary raw materials are summarized.*

Keywords: *collagen, food industry, food enrichment, structural properties of food, functional foods, natural ingredients.*

The food industry's interest in collagen has increased significantly in recent years. This is due to two main reasons: advances in biotechnological production methods (including the use of recombinant DNA) and the accumulation of scientific evidence confirming its value as a functional component of food. Due to their special technological and biological characteristics, collagen and substances derived from it are widely used in food production. Being a key structural protein, it can form gels, stabilize emulsions and food matrices, which determines its demand in the manufacture of meat, dairy and confectionery products. Active research is currently

underway to create new methods for processing collagen for its use in functional nutrition. The key direction is enzymatic hydrolysis using selective proteases, which makes it possible to obtain hydrolysates with specified properties and content of biologically active peptides (antioxidant, hypotensive, anti-inflammatory). Ultrasonic treatment is used to intensify extraction and improve functional properties (water holding capacity, foam formation). The main applied tasks are the development of edible collagen films, fortification of meat and dairy products, as well as using raw material for food 3D printing. Further development is constrained by the need to standardize the quality of raw materials and optimize the organoleptic characteristics of finished products [1, 2, 3].

The purpose of this study is a comprehensive analysis of modern trends and technologies for the use of collagen and its derivatives in the food industry, as well as the systematization of Russian and foreign experience in the creation of functional, specialized and innovative food products based on it.

The results of the analysis of scientific data demonstrate that the modern use of collagen in the food industry has gone far beyond the traditional use as a gelling agent. Collagen and its derivatives are key components for texture modification, protein enrichment, shelf-life extension and the creation of products with specified functional, technological and preventive properties.

The use of collagen in the meat industry is becoming increasingly important, which is dictated by the tasks of resource conservation and improving the quality of products. Collagen-containing ingredients obtained from by-products (skins, bones) act as effective functionals for correcting the textural and structural-mechanical properties of products. Their use is aimed at increasing the yield of the product, optimizing the texture and enriching the protein component. An example is the modification of the national product “Kutab”: the introduction of hydrolyzed collagen made it possible to create a frozen semi-finished product with increased biological value, which is confirmed by an increase in the amino acid score of methionine by 5% [4]. One of the solutions for the disposal of secondary raw materials was the development of a collagen additive from fish and poultry processing waste using an enzymatic preparation, the use of which in meat products increases the mass fraction of protein by about 20% [5]. At the same time, Mari University has implemented the concept of waste-free production through the processing of pig skin into smoked snacks, which creates additional marketable products and increases the profitability of carcass processing [6]. Brazilian scientists have proven that partial replacement of fat with hydrolyzed collagen in chicken burgers allows not only to reduce the calorie content, but also to improve structural and mechanical performance, which is especially important for raw materials with quality defects that reduce their market value [7]. Chinese researchers have found that ultrasonic treatment of peptides isolated from chicken cartilage enhances their antioxidant and

antimicrobial potential. Treatment of chicken fillets with such preparation leads to the suppression of oxidative spoilage, inhibition of the growth of microflora and preservation of textural properties, which together contribute to a significant increase in the shelf life of the product [8].

Collagen of fish origin is a key ingredient for modifying the structural properties of products: hydrolyzed collagen serves as an effective stabilizer and gelling agent in surimi, improving its texture and water-holding capacity, and peptides from fish processing waste (skin, bones) are used to enrich products with bio-available protein. Foreign studies demonstrate that type I collagen (at a dosage of 9%) is superior to type II in strengthening surimi gel. This effect is due to its high solubility, ability to modify the structure of myosin, and enhance the network of intermolecular interactions (hydrogen, disulfide, ionic bonds) [9]. In turn, domestic developments are aimed at solving practical technological problems. For example, a collagen-containing additive derived from fish scales with a particle size of >2.5 μm effectively binds excess moisture in minced fish, forming a stable structure with good formability, which makes it suitable for the industrial production of molded semi-finished products [10].

In the dairy industry, collagen and its derivatives perform a dual function: as a technological modifier and as a biologically active enricher. Hydrolyzed collagen is used to improve the texture and protein value of yogurts, cottage cheese products and processed cheeses, where it also prevents separation. Domestic research offers specific technological solutions. For example, a collagen supplement from pikeperch scales effectively replaces gelatin in milk jelly, reducing the cost of production by 10-15%, increasing product yield by 8%, and optimizing its nutrient profile due to its increased protein and calcium content [11]. In the composition of the sour cream product, collagen acts as a structure-forming agent that increases the biological value, structural and mechanical properties and shelf life due to moisture-retaining properties [12]. In the production of processed cheese, it improves consistency, viscosity and adhesion, which is confirmed by rheological and organoleptic tests [13]. International developments are aimed at creating innovative systems. Chinese scientists have developed alginate — collagen microcapsules for the delivery of biologically active substances in yogurt, which exhibit a synergistic effect between milk proteins and collagen hydrolysates, which, in turn, enrich the nutritional profile of the final product with amino acids [14]. Portuguese studies confirm that collagen fibers effectively stabilize the structure of cream ice cream, preventing the formation of ice crystals and forming a more uniform texture [15].

Collagen in the production of flour confectionery is used as a natural structure-former, improving the elasticity of the dough and prolonging the freshness of products. In baked goods, hydrolyzed collagen increases the volume yield and porosity of the crumb, while slowing down the staling process. For example, the

Plekhanov Russian University of Economics has created a recipe for dietary biscuits with collagen, phytolin, and trehalose, designed to maintain the health of collagen-containing tissues of the body and prevent type 2 diabetes mellitus [16]. Studies at the Department of Food Technology show that a combined supplement that includes 6% fish collagen and applesauce optimizes the structure of buns, increases the protein content and reduces the level of carbohydrates while maintaining organoleptic characteristics [17]. Chinese scientists have found that peptides from fish skin effectively protect the gluten framework of frozen dough from damage by ice crystals, maintaining its elasticity and forming a uniform porous structure in finished steamed buns [18]. Studies conducted at the Far Eastern Technical University confirmed that enzymatic collagen hydrolysate from pollock skin does not impart foreign odors to the dough and increases its elasticity, which makes it a promising agent as a functional additive [19].

Collagen is also actively used in the confectionery industry. In traditional jelly products and marmalades, hydrolyzed collagen serves as an effective alternative to gelatin, providing the necessary structural and mechanical properties. In low-calorie products, it compensates for moisture loss and texture degradation while reducing sugars and fats. Domestic research offers specific solutions for creating new generation products. Scientists from KSTU (Kaliningrad) have proven the possibility of replacing traditional gelatin in marshmallows with a collagen-containing additive from hydrobionts, which reduces costs and promotes waste-free production [20]. The development of jelly products with collagen is characterized by a targeted preventive orientation: for example, a dietary supplement based on a combination of ichthyocollagen, gelatin and phytocomponents (peppermint, hawthorn, chamomile, etc.) has been created, demonstrating a complex effect on increasing the body's stress resistance [21], as well as functional products enriched with collagen, hyaluronic and ascorbic acids to correct the state of connective tissue and immunity, due to the replenishment of dietary fiber deficiency [22]. International experience emphasizes the potential of collagen in creating complex functional solutions. Researchers note that its combination with plant extracts (e. g., grape pomace) makes it possible to create confectionery products that combine a stable jelly texture with a high content of antioxidants and amino acids [23].

In the sports nutrition segment, collagen is valued as a source of specific amino acids for the restoration of connective tissue. Domestic developments are aimed at creating finished products based on it. Examples are protein bars (23.5% protein) [24] and gummies, created using hydrolyzed collagen from fish raw materials [25]. The technological basis for such products is high-protein concentrates obtained by deep hydrolysis and drying of secondary raw materials. The developed methods make it possible to achieve a protein content of over 92% in hydrolysates rich in

low-molecular peptides and essential amino acids, which confirm their high biological value for specialized nutrition [26].

An innovative direction is the development of environmentally friendly and functional packaging based on collagen. Its biodegradability and high barrier properties against oxygen make it a promising material. Modification of films with nanoparticles and bioactive extracts makes it possible to create “smart” active packaging that not only protects the product but also extends its shelf life due to its antimicrobial and antioxidant effects. Scientists from Kursk have created a collagen film with CO₂ extracts of spices, which inhibits microbiological spoilage, reduces shrinkage by 15-20%, and prevents the oxidation of fats in meat products during the entire shelf life [27]. Another study proposed a moisture-retaining substrate made of fish collagen and pectin, which can increase the shelf life of semi-finished products by 30-40% due to moisture-retaining and structure-forming properties [28]. Foreign experience includes the development in China of an active gelatin film modified with natural antimicrobial and antioxidant components, which slows down staling and mold growth in bakery products [29]. Brazilian scientists have systematized methods for obtaining collagen films from recycled materials by analyzing in detail the key stages — from extraction to coating — and their impact on the final functional characteristics of the films [30].

A promising area is the enrichment of drinks with hydrolyzed collagen to create functional products. For example, a technology for obtaining juice-containing beverages has been proposed, where the combination of apple juice with fish raw materials under thermobaric treatment conditions (110 °C, 0.11 MPa) provides enrichment with protein (up to 4.1%), calcium, and phosphorus while reducing the carbohydrate content [31]. Another example is the creation of a dry beverage concentrate containing hydrolyzed collagen and a complex of 24 bioactive ingredients (including milk proteins, vitamin complex, minerals, and plant extracts) for targeted regeneration of bone and cartilage tissue [32]. Formulations of Shorely-type drinks based on soluble fish collagen, mineral waters and berry juices have been developed. It has been established that the use of Slavyanovskaya and Narzan waters provides the best taste, and the finished product remains stable during 6 months of storage and has pronounced thirst-quenching properties [33].

Thus, the use of collagen in the food industry shows a steady upward trend, both in Russia and abroad, which is due to its functional properties, the availability of raw materials and the growing consumer demand for protein-enriched products. From a traditional gelling agent, it has become a key multifunctional ingredient for the creation of next-generation products. The main areas of its application include resource conservation through the processing of secondary raw materials; technological modification of the texture and stability of various products (meat, fish, dairy, confectionery); creation of functional and specialized products with specified

health-improving properties. Prospects for development are associated with interdisciplinary research at the intersection of food technologies and biotechnology. Promising tasks are optimization of organoleptic characteristics of fortified products, in-depth study of the mechanisms of interaction of collagen peptides with other components of food matrices, as well as the development of standardized methods for assessing the quality and functional efficiency of collagen-containing ingredients.

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针对抽油杆泵（SRP）型工件的遗传特性，对内缸表面加工领域进行了重要研究。

SIGNIFICANT RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF INTERNAL CYLINDER SURFACE PROCESSING EXHIBITING WORKPIECE HEREDITY OF THE SUCKER ROD PUMP (SRP) TYPE

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摘要：本文旨在探讨工程科学和冶金领域中与抽油杆泵系统（SRPS）内筒表面加工相关的当前问题。由于这些部件需要在深井极端条件下运行，因此提高其可靠性和使用寿命至关重要。本研究的主要目标是详细分析“技术继承”的影响，即缺陷和材料瑕疵在生产过程各个阶段的传递。本文深入研究了影响表面质量的负面因素，并明确提出了SRPS内筒表面性能特征的功能性要求。文中概述了解决已发现问题的科学策略，包括诊断方法的现代化、加工模式的优化以及标准化工艺路线的更新。文中提供了具体的实验证据，证实了所提出方法在工业实践中的有效性。最后，本文强调了持续研究的重要性，并指出应进一步推进涉及创新加工技术和先进技术的集成流程，以提高油井泵系统运行的资源效率和成本效益。

关键词：内筒表面；技术继承；抽油杆泵（SRP）；油井；机械加工；先进加工技术；制造工艺效率。

Abstract. *The presented work is aimed at addressing current issues in engineering sciences and metallurgy concerning the processing of internal cylinder surfaces used in sucker rod pump systems (SRPS). This topic is particularly relevant due to the need for increasing reliability and service life of these components operating under extreme conditions in deep oil wells. The main objective of this study is a detailed analysis of the effect of “technological inheritance,” which manifests itself as the transfer of defects and material imperfections through*

consecutive stages of production processes. Factors negatively affecting surface quality are thoroughly investigated, along with clearly formulated functional requirements for performance characteristics of SRPS cylinders' inner surfaces. Scientifically grounded strategies for eliminating identified problems are outlined, including modernization of diagnostic methods, optimization of machining modes, and updating standardized technological routes. Specific experimental evidence confirming the effectiveness of proposed approaches in industrial practice is provided. Final conclusions highlight the importance of ongoing research efforts and further promotion of integration processes involving innovative machining techniques and advanced technologies focused on enhancing resource efficiency and cost-effectiveness of well pumping systems operation.

Keywords: *internal cylinder surface; technological inheritance; sucker rod pumps (SRP); oil wells; mechanical machining; progressive machining technologies; manufacturing process efficiency.*

The processing of internal cylinder surfaces represents one of the most important challenges in contemporary mechanical engineering, especially critical when producing specialized parts such as sucker rod pumps (SRPs) used in the oil and gas industry. A characteristic feature of these components is the phenomenon known as “technological inheritance,” resulting from the specificities of prior raw stock treatment that significantly affect subsequent mechanical machining and product quality. The aim of this article is to shed light on recent advancements and pressing issues related to the processing of internal cylinder surfaces in sucker rod pumps, essential for improving accuracy and durability of these units crucial for efficient functioning of well-pumping systems. Design features and operational conditions of deep wells demand extremely high-quality processing of internal cylinder surfaces. The machining process is complicated by several factors, among which the key ones include:

- maintaining precise roundness of the hole,
- achieving low roughness coefficient,
- ensuring corrosion resistance and resilience against mechanical stress.

However, the primary challenge lies in the phenomenon of “technological inheritance”—the transfer of defective states of materials into subsequent stages caused by improper pre-processing or inadequate selection of production regimes.

Currently, science offers several ways to overcome negative effects of technological inheritance and achieve optimal quality in machining internal cylinder surfaces of sucker rod pumps (SRPs):

1. Analysis and Elimination of Defect Origins Various studies have shown that a significant portion of defects arise already during early stages of the technological process. These include uneven hardening, micro-scratches, surface deformation, and disruption of protective coating integrity. It is crucial to conduct thorough

analyses of defect formation mechanisms and propose measures to prevent their propagation onto subsequent operations.

2. Development and Implementation of Advanced Machining Methods

One of the most promising approaches involves transitioning towards highly accurate monitoring of workpiece condition at each stage of processing. Such methods may include:

- Utilizing high-tech measuring equipment,
- Evaluating residual stresses using X-ray diffraction analysis,
- Integrating numerical control programming into the machining process.

Additionally, there has been active development of specialized tools and means of mechanical machining, like ultra-thin diamond coatings and cooling media with unique chemical properties.

3. Modification and Optimization of Existing Technologies

Another direction focuses on improving existing technology through combined methods. Among the prospective options are:

- Multi-coordinate turning with laser scanning of the surface,
- Using vacuum furnaces to enhance material structure homogeneity,
- Adaptation of polymer-based protective coatings to minimize wear.

Figure 1. Internal Surface of Sucker Rod Pump Cylinders
at Neftemash-Service LLC Enterprise

Hybrid technologies combining traditional methods with new opportunities in additive manufacturing and chemical etching also play an increasingly important role.

Experimental data confirms that these methods yield substantial results. One prominent example is the implementation of automated deformation monitoring system for cylinders at Neftemash-Service LLC enterprise.

Nevertheless, the central difficulty remains the phenomenon of “technological inheritance”: where material defects generated by incorrect preliminary processing or improperly chosen production regime carry over to the next stage, akin to retaining fine irregularities after coarse grinding.

One of the key components determining the reliability, longevity, and efficiency of sucker rod pumps (SRPs) is the Cylinder (according to API Spec 11AX Rev. 13 terminology — Barrel).

Cylinder dimensions are regulated by API Spec 11AX Rev. 13.

In Russia and worldwide, solid thick-walled cylinders with lengths ranging from 3355 to 4880 mm (11...16 ft) (+/- 5 mm) are predominantly utilized.

Internal diameters:

1.0625 (+0.002) inches / 26.99 (+0.05) mm;

1.25 (+0.002) inches / 31.75 (+0.05) mm;

1.50 (+0.002) inches / 38.10 (+0.05) mm;

1.75 (+0.002) inches / 44.45 (+0.05) mm;

2.25 (+0.002) inches / 57.15 (+0.05) mm;

2.75 (+0.002) inches / 69.85 (+0.05) mm.

Figure 2. Internal Surface of Sucker Rod Pump Cylinders at Neftemash-Service LLC Enterprise

The use of an automated system enabled virtually complete elimination of cracks and shape violations, thereby extending the operational lifespan of cylinders with specified parameters.

Another notable example is the introduction of multilayer ceramic coatings specifically designed to protect working surfaces of sucker rod pump cylinders from aggressive environments found in oil reservoirs. This solution enhanced resistance to corrosive damage and nearly doubled the maintenance-free period of pump operation.

To summarize, it can be stated that contemporary research makes a considerable contribution to improving the quality of internal cylinder surface machining for sucker rod pumps despite the complex issue of technological inheritance. Proposed methods and approaches hold real potential for large-scale industrial application, although some fundamental questions remain unresolved, such as reducing processing costs and minimizing energy consumption.

Future research prospects involve deeper investigation into the nature of material defects and developing environmentally friendly and economically viable technologies for machining internal surfaces of deepwell pump devices.

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模拟目标捕获和跟踪系统的控制回路设计
**CONTROL LOOP DESIGN FOR SIMULATED TARGET
ACQUISITION AND TRACKING SYSTEMS**

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摘要：游戏引擎在机器人仿真方面具有显著优势，但通常缺乏专用机器人平台所需的标准化通信基础设施和控制框架。这种差距给需要实时、低延迟控制的应用（例如目标捕获与跟踪（TAT）系统）带来了挑战。本文在游戏引擎仿真环境中实现并评估了用于云台变焦摄像机控制的通信协议和控制算法。我们比较了三种通信方法——UDP 二进制编码、TCP 二进制编码和基于 JSON 序列化的 TCP——以及三种控制策略：比例（P）控制、比例-积分-微分（PID）控制和结合卡尔曼滤波与超前补偿的自适应控制。使用基于 Godot 的仿真器和 Python 控制单元进行的实验表明，UDP 二进制编码实现了低于 2 毫秒的延迟，且丢包率可忽略不计；而与比例控制相比，卡尔曼超前控制器在目标进行不规则机动时，可将跟踪误差降低 44%，振荡降低 78%。

关键词：目标跟踪，游戏引擎仿真，通信协议，自适应控制，卡尔曼滤波，反无人机，Godot，Python。

Abstract. *Game engines offer compelling advantages for robotics simulation but typically lack the standardized communication infrastructure and control frameworks expected in dedicated robotics platforms. This gap presents challenges for applications requiring real-time, low-latency control, such as target acquisition and tracking (TAT) systems. This paper implements and evaluates communication protocols and control algorithms for pan-tilt-zoom camera control within a game engine simulation environment. We compare three communication approaches — UDP binary encoding, TCP binary encoding, and TCP with JSON serialization — alongside three control strategies: proportional (P) control, proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control, and adaptive control combining Kalman filtering with lead compensation. Experiments using a Godot-based simulator and Python control unit demonstrate that UDP binary achieves sub-2ms*

latency with negligible packet loss, while the Kalman-lead controller reduces tracking error by 44% and oscillation by 78% compared to proportional control during erratic target maneuvers.

Keywords: *target tracking, game engine simulation, communication protocols, adaptive control, Kalman filtering, counter-UAV, Godot, python.*

1 Introduction

The use of commercial game engines for robotics simulation has gained significant traction in recent years, offering advantages in visual fidelity, physics simulation, and development speed compared to traditional robotics simulators [1, 2]. Game engines like Unreal Engine, Unity, and Godot provide powerful rendering capabilities and accessible development environments that accelerate prototyping of vision-based robotic systems [3]. However, these platforms were designed primarily for entertainment applications and often lack the robust real-time communication infrastructure and standardized control protocols expected in dedicated robotics simulation frameworks such as Gazebo or Webots [4, 5].

Target Acquisition and Tracking (TAT) systems impose stringent requirements on control systems, such as low latency, high update rates, and predictable behavior under varying target dynamics [6, 7]. When implementing TAT systems in game engine environments, developers face fundamental architecture decisions regarding communication protocols and control algorithms. While robotics middleware frameworks like ROS provide well-established communication patterns and control libraries, integrating these frameworks with game engines introduces additional complexity, external dependencies, and often requires non-trivial bridging layers that can introduce latency and increase development time [8].

This paper addresses this gap by implementing and comparing communication protocols and control algorithms for real-time PTZ camera control within a game engine simulation environment. Specifically, we develop a Godot-based TAT system simulator and Python-based control unit, evaluating three communication architectures — timestamped UDP, TCP with JSON encoding, and TCP with custom packet structure — alongside three control strategies: proportional (P) control, proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control, and adaptive control with Kalman filtering and lead compensation.

2 Communication protocol design

2.1 Task requirements and architectural considerations

The communication architecture for a target tracking system must address two distinct data flows: telemetry transmission from the simulation environment to control unit, and command transmission from control unit to the simulated

platform. Each flow has different characteristics and requirements that influence protocol selection.

Telemetry transmission consists of high-frequency state updates including current platform orientation, target orientation values, timestamps and other relevant data. This data stream operates at simulation's physics update rate of 60 Hz, generating a continuous flow of state information. The primary requirements for telemetry are low latency and temporal consistency — the control algorithm needs fresh data to compute accurate commands, and outdated telemetry packets provide little value. In contrast, the loss of individual telemetry packets is generally acceptable, as the next update arriving 16.7 ms later (at 60 Hz) will overwrite any missing information. This characteristic makes telemetry well-suited for a fire-and-forget continuous stream approach, where the receiver always processes the most recent packet and discards stale data.

Command transmission presents different considerations depending on the nature of the commands being sent. Control commands can be broadly categorized into two types: continuous control signals and discrete action triggers. Continuous control signals, such as target pan and tilt angles for camera gimbals or velocity setpoints for drone control, are typically transmitted at regular intervals regardless of whether the commanded values have changed. This approach, represented by handling of RC inputs by MAVLink protocol [9], serves multiple purposes: provides an implicit heartbeat mechanism for fallback mode activation and simplifies the control loop implementation by eliminating the need to track state changes and decide when transmission is necessary.

2.2 Protocol implementations

In this work we employ a simplified structure of telemetry with only the relevant information present. Specifically, one telemetry entry includes: timestamp, ground truth bounding box dimensions in YOLO format, current pan and tilt angles, internal target angles and current operating mode.

JSON over TCP approach prioritizes human readability and ease of debugging during development. Messages are serialized as JSON objects with named fields and transmitted over a reliable TCP connection. TCP's built-in acknowledgment mechanism ensures reliable, in-order delivery. This reliability comes at a cost: TCP's congestion control can introduce variable latency, and its stream-oriented nature requires application-layer message framing.

Binary encoding reduces overhead while maintaining TCP's reliability guarantees. The telemetry packet structure (Figure 1) consists of tightly-packed fields totaling 41 bytes. This encoding reduces packet size by approximately 78% compared to JSON, significantly decreasing serialization time and bandwidth consumption. Binary packets inherit TCP ACK mechanism and retransmission guarantees but sacrifice human readability.

8 bytes timestamp	4 bytes bbox_x	4 bytes bbox_y	4 bytes bbox_w	4 bytes bbox_h	4 bytes cur_pan	4 bytes cur_tilt	4 bytes tgt_pan	4 bytes tgt_tilt	1 byte mode
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Figure 1. Data layout in a custom packet

UDP eliminates TCP’s reliability mechanisms in favor of minimal latency. Packets may be lost, duplicated, or arrive out of order, however, for continuous 60 Hz streams, UDP’s lack of guarantees is not critical. A new telemetry packet arrives every 16.7 ms, so if one is lost, the next packet arrives shortly with updated information that supersedes the missing data.

2.3 Control algorithm design

The control objective is to compute target pan and tilt angles that drive the camera to center the tracked object in the field of view. Given normalized bounding box, the control algorithm must translate the pixel-space error into angular commands that minimize the offset between the target and the image center.

Normalized error between bounding box center and image center is computed as:

$$e_x(t) = bbox_x(t) - 0.5$$

$$e_y(t) = bbox_y(t) - 0.5$$

where e_x and e_y represent horizontal and vertical displacement in normalized image coordinates. To convert normalized errors into angular errors, we apply field-of-view scaling:

$$e_{pan}(t) = e_x(t) \cdot FOV_h$$

$$e_{tilt}(t) = -e_y(t) \cdot FOV_v$$

where FOV_h and FOV_v are horizontal and vertical field of view respectively. The negative sign for tilt accounts for the image coordinate convention (positive y-axis points downward in images, while positive tilt angles point upward).

To prevent oscillations around the target when it is already well-centered, we implement a deadzone:

$$r_{deadzone} = 0.25 \cdot bbox_w$$

$$if \sqrt{e_x^2 + e_y^2} < r_{deadzone}, then e_x = e_y = 0$$

Deadzone radius scales with the target’s bounding box width, ensuring that small targets require tighter centering while large, close targets have more tolerance. A scaling factor of 0.25 means the deadzone radius is a quarter of the target’s width, providing a reasonable balance between precision and stability.

2.4 Proportional (P) controller

Proportional controller represents the simplest feedback control strategy, computing the control output as a direct linear function of the error:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{pan}(t) &= K_p \cdot e_{pan}(t) \\ \Delta_{tilt}(t) &= K_p \cdot e_{tilt}(t)\end{aligned}$$

where K_p is proportional gain, a tuning parameter that determines the aggressiveness of the controller's response. The target angles are then computed by adding these corrections to the current platform angles:

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{targetpan}(t) &= \theta_{currentpan}(t) + \Delta_{pan}(t) \\ \theta_{targettilt}(t) &= \theta_{currenttilt}(t) + \Delta_{tilt}(t)\end{aligned}$$

Larger errors produce larger corrections, driving the system toward the desired state. However, pure proportional controller suffers from several limitations: it can't eliminate steady-state error in presence of disturbances or system biases and high gain K_p yields fast response but cause overshoot and cause oscillation, while low gains produce sluggish response. Moreover, the controller is purely reactive, responding only to current error without considering error history or rate of change.

2.5 Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) Controller

PID controller extends proportional control by incorporating two additional terms: an integral term that accumulates past error to eliminate steady-state offsets, and a derivative term that anticipates future error based on the current rate of change. The control law is:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{pan}(t) &= K_p \cdot e_{pan}(t) + K_i \int_0^t e_{pan}(t)dt + K_d \frac{de_{pan}(t)}{dt} \\ \Delta_{tilt}(t) &= K_p \cdot e_{tilt}(t) + K_i \int_0^t e_{tilt}(t)dt + K_d \frac{de_{tilt}(t)}{dt}\end{aligned}$$

where K_p , K_i and K_d are proportional, integral, and derivative gains, respectively.

Proportional term provides the primary corrective action proportional to the current error. Integral term accumulates error over time, increasing the control output as long as error persists. This term drives steady-state error to zero. However, the integral term can cause «integral windup» when large errors persist, leading to overshoot. We implement anti-windup by clamping the integrated error:

$$I_{pan}(t) = clamp\left(\int_0^t e_{pan}(t)dt, -I_{max}, I_{max}\right)$$

where I_{max} limits the maximum contribution of the integral term, preventing excessive accumulation during transients.

Derivative term responds to the rate of change of error, providing damping that reduces overshoot and oscillation. When error is decreasing rapidly (target approaching center), the derivative term produces a corrective action opposing the proportional term, slowing the approach and preventing overshoot. Mathematically, the derivative anticipates where the error will be in the near future based on its current trajectory.

The complete discrete PID control law becomes:

$$\Delta(t_k) = K_p \cdot e(t_k) + K_i \cdot I(t_k) + K_d \cdot D(t_k)$$

2.6 Adaptive Control with Kalman Filtering and Lead Compensation

While PID controllers provide robust performance for many tracking applications, counter-UAS scenarios present unique challenges that motivate more sophisticated control strategies. UAV targets exhibit erratic, unpredictable maneuvers — sudden direction changes, acceleration bursts, and spiral evasive patterns, which can cause traditional feedback controllers to lag behind the target's actual position. Additionally, computer vision-based detection introduces measurement noise: bounding box coordinates jitter due to pixel-level quantization, detector confidence fluctuations cause box dimensions to vary frame-to-frame, and tracker handoff events can produce sudden discontinuous jumps in reported position.

To address these challenges, we implement an adaptive control strategy combining Kalman filtering for state estimation and lead compensation for predictive control. The Kalman filter provides optimal state estimation in the presence of noisy measurements, smoothing bbox jitter while estimating target velocity. The discrete-time state transition with timestep Δt is:

$$x_k = Fx_{k-1} + w_k, F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $w_k \sim N(0, Q)$ represents process noise. The measurement model observes bbox center position:

$$z_k = Hx_{k-1} + v_k, H = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

with measurement noise $v_k \sim N(0, R)$. The filter recursively estimates state through standard predict-update equations, yielding smoothed position (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) and velocity $(\hat{\dot{x}}, \hat{\dot{y}})$ estimates. To compensate for control loop delays and platform dynamics, we predict the target's future position using estimated velocity:

$$x_{pred} = \hat{x} + \hat{\dot{x}} \cdot T_{lead}; y_{pred} = \hat{y} + \hat{\dot{y}} \cdot T_{lead}$$

where T_{lead} matches the expected camera settling time. The control law applies proportional control to the predicted error:

$$e_{pan}^{pred} = x_{pred} \cdot FOV_h; e_{tilt}^{pred} = -y_{pred} \cdot FOV_v$$

$$\Delta(t) = K_p^{adaptive} \cdot e_{pred}$$

This strategy provides key benefits for UAV tracking, such as noise rejection, reduced oscillation and maneuver handling.

3 Experimental Setup

The experimental platform consists of a Godot Engine 4.5 simulation environment modeling a stationary pan-tilt camera platform and a Python-based control unit. The control loop operates at 60 Hz, matching the simulation's physics update rate. The target follows a predefined trajectory designed to evaluate controller performance across varied motion profiles — the first half features smooth, gradual turns with constant velocity, simulating cooperative or non-evasive target behavior, the second half introduces erratic maneuvers including sharp directional changes, rapid altitude variations, and velocity changes, representative of evasive UAV flight patterns.

To ensure experimental repeatability across tests, we use ground-truth bounding boxes from the simulation with artificially introduced jitter to simulate realistic detector noise. Gaussian noise with standard deviation $\sigma = 0,01$ (1% of image width) is added to bounding box center coordinates at each frame, and uniform noise with range $\pm 0,1$ to bounding box dimensions. This jitter magnitude reflects typical variance observed in state-of-the-art object detectors operating on high-quality video streams.

4 Results

Figure 2 presents the performance comparison of the three communication protocols across latency and bandwidth utilization metrics. UDP binary encoding achieved the lowest average latency at 1.2 ms, followed by TCP binary at 2.8 ms and TCP JSON at 4.6 ms. The latency differences reflect protocol overhead: UDP connectionless nature eliminates ACK wait times and connection management, while TCP reliability mechanisms introduce round-trip delays. The TCP JSON implementation exhibits additional latency due to serialization/deserialization overhead.

Figure 2. Communication protocol comparison

Bandwidth utilization follows a similar pattern. UDP consumed approximately 71.8 KB/s, TCP binary used 84.2 KB/s, and TCP JSON consumed 322.4 KB/s. The factor-of-4 bandwidth difference between binary and JSON encodings demonstrates the cost of human-readable serialization. TCP’s additional overhead compared to UDP (81 vs 69 bytes per packet) stems from larger TCP headers (minimum 20 bytes vs UDP’s 8 bytes) and protocol control segments.

Figure 3 (left) shows that all three control algorithms achieved similar time-to-lock performance: P controller at 621 ms, PID at 582 ms, and Kalman-lead at 577 ms. The minimal differences indicate that initial target acquisition is primarily limited by the platform’s maximum angular velocity ($75^\circ/s$) rather than controller sophistication. Figure 3 (right) reveals significant differences in control stability, measured as the frequency of sign changes in commanded corrections (oscillation index). The P controller exhibited the highest oscillation index at 0.212, indicating that the commanded pan/tilt deltas reversed direction in 21% of control iterations — symptomatic of overshoot and hunting behavior around the target. The PID controller reduced oscillation to 0.11 through derivative damping, while the Kalman-lead controller achieved the lowest value at 0.043, representing a 78% reduction compared to P control.

Figure 3. Time-to-lock and oscillation comparison across control algorithms

Figure 4 presents average tracking error magnitude over the experimental trajectory. During the stable flight segment (iterations 0-300), all three controllers maintained low error with Kalman performing marginally better (mean error 0.012 vs 0.015 for PID and 0.019 for P). The critical performance divergence occurs during the erratic maneuver segment (iterations 300-400), where the target executes sharp turns and rapid altitude changes. In this region, the P controller’s error spikes to 0.045-0.050, representing visible lag as the camera struggles to track aggressive maneuvers. The PID controller’s integral action reduces peak

error to 0.035-0.040, but the Kalman-lead controller maintains errors below 0.025 throughout.

Figure 4. Tracking error comparison across control algorithms

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a systematic comparison of communication protocols and control algorithms for real-time camera control in game engine-based target tracking simulations. We implemented a Godot simulation environment coupled with a Python control unit, evaluating three communication approaches and three control strategies under counter-UAS tracking scenarios. The experimental results demonstrate that UDP binary encoding achieves the lowest latency and minimal bandwidth overhead, making it the recommended choice for high-frequency telemetry and command streams. For control algorithms, the Kalman filter with lead compensation outperformed both P and PID controllers in tracking stability and error reduction during erratic target maneuvers, achieving 78% lower oscillation and 44% reduced tracking error compared to proportional control.

Several extensions could further improve system performance. First, implementing more sophisticated adaptive control strategies — such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) with explicit platform dynamics constraints or reinforcement learning-based policies trained on diverse UAV flight patterns — may yield additional tracking improvements. Second, creating a unified software library that encapsulates the communication protocol stack and control algorithms would facilitate technology transfer from simulation to physical hardware prototypes. Finally, hardware-in-the-loop testing with actual pan-tilt platforms would validate whether simulation-derived control parameters transfer effectively to real systems with physical nonlinearities such as backlash, friction, and servo deadbands.

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数字化转型背景下知识经济的管理机制
**MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS OF THE INTELLECTUAL
ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了知识经济时代现代管理机制的本质和结构组成，并识别了数字化背景下管理机制转型的关键特征和方向。

关键词：知识经济，管理机制，数字化转型，知识管理，层级结构，灵活性。

Abstract. *The article examines the essence and structural components of modern management mechanisms in the intellectual economy. The key features and directions of transformation of management mechanisms in the context of digitalization are identified.*

Keywords: *intellectual economy, management mechanisms, digital transformation, knowledge management, hierarchy, flexibility.*

In the current conditions of development of socio-economic systems, digital transformation is becoming the basis of the intellectual economy, as it contributes not only to economic evolution, but also to a qualitative reevaluation of classical factors of production. This is a shift in the economic paradigm, where knowledge, information, and technology are no longer auxiliary elements, but rather system-forming factors and the primary environment for creating value and adding value. In this context, the creation of a new management architecture that enables the transition from tangible to intangible factors, and from the industrial to the intellectual era, becomes increasingly important.

The intellectual economy as an external environment for modern organizations integrates all previous stages of economic evolution, elevating the role of intangible assets. The intellectual economy as a scientific definition is a systemic concept that combines three stages of economic development (knowledge economy,

digital economy, and data economy) to describe a qualitatively new state of the economic system. Here, the main production resource is intellectual capital in its complex form, and the key process is nonlinear innovation based on a combination of human creativity, digital tools, and data analysis. For management mechanisms, this means that they need to work not just with people's knowledge, but with the entire digital intellectual system, where people, data, and algorithms form a new hybrid entity of economic activity [4]. In classical management, the management mechanism is a set of formalized tools that ensure order, predictability, and efficiency in production under conditions of certainty. The focus is on processes and structures through universal functions and principles of management, as well as the main elements (planning, control, motivation, decision-making, and coordination). Humanistic, systemic, and situational approaches, as a continuation of classical management, change the perception of management mechanisms by denying the universality of management in organizations. Now, it is not just about formal rules in management, but also about social interactions and flexibility. The focus is shifting towards the need for adaptation and the importance of the human factor in professional management.

In today's context of the smart economy, environmental turbulence, and digitalization, the management approach must undergo a radical transformation. The management mechanism of the 21st century is viewed as a dynamic, adaptive, networked, and technologically advanced ecosystem. This is due to the challenges posed by Industry 4.0 for the smart economy and new management. According to Klaus Schwab, the Fourth Industrial Revolution is characterized by the convergence of digital, biological, and physical technologies, accelerating the development of the smart economy and creating qualitatively new systemic challenges. [5]. It is they who challenge traditional economic and management paradigms, requiring a rethinking of the foundations of organization, competition, and value creation. In this regard, scholars identify different types of mismatch between traditional hierarchical management mechanisms and the requirements of the new economy:

- cognitive mismatch (today, the key competitive factor is the speed of decision-making and implementation; it is necessary to respond instantly to market changes, customer data, and competitor actions; the existing multi-level approval process becomes an obstacle to the management process);

- information mismatch (decisions should be made at the point of maximum concentration of relevant information and competencies; the existing centralization of decision-making rights at the upper levels often disconnects decisions from reality and demotivates knowledge holders);

- structural inconsistency (the modern requirement for flexibility is related to the need to use cross-functional collaboration within the organization; hierarchical

mechanisms with rigid functional divisions of labour and vertical subordination create interfunctional barriers and competition for resources within the organization);

— motivational mismatch (creating value through non-standard solutions and initiatives requires internal motivation, creativity, and an entrepreneurial spirit; in a system of motivation based on following rules, avoiding mistakes, and meeting KPIs, an innovative “block” occurs);

— strategic mismatch (in order to develop an organization, it is necessary to constantly adapt business models, products, and processes to changing external conditions; hierarchical mechanisms are focused on eliminating deviations from the plan rather than finding new paths, which leads to strategic blindness);

— communicative mismatch (the modern requirement of the economy is transparent, fast, and horizontal exchange of information and knowledge; it is supported by the capabilities provided by open data, internal social networks, and shared digital platforms; traditional mechanisms suffer from the “broken telephone” effect, where information flows are filtered and distorted at each level of the hierarchy, and the information itself becomes a source of power, which is unacceptable for creating a unified contextual communication field).

Thus, the intellectual economy is based on knowledge, information, and digital technologies, which means that it requires the transformation of classical management mechanisms to meet the new conditions of the external environment [2]. Based on numerous studies by domestic and foreign scientists, as well as business practice cases, the management mechanism of the intellectual economy can be defined as a digital platform that combines four key blocks that meet the requirements of the modern world:

— information and analytical unit (turns data into knowledge and informed decisions through data collection and aggregation, analytical processing, visualization, and decision support, as well as the use of digital twins; this is where a special data-driven culture is formed, where decisions are based on objective data rather than intuition);

— the organizational and coordination unit (provides flexibility, speed, and effective interaction through network and platform structures, flexible methodologies, virtual and cross-functional teams, holacracy, and sociocracy; the result of the unit’s work is a self-organizing and quickly responding internal organizational environment);

— the motivational and innovative block (stimulates the generation of knowledge, creativity, and entrepreneurial initiative within the organization through relevant goal-setting models, crowdsourcing platforms, and internal startup studios, gamification, recognition, and development systems; it creates a constant flow of innovation and increases the level of engagement of key specialists, providing opportunities for talent development within the organization);

— the knowledge and talent management unit (this is the core of intellectual capital that can systematically accumulate, disseminate, and protect key assets

such as employee knowledge and competencies through a knowledge base and expert systems, social networks and corporate collaborative platforms, mentoring and community systems, and talent management systems; the result of this unit's work is the creation of a sustainable "organizational memory," the development of "collective wisdom," and the prevention of "brain drain").

In our opinion, the structure of management mechanisms in the intellectual economy should be an integrated, digital, and human-centric system. Its key features should be as follows:

- focus on creating value through knowledge (management mechanisms are aimed at constantly generating new knowledge and transforming it into market innovations and solutions instead of traditional optimization of existing processes; there is a shift from strict control of performance indicators to managing knowledge flows and innovation cycles with the development of an innovative culture);

- flexibility and adaptability as a basic norm (management mechanisms are designed to be quickly transformed to meet new challenges and environmental changes, replacing rigid regulations with principles and new value frameworks that define ranges of autonomous actions; there is a gradual shift from stable and unchanging regulations and structures to flexible architectural solutions that use the principles of holacracy and spiral dynamics);

- the network and ecosystem nature of interaction (management goes beyond the boundaries of a single legal entity through mechanisms for coordinating the activities of distributed ecosystem participants based on platform rules and digital interfaces; there is a paradigm shift from managing a hierarchy of subordinates to coordinating a network of equal agents);

- decision-making based on a data-driven approach (strategic and operational decisions are made based on the analysis of big data, algorithms, and models, rather than just on the personal experience and intuition of managers; there is a shift from an intuitive and experiential management style to a scientifically evidence-based one, which improves the quality and speed of decision-making);

- intellectualization of management processes through automation (the possibility of delegating routine management functions to artificial intelligence and algorithms is used to focus managers on creative tasks, motivation, and strategy; this allows managers to be freed from the functions of a controller-administrator and strengthen their role as a strategist, leader, and interpreter);

- a culture of openness and collaboration (management mechanisms intensively develop horizontal connections, maintain an open exchange of information and allow mistakes as a source of learning; at the same time, cross-functional barriers are destroyed, internal structural closeness is overcome, competition between organizational units is reduced, fear of failure is eliminated and the "resistance to change" syndrome is taken into account).

Such management mechanisms of the new organizational architecture are capable of not only maintaining the current order, but also creating objective conditions for continuous updating, learning, and anticipatory response to global challenges in the external environment [3]. Research on the trends and development of the economy and management in the 21st century allows us to identify five groups of such challenges. The first group is defined by technological aspects that reflect the inevitability of the transition from digitalization to cyber-physical integration, with a gradual shift in the role of humans in decision-making. The second group is responsible for the economic state of the socio-economic system, where hyper-competition, platform business models, and network effects lead to market concentration, and technology erases the boundaries between traditional industries. Organizational challenges are related to the crisis of traditional structures that are unable to respond to the speed and complexity of change. Modern organizations must not only adapt, but also benefit from the challenges and uncertainties of the world, which means they must be antifragile. The fourth socio-humanitarian group explains how scientific and technological progress outpaces social adaptation, leading to deep systemic imbalances. The strategic challenges group describes the opportunities and complexities of managing in a radically uncertain world through the mental models of VUCA and BANI. All of this highlights the importance of creating an adaptive management ecosystem that is fit for the challenges of Industry 4.0 in the smart economy.

In his works, I. Adizes systemically and reasonably formulated priority positions that characterize key processes that change the existing management paradigm, thereby emphasizing the importance of changes in management mechanisms. These can be considered factors that modify management methods: the decline of authoritarian management styles, the end of hierarchies, the power of team spirit, the emphasis on organizational architecture, the focus on millennials, data transparency, stress management, the need for consultants, the health of the organization as a new corporate goal, and value-based management [1]. In this regard, it is necessary to determine the directions of transformation of management mechanisms in response to the challenges of the intellectual economy. It is important to emphasize that such transformation is not a matter of spot modernization. Instead, it is a matter of systemic restructuring in various and interconnected areas, leading to a change in the very paradigm of management. In our opinion, the following priority areas for change (key vectors of management transformation) can be identified:

— transition from a hierarchical organizational pyramid to an ecosystem platform (shifting the role of the management mechanism from administrative control of internal processes to coordination and value creation in an open network; this requires restructuring the organization to create a digital infrastructure, changing the role of the manager to that of a curator, architect of interaction rules, and creator of a trusting environment to ensure network effects and synergies among

participants, as well as new coordination mechanisms through clear technical and business interaction protocols);

— creation of an “intelligent control loop” (forming a closed control loop with reinforcement of each stage (planning, organization, motivation, and control) with the necessary data and algorithms to reduce the time lag and eliminate cognitive distortions; such a loop requires the use of predictive planning tools, automated process organization, dynamic control, and adaptation, which allow for the correction of actions and automatic reconfiguration of processes);

— humanization and personalization of motivation mechanisms (the use of comprehensive, individually-oriented systems aimed at revealing creative and intellectual potential through the transition to flexible goal-setting systems with a focus on ambitious results, the creation of internal platforms with expert rating systems, badges for competencies, public project portfolios, and personalization of career trajectories);

— institutionalization of continuous innovation and strategic flexibility (transforming innovation activities from a periodic, R&D-centric function into a continuous, organizational mechanism embedded in all processes; this requires the creation of a management model that combines operational and innovation loops, the use of internal crowdsourcing platforms for collecting ideas, and the management of a portfolio of strategic projects to maintain strategic flexibility);

— development of the concept of “cybernetic management” and the ethics of interaction with artificial intelligence (formation of new competencies and principles for effective and responsible management of hybrid human-machine systems based on the development of the principles of “algorithm management”, the formation of digital ethics and a culture of data trust, as well as the development of soft skills in managers with a focus on emotional intelligence, empathy, critical thinking, and creativity).

Thus, in the context of digital transformation, knowledge sets the direction of change, information serves as an important resource, and technology acts as a transformative force. The primary objective of modern management mechanisms that support digital transformation is to create an environment that enables the continuous generation and capitalization of intellectual capital. To ensure successful transformation, it is crucial to synchronize and interconnect the technological and human aspects of the management process, while simultaneously fostering a new organizational data-driven culture.

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当前阶段企业竞争力管理的系统性变革
**SYSTEMIC TRANSFORMATION OF ENTERPRISE
COMPETITIVENESS MANAGEMENT AT THE PRESENT STAGE**

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摘要：本文探讨了在现代发展条件下企业竞争力管理转型升级的必要性，并分析了企业竞争力水平。文章阐述了影响企业竞争力的各子系统之间的相互关系，强调了运用综合方法进行竞争力管理的重要性，并提出了一种企业竞争力预测算法。

关键词：竞争力，企业，战略，管理，经济，发展，效率。

Abstract. *The article examines the necessity of transforming enterprise competitiveness management, considering modern development conditions, and analyzes the levels of enterprise competitiveness. The interrelationships of subsystems affecting enterprise competitiveness are presented. Emphasis is placed on applying a comprehensive approach to competitiveness management. An algorithm for forecasting enterprise competitiveness is presented.*

Keywords: *competitiveness, enterprise, strategy, management, economy, development, efficiency.*

In a market economy, competition plays a fundamental role. It stimulates enterprises to continuous improvement and the pursuit of unique advantages that enable them to stand out among competitors. Each company is focused on maximizing profit, gaining consumer loyalty, and strengthening its position in the market. Achieving these goals requires the development of a systemic approach to managing competitiveness.

The levels of an organization's competitiveness can be presented as follows:

Production-oriented level: management is focused on product output, ignoring market realities — consumer demands and competitor activity.

Market adaptation level: management strives to ensure the product meets existing market standards and characteristics established by competitors.

Level of innovative leadership: the organization aims to become a trendsetter in its industry, setting trends that competitors will follow [1, p. 113].

Strategic level of management: the key factor for success is not so much the production itself, but competent management and organization of all processes, which enables the company to secure a leading position in the market across all aspects.

An enterprise is considered highly competitive if it effectively utilizes its resources to achieve profits exceeding those of its competitors. This indicates the company's strong position in the market and high demand for its products. To maintain such an advantage, management must actively adapt to changes, for instance, by improving the product range, implementing innovations, expanding production, optimizing sales channels, and entering new markets [2, p. 56].

Effective management of competitiveness aims to establish such a level of superiority that ensures the enterprise achieves its intended objectives and meets planned performance indicators. The enterprise competitiveness management system is designed to harmonize the work of all enterprise departments to achieve the necessary competitiveness and obtain a synergistic effect, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 — Interconnection of subsystems influencing the competitiveness of the organization

Integration of the competitiveness management system with each of the enterprise's internal subsystems is a key factor in achieving a high level of

competitiveness. This approach ensures the improvement of product and service quality, stimulates organizational transformations, and facilitates more effective cross-functional interaction [3, p. 236].

An organization is a complex structure in which all its components are closely interdependent. Therefore, to enhance an enterprise's competitiveness, it is necessary to apply a systemic management approach that encompasses all internal connections and considers the company as a unified whole [4, p. 115].

For any organization, achieving an optimal level of management and strengthening its market position is essential. The task of the enterprise goes beyond mere survival in a competitive environment; it consists in maximizing financial returns.

It is vital for enterprises to be competitive, and business management essentially boils down to managing this competitiveness. Sustainable development and competitiveness are two sides of the same coin: they proceed in tandem, reinforcing each other and leading to increased productivity and improved financial performance of companies [5, p. 803].

Figure 2 – Algorithm for forecasting enterprise competitiveness

To achieve a competitive advantage, it is critically important to analyze the specifics of the market environment, strategic objectives, and the product life

cycle stage. Such analysis enables the identification of the most promising product attributes and the formulation of a unique value proposition for the target audience.

A comprehensive approach to competitiveness management implies a strategic perspective that considers not only the company's current position but also its future opportunities. Determining potential competitiveness becomes a central element of this strategy. To successfully achieve the set goals, the enterprise must forecast consumer expectations as accurately as possible, identify the most demanded products, and consistently improve the quality of its competitive offerings, thereby ensuring a stable financial position [6, p. 67].

The forecasting algorithm for enterprise competitiveness is presented in Figure 2.

Effective management of a company's competitiveness requires the following:

Developing a methodology for assessing its market positions.

Identifying optimal tools for analyzing competitive advantages.

Optimizing investment decisions to maximize the strengthening of competitive positions.

Formulating a long-term strategy that ensures market leadership.

Within the framework of the proposed systemic approach to enterprise competitiveness management, it is envisaged to conduct a comprehensive diagnosis of the current level of competitive positions, form a portfolio of effective investment projects, and develop forecasting models for the development of the organization's competitiveness under conditions of external environment variability.

Successful adaptation of a company is demonstrated by its ability not only to accommodate new competitive realities but also to actively leverage them for its own development, ultimately elevating it to a new level of competitiveness.

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俄罗斯云计算技术：制裁与进口替代下的持续增长
**CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN RUSSIA: GROWTH AMID
SANCTIONS AND IMPORT SUBSTITUTION**

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摘要：本文探讨了在地缘政治不稳定、外国IT供应商撤离以及设备老化等背景下，俄罗斯云计算技术市场的转型过程。文章分析了导致IT资源消费模式转变的关键因素：从成本优化转向确保技术自主性和业务可持续性。作者考察了IaaS、PaaS和SaaS领域的现状，重点关注硬件短缺和合格人才匮乏等进口替代挑战。文章提出了一种基于混合环境、微服务架构和国产虚拟化工具的自主云模型。文章估算了转向俄罗斯云解决方案的经济效益，并确定了关键信息基础设施全面迁移的时间表。

关键词：云计算技术、进口替代、IT基础设施、技术自主性、IaaS-、PaaS、SaaS、数字化转型、信息安全。

Annotation. *The article examines the process of transformation of the Russian cloud technology market in the context of geopolitical instability, the departure of foreign IT providers and obsolescence of equipment. The analysis of the key factors that led to a paradigm shift in the consumption of IT resources: from cost optimization to ensuring technological sovereignty and business sustainability. The author examines the current state of the IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS segments, focusing on import substitution challenges such as hardware shortages and lack of qualified personnel. The concept of a sovereign cloud model based on hybrid environments, microservice architecture, and domestic virtualization tools is proposed. The paper presents estimates of the economic efficiency of switching to Russian cloud solutions and defines the time frame for implementing a full-scale migration of critical information infrastructure.*

Keywords: *cloud technologies, import substitution, IT infrastructure, technological sovereignty, IaaS, PaaS, SaaS, digital transformation, information security.*

1. Problem statement.

A large-scale reconfiguration of the Russian IT sector under the influence of geopolitical factors has predetermined a change in the role of cloud technologies: from an auxiliary optimization tool to a critical foundation for business sustainability. The urgency of this situation is caused by the imperative of accelerated import-substituting migration from foreign PaaS / IaaS solutions (such as AWS, Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud) to domestic developments that meet strict performance and cybersecurity requirements.

The risks associated with integrating clouds into critical information infrastructure objects (CII) make maintaining operational integrity and implementing national digitalization programs a priority for government customers and the corporate sector. Cooperation between regulators (the Ministry of Digital Development, FSTEC) and private businesses is aimed at overcoming the shortage of cloud capacity that has arisen due to restrictions in the supply of high-tech equipment and semiconductors. According to statistical indicators [8-10], the growth of budgets for IT infrastructure is accompanied by a structural shift: companies abandon capital expenditures (CAPEX) for building their own server ones in favor of operating expenses (OPEX) based on the service model of resource consumption.

2. Cause analysis

The root cause of the current market transformation is the geopolitical factor that provoked the mass exodus of foreign IT giants from Russia. This led to the disruption of established supply chains and the termination of technical support for already implemented solutions. The system analysis shows [1] that the sanctions pressure was a catalyst that exposed the risks of excessive dependence on proprietary foreign software and cloud services operating on a subscription model, access to which can be restricted unilaterally. In addition, studies [4] note that a qualitative restructuring of the national economy should be implemented on the basis of domestic demand.

Causal relationships in this context are as follows:

1. Crisis of trust: License revocation and account blocking by global providers caused a lack of trust in cross-border cloud solutions. This made businesses realize that data stored outside the jurisdiction of the Russian Federation is in a high-risk area.

2. High demand: As a result, there was a sharp influx of customers to Russian data centers. Local sites are faced with the need to scale their capacities as soon as possible.

3. Resource hunger: The rapid growth in demand has revealed system difficulties associated with the lack of qualified DevOps engineers and architects capable of designing fault-tolerant cloud systems based on Open Source (OpenStack, Kubernetes) and domestic operating systems.

4. Hardware restrictions: Sanctions on the supply of server processors (Intel, AMD) and data storage systems (DWH) created barriers to the physical expansion

of cloud platforms, which prompted the development of parallel import and development of servers based on Elbrus and Baikal processors.

3. Review of existing solutions

Russian experience in the field of cloud technologies in recent years has gone from providing simple virtual servers (VPS) to creating complex ecosystem solutions at the Hyperscaler level. Leading Russian providers (Yandex Cloud, Cloud.ru, VK Cloud, Rostelecom-DPC) are actively developing platform services (PaaS), which include managed Databases, tools for Big Data analysis and machine learning (ML).

A comparative analysis shows [5] that Russian platforms today compete in the following parameters:

- **Safety:** Compliance with the requirements of 152-FZ and availability of certified polygons for working with GIS.
- **Technology stack:** Transition from VMware and Hyper-V to domestic virtualization systems (for example, P-Platform, Basis, zVirt) based on KVM.
- **Integration:** The ability to seamlessly interface cloud resources with on-premise systems of the customer through dedicated communication channels (Direct Connect).

Assessment of the applicability of solutions indicates the demand for “boxed” cloud products for typical business tasks. Particular attention is paid to migration of BPM systems (Business Process Management) and ERP solutions to the cloud [3]. This allows enterprises to automate marketing, sales, and internal document management without capital investment in hardware, taking advantage of the SaaS (Software as a Service) model.

Table 1. State of the cloud market segments in Russia.

Service type	Main features in the Russian Federation (2024-2025)	Import substitution level
IaaS	Lease of computing power and object storage (S3), SDN	High (transition to domestic hypervisors and OpenStack)
PaaS	Managed Kubernetes, DBMS (PostgreSQL), AI and analytics tools	Medium (active development of containerization and proprietary APIs)
SaaS	Cloud software (office suites, CRM (Bitrix24), ERP, video communication systems)	High (dominance of Russian vendors)

Source: compiled by the author based on the results of the analysis [6-10]

4. Proposed solution: Sovereign Cloud Model

The proposed concept considers the transition to a sovereign cloud model that combines infrastructure independence and flexibility of modern IT architectures.

Key components of the solution:

1. **Microservice transformation:** Instead of simply moving old systems to the cloud (Lift-and-Shift), it is proposed to recycle applications for a cloud-oriented (Cloud Native) architecture. This ensures high availability and makes it easier to update components.

2. **Hybrid infrastructure:** Applying a model where sensitive data (state secrets, first-level personal data) is stored in a private cloud, and less critical computing and frontend services are scaled in the public Cloud of a trusted provider.

3. **Unified management stack:** Use of Russian orchestrators and monitoring systems that are independent of foreign updates.

Required resources for implementation:

- **Personnel resources:** Large-scale retraining of specialists in working with the Russian technology stack (Astra Linux, P-Platform, platforms Cloud.ru and Yandex).

- **Technological solutions:** Formation of a strategic reserve of server equipment included in the register of the Ministry of Industry and Trade, and development of domestic microelectronics.

- **Financial services:** Use of public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms, subsidizing interest rates on loans for the purchase of domestic software and cloud services.

The time frame for implementing a full-scale transition to a sovereign model on a national scale is estimated at 3-5 years.

5. Performance assessment and risks

To assess the effectiveness of implementation, it is proposed to use business continuity metrics (SLA of at least 99.95%), the import substitution index in the IT architecture, and indicators for reducing the total cost of ownership (TCO).

Possible expected effects:

- **Economic:** Optimization of TCO by 20-30% by eliminating license payments to foreign vendors and switching to Pay-as-you-go.

- **Operational:** Reducing the time-to-Market cycle of products by using ready-made PaaS tools.

- **Strategic:** Full technological independence of critical business processes from external sanctions factors.

Critical analysis of constraints:

- **Hardware shortage:** The risk of a shortage of high-performance processors and GPUs for training neural networks in the cloud.

- **Cyberthreats:** The growing complexity of the attack landscape requires the introduction of the Zero Trust concept and enhanced protection at the application software level (WAF, anti-DDoS).

• Legacy systems: The difficulty of adapting old proprietary software written under Windows / Oracle to work in a Linux cloud environment.

Despite the challenges, a systematic approach to the development of cloud technologies is the only alternative way to ensure Russia's digital sovereignty and maintain economic growth in the face of global instability.

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数字平台是上海合作组织产业生态系统的核心
**DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS THE CORE OF INDUSTRIAL
ECOSYSTEMS IN THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION
ORGANIZATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了数字技术对上海合作组织（上合组织）产业合作模式的影响。通过分析上合组织2019年至2025年的文件和举措，作者指出，上合组织内部开发的专业数字平台（涵盖能源、技术转让和数字经济领域）正从沟通工具演变为新兴跨国产业生态系统的 key 组成部分。这些平台如同“数字轮廓”，连接着合作伙伴搜索、技术交流、联合开发和生产本地化等各个阶段。本文评估了这种模式在增强成员国经济韧性和技术自主性方面的潜力。

关键词：上合组织，产业合作，数字化转型，数字平台，产业生态系统，技术自主性，可持续发展。

Abstract. *The article examines the transformation of industrial cooperation models within the SCO under the influence of digital technologies. Based on an analysis of the organization's documents and initiatives (2019-2025), the author demonstrates that the specialized digital platforms developed within the SCO (in the fields of energy, technology transfer, and the digital economy) are evolving from communication tools into a key component of the emerging transnational industrial ecosystems. These platforms serve as a “digital contour,” connecting the phases of partner search, technology exchange, joint development, and production localization. The article evaluates the potential of this approach to strengthen the resilience and technological sovereignty of the economies of member countries.*

Keywords: *SCO, industrial cooperation, digital transformation, digital platforms, industrial ecosystems, technological sovereignty, sustainable development.*

The global economy has faced a series of crises. The COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical tensions have revealed the fragility of traditional value chains. In response to these challenges, the countries of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) have intensified efforts to identify sustainable regional development models. A key milestone was the adoption in 2022 of the Industrial Cooperation Promotion Program, which signified the transition from dialogue to practical integration [1].

However, the success of large-scale industrial cooperation in such a heterogeneous region depends on overcoming barriers such as logistical gaps, differences in standards, and levels of technological development. In this context, digital transformation ceases to be a mere auxiliary tool and becomes a systemic prerequisite, redefining the very logic of interaction.

The objective of this article is to analyze how the development of specialized digital platforms within the SCO forms a new architecture of industrial cooperation, promoting the emergence of transnational industrial ecosystems.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in viewing the digital initiatives of the SCO (in energy, technology transfer, and the digital economy) not as isolated services, but as interconnected elements of a unified digital ecosystem infrastructure. These platforms function as a ‘digital contour’ that integrates participants and supports the entire cycle of collaborative activity.

The analysis of contemporary models of industrial cooperation necessitates moving beyond traditional paradigms. The cluster approach, which focuses on the geographical agglomeration of interconnected companies, proves insufficient for understanding the dynamic, transnational, and digitally mediated forms of interaction characteristic of the twenty-first century. A more adequate analytical lens is the ecosystem approach, which considers industrial development as the result of the co-evolution of heterogeneous yet interdependent actors (companies, states, research centers, development institutions) united by the common goal of creating value within a specific technological or industrial domain.

In the context of accelerated digitalization, a key element structuring such ecosystems is digital platforms. In this article, the term ‘digital ecosystem platform’ refers not merely to a website or application, but to a deliberately created digital infrastructure that performs several interrelated systemic functions. It serves as a mechanism to reduce transaction costs by ensuring informational transparency, implementing standardized procedures, and algorithmically selecting counterparties. The platform plays the role of a system integrator for multilateral interactions, enabling heterogeneous participants — from suppliers and customers to technological partners and investors — not only to find each other but also to effectively coordinate joint activities. Furthermore, its key function is to support the entire cooperation cycle, from idea generation and partner search to joint development, production organization, and market entry. Thus, the platform materializes a digital interaction loop that ensures the continuity and integrity

of collaborative activities in a geographically distributed environment, transforming fragmented opportunities into sustainable value creation chains.

The digital transformation of cooperation within the SCO is not a spontaneous response to recent crises but represents the outcome of gradual institutionalization that has passed through several qualitative stages.

The initial phase (2004-2018) focused on addressing specific technical challenges to facilitate cross-border interaction. As early as 2004, the SCO Working Group on E-Commerce was established, and in 2009-2010 A unified electronic signature system and an online trade-investment platform were implemented [2]. These measures were utilitarian in nature, aimed at digitizing specific processes, primarily in the trade sector, without intending to change the cooperation model as a whole.

The turning point (2019-2022) was the recognition of digitalization as a systemic factor in economic development and security. In 2019, the SCO Concept of Cooperation in Digitalization and ICT was adopted, and in 2020, a communiqué on the harmonization of digital technologies was issued [2]. However, 2022 became a pivotal year for industrial cooperation, when, against the backdrop of global upheavals, the Program to Stimulate Industrial Cooperation among the Business Circles of the SCO Member States was finally agreed upon and adopted [1; 3]. It was precisely within the framework of this program's discussion that the idea of establishing Centers for Industrial Cooperation in the SCO countries was proposed as a practical mechanism for its implementation [3]. This initiative marked the shift from digitalizing procedures to designing digital infrastructure for deep production integration, serving as the conceptual prototype of future ecosystem platforms.

The period from 2023 to 2025 marked the transition to the phase of practical construction of the network ecosystem, when specific digital institutions began to emerge, endowing previously adopted concepts with tangible content. This was manifested in a shift away from universal solutions toward deep sectoral and functional specialization of platforms, which started to form a complementary network. Its key nodes included the sectoral Energy Cooperation Platform, launched by China to consolidate efforts in the 'green' transition [4], and the China Technology Transfer Center, which assumed the role of operator connecting companies and regions such as Moscow for localization projects and joint research [5]. The most comprehensive functionality was developed by specialized platforms in Tianjin, which provide not merely communication but a complete service cycle — from technology demonstrations in joint laboratories to the implementation of specific projects, as clearly exemplified by fulfilling a request from a Russian enterprise for artificial intelligence integration [6]. Thus, an evolution took place from tools for trade via concepts and programs to the launch of a network of specialized platform-ecosystems, where each element, interacting with others, enhances the overall effect, which is a characteristic feature of the maturing digital environment of industrial cooperation.

The digital infrastructure being developed within the framework of the SCO is not a homogeneous space but exhibits a clear architecture with a division of functions among various platforms and their close integration with the physical world. A multi-level system is emerging, where each ‘floor’ addresses its own tasks, ensuring the seamless progression of a project from conception to market implementation.

Despite the dynamic development of digital platforms, their transformation into a fully-fledged framework for a sustainable industrial ecosystem of the SCO faces a number of systemic challenges. Firstly, a deep digital and innovation divide persists among the member states, clearly demonstrated by the significant disparity in their positions in reputable international rankings. According to the latest UN E-Government Development Index (2024), positions range from 24th (Kazakhstan) to 136th (Pakistan), with a gap of 112 places [7]. An even more pronounced contrast is observed in the sphere of fundamental innovation potential. In the Global Innovation Index 2024 (GII), the gap between the most (China, 11th place) and the least (Tajikistan, 107th place) innovation-developed members of the organization reaches 96 positions [8]. Such heterogeneity in the innovation and digital landscape presents a key challenge for the organization, as building a balanced ecosystem requires transforming these differences from a potential source of asymmetry into a basis for complementarity and mutual growth. Secondly, to fully realize the potential of digital circuits, further efforts are required to harmonize technical, regulatory, and manufacturing standards. Discrepancies in certification standards, data requirements, and interaction protocols can negate the advantages of digital platforms, leaving the ‘last mile’ of integration unfulfilled. Finally, scaling cooperation through digital environments greatly heightens the importance of cybersecurity and intellectual property protection issues. Trust in platforms as a secure space for exchanging critically important industrial data and technologies is an essential prerequisite for their long-term viability.

Overcoming these barriers and realizing the potential of the digital ecosystem necessitate focused actions. A key prospect is the deep integration of national digital strategies (such as the new Russian Federation national project “Data Economy and Digital Transformation of the State” starting in 2025 or Kazakhstan’s plans to establish a digital state by 2026) with the SCO supranational platform architecture. This will prevent the creation of parallel digital realities and instead use the SCO platforms as the key interaction infrastructure, ensuring the compatibility of national initiatives. Such an approach provides businesses and government entities access to broader markets, data, and collaborative technological projects (notably in the field of artificial intelligence) at a new stage of digital transformation.

Alongside the development of technological infrastructure, investment in the ‘soft’ components of the ecosystem — human capital and institutions of interaction — is also necessary. A key role in this context is assigned to the Digital Literacy Development Program, adopted as part of the comprehensive package of

SCO initiatives [2]. Measures of this kind at the organizational level are critically important for overcoming digital inequality and preparing personnel capable of working effectively within a transnational digital environment.

The ultimate objective of platform development is their evolution from passive communication venues into active tools of sectoral coordination. The key principle underlying the cooperation established by the 2022 Program — the promotion of industrial cooperation among business communities [1] — can at this new stage be realized through the analytical capabilities of digital platforms. The accumulation and analysis of data on production capacities, competencies, and ongoing projects will enable the offering of optimal, mutually complementary cooperation schemes to participants, minimizing duplication and facilitating the formation of specifically regional value creation chains. This approach, clearly demonstrated by the already operational technology transfer projects [5] and digital services [6], establishes the foundation for a sustainable model of joint industrial development, where the digital ecosystem serves as the framework for strategic planning across the entire SCO.

The conducted analysis demonstrates that digital transformation within the Shanghai Cooperation Organization has transcended mere modernization of communications, forming a new architecture of economic interaction. Specialized digital platforms, having evolved from instrumental services to integral elements of the emerging ecosystem, assume the role of the ‘digital contour’ of industrial cooperation. They connect disparate actors, reduce transaction costs, and provide comprehensive project support — from conception to localization. Despite persistent challenges such as digital and innovation inequality and inconsistency of standards, the focused development of this platform network, closely linked with physical and institutional infrastructure, paves the way for establishing a sustainable model of joint development. Thus, the SCO, through the prism of digital ecosystems, is developing a model in which technological sovereignty is achieved not through autarky, but through deepened, technologically mediated interdependence and synergy across the Eurasian space.

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通过实施闭环维修循环模型来减少冶金厂的碳足迹
**REDUCING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF A METALLURGICAL
PLANT BY IMPLEMENTING A CLOSED-LOOP REPAIR CYCLE
MODEL**

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摘要：在全球脱碳和日益严格的环境、社会及公司治理（ESG）要求的背景下，冶金企业被迫开发综合解决方案以减少其碳足迹。除了技术现代化之外，实施循环经济原则也蕴藏着巨大的潜力，尤其是在优化重载运行设备的生命周期方面。本文以某冶金企业轧机轴部件的修复为例，评估了实施闭环维修循环模式的经济和环境效益。

关键词：碳足迹，黑色冶金，循环经济，冶金脱碳。

Abstract. *Amid global decarbonization and tightening ESG requirements, metallurgical companies are compelled to develop comprehensive solutions to reduce their carbon footprint. Beyond technological modernization, significant potential lies in implementing circular economy principles, particularly in optimizing the lifecycle of equipment operating under heavy loads. The article presents an assessment of the economic and environmental efficiency of implementing a closed-loop repair cycle model using the example of restoring rolling mill shaft components at a metallurgical enterprise.*

Keywords: *carbon footprint, ferrous metallurgy, circular economy, metallurgy decarbonization.*

Key approaches to decarbonizing ferrous metallurgy enterprises, besides technological methods for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and the adoption of low-carbon energy, include the implementation of circular economy principles. [1] In the context of global competition, the development of ESG practices, and tightening environmental regulations [2], the metallurgical industry is compelled to reconsider traditional approaches to the operation of fixed assets. A key strategic challenge is to find a balance between the reliability of expensive equipment and the necessity for strict control over operational costs. In this context, optimizing

the restoration processes of critically important units, such as the axes of rolling mill shafts, evolves from a technical task into a crucial element of the economic and environmental sustainability of the enterprise.

The axes of rolling mill rolls are key structural elements of the rolling mill, directly determining the continuity of the technological process, the quality of the produced products, and the economic performance of the production. Their significance extends beyond that of a machine component, acquiring strategic importance for the metallurgical enterprise.

The rolling mill roll shaft is the power and technological core of the entire rolling process. Its reliability and service life directly affect productivity, production cost, stability of the production rhythm, capital and operating expenses for mill maintenance, as well as industrial and environmental safety. Shaft failure results in the immediate shutdown of the rolling mill and the entire rolling line. The shaft's service life often dictates the frequency of scheduled preventive maintenance. Shaft failure during rolling constitutes a major accident causing prolonged downtime, damage to adjacent assemblies (bearings, drive spindles), and necessitates complex restorative repair. The shaft is manufactured from high-alloy steels (often forged) and undergoes complex heat treatment and machining. Its cost represents a significant portion of the total cost of the composite roll. During intensive operation, especially in rail-beam mills, shaft replacement due to wear is a regular and costly procedure, constituting a substantial part of the repair fund budget.

Materials and methods

The research methodology includes: an analysis of technological solutions for the restoration of worn shafts and associated risks; techno-economic and investment analyses of establishing a high-tech surfacing and precision machining workshop at JSC 'EVRAZ ZSMK'; and an assessment of the carbon footprint of implementing the proposed initiative.

Results and its discussion

The lifecycle management of shafts, encompassing modern methods of diagnostics, restoration, and reuse, ceases to be a secondary task of the repair department. It becomes a strategic direction for increasing the competitiveness and sustainability of the metallurgical enterprise, exemplified by the implementation of circular models. Investments in the preservation and regeneration of this unit are repeatedly recouped owing to the guaranteed continuity of the primary technological process.

An example illustrating the relevance of this issue is the experience of JSC 'EVRAZ ZSMK', where operational wear of rolling mill shafts due to extreme cyclic and thermal shock loads generates a constant demand for costly renewal of the equipment fleet. Financial expenditures allocated to the procurement of new components impose a significant burden on the production cost of the plant's output.

In response to this challenge, a transition to a resource-saving closed-loop model is proposed, based on a combined method for the restoration of worn shafts. The core of the solution lies in the sequential application of advanced surfacing and precision machining. This approach ensures a multiple increase in the service interval of the component while significantly reducing direct costs compared to purchasing a new unit. For the systematic implementation of this initiative and the transition from experimental to serial deployment, a structured technical and economic feasibility study complying with the requirements of modern standards and investment practices is required.

The technological foundation of the proposed initiative was established through the analysis of current research and patent solutions [3-7], confirming the maturity and effectiveness of restoration technologies. Modern techniques, such as automated submerged arc welding or powder wire welding followed by heat treatment and machining on CNC machines, enable not only the restoration of the part's geometry but also the formation of a surface layer with improved operational properties. This provides the restored shaft with a service life amounting to 80-90% of that of a new product.

The project of JSC 'EVRAZ ZSMK' envisions the establishment of a workshop on existing premises, designed for the restoration of 90 shafts annually. The total investment volume, including the procurement of specialized equipment (welding automation, CNC lathe and screw-cutting machine), its installation, and premises preparation, is estimated at 13 million. rubles, financed from the company's own funds.

The calculation of operating costs for restoring one shaft is approximately 115 thousand rubles. while the average price of a new shaft reaches 550 thousand rubles. Thus, the economic effect (income) of the project is generated by cost avoidance and amounts to approximately 435 thousand rubles per unit. With a planned annual volume of 90 units, the annual cash flow reaches 39.15 million rubles.

The financial analysis of the project, conducted over a 5-year planning horizon with a 20% discount rate, demonstrates exceptionally high efficiency indicators: the NPV is 104 million. rub., payback period of less than 5 months.

The project is characterized by a low risk level owing to the use of equity capital, a short payback period, guaranteed domestic demand, and controlled technology. The most significant risk — non-compliance with quality — is mitigated through the implementation of a multi-level system for incoming and outgoing quality control.

The implementation of this project extends beyond local cost savings. It represents a conceptual shift from the linear model 'purchase-use-dispose' to a circular economy, whereby tooling becomes a managed asset with an extended lifecycle. This contributes to reducing dependence on external suppliers (import substitution); increasing production profitability through cost optimization; a significant reduction in the carbon footprint through minimization of metal waste and energy

consumption in the production of new billets; laying the foundation for the future digitalization of equipment lifecycle management.

Implementation of a closed-loop repair cycle for rolling mill shafts results in a systemic reduction of the carbon footprint of metallurgical production, manifested in several interrelated aspects:

1. Reduction of emissions from primary metal production. Manufacturing a single new shaft weighing several tons requires steel smelting in converters or electric furnaces with high energy consumption (4000-6000 kWh per ton) and significant direct CO₂ emissions (1.8-2.2 tons of CO₂ per ton of steel). Restoring 90 shafts annually saves 180-250 tons of cast steel, preventing emissions of 350-550 tons of CO₂-equivalent per year at the metallurgical processing stage alone.

2. Reducing the energy intensity of mechanical processing by minimizing the number of machining stages of the part. Restoration requires surfacing only the worn surfaces followed by subsequent machining, whereas the production of a new shaft from forging or casting includes: rough machining of the blank; heat treatment (bulk quenching, tempering); finish grinding. The total reduction in energy consumption for mechanical operations amounts to 60-70% compared to the complete manufacturing cycle of a new part.

3. Elimination of logistics-related emissions. The creation of a roll regeneration facility eliminates the transportation of new shafts from external manufacturers (often abroad) over distances of up to several thousand kilometers, as well as the reverse logistics of worn parts for recycling. For 90 shafts, the total transportation savings amount to approximately 50-80 tons of CO₂ per year (assuming an average transport distance of 1500 km by road and rail).

4. Reduction of waste and reuse of secondary materials. The zero waste principle is implemented, as the worn shaft is not sent to scrap metal but serves as the basis for a new part. Surfacing with wear-resistant alloys consumes 5-7 times less metal than is required for casting a new blank. Eliminating the need to remelt scrap into steel additionally saves approximately 500 kW·h of energy per ton of scrap.

5. The indirect environmental effect is manifested in the extension of the service life of associated equipment: restored shafts ensure more stable operation of rolling stands, reducing the frequency of repair and replacement of other components, which also decreases the material and energy intensity of maintenance. Reducing the overall energy intensity of production enhances the potential for transitioning to renewable energy sources within a metallurgical enterprise.

For the proposed project of refurbishing 90 shafts annually, the cumulative carbon footprint reduction can be estimated at 900-1200 t CO₂-equivalent per year, which is comparable to emissions from burning 350-400 t of hard coal, the annual carbon footprint of 60 average vehicles with a mileage of 20,000 km/year, or the CO₂ absorption by approximately 150 hectares of forest.

Overall, the investment project has strategic significance for the ESG agenda of the metallurgical industry, as it contributes to achieving Russia's national climate goals, reduces the carbon intensity of products, and improves the ESG rating of the manufacturing enterprise, which is important for accessing international markets and obtaining 'green' financing. It is a practical implementation of the circular economy, transforming the linear model of 'extraction-production-waste' into a closed-loop system.

Thus, the establishment of a shaft regeneration facility is not only economically advantageous but also environmentally responsible, contributing to the sustainable development of the enterprise and the metallurgical industry as a whole by reducing the carbon footprint throughout the entire equipment lifecycle.

The presented techno-economic justification convincingly demonstrates the high investment attractiveness and operational feasibility of the project for organizing a rolling mill shaft restoration facility. The implementation of the project will provide JSC 'EVRAZ ZSMK' with substantial annual savings, a rapid return on investment, enhanced technological independence, and a contribution to the environmental sustainability of production, thereby strengthening the enterprise's long-term competitiveness.

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旅游行业人员培训的国际经验：模式、原则及对俄罗斯的适应潜力
**INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN TRAINING PERSONNEL FOR
THE TOURISM INDUSTRY: MODELS, PRINCIPLES,
AND ADAPTIVE POTENTIAL FOR RUSSIA¹**

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摘要：本文对几个发达国家（瑞士、奥地利、法国、英国、加拿大、美国、泰国）旅游和酒店业人员的专业培训体系进行了比较分析。文章识别了关键模式、共同的有效性原则和各国国情。基于标杆分析，本文提出了在俄罗斯旅游休闲综合体人员培训体系现代化背景下，借鉴国际最佳实践的关键方向。文章特别强调了机构间合作、实践导向型培训模式和灵活的教育路径的发展。

关键词：职业教育，旅游，酒店业，国际经验，人员培训，二元制培训，实践导向型方法，机构间合作，模式借鉴。

Abstract. *The article presents a comparative analysis of professional training systems for personnel in the tourism and hospitality sectors in several developed countries (Switzerland, Austria, France, United Kingdom, Canada, USA, Thailand). Key models, common principles of effectiveness, and national characteristics are identified. Based on the benchmarking conducted, key directions for adapting the best international practices are formulated within the context of modernizing the Russian system for training personnel for the tourism and recreation complex. Special emphasis is placed on the development of interinstitutional partnership, practice-oriented training formats, and flexible educational trajectories.*

Keywords: *professional education, tourism, hospitality industries, international experience, personnel training, dual training, practice-oriented approach, interinstitutional partnership, adaptation of models.*

¹ The article was prepared within the framework of fulfilling the state assignment of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Bashkortostan.

Introduction

The globalization of the tourism market and the rising standards of service quality impose increased demands on the competencies of specialists in the hospitality industries. Ensuring the competitiveness of the national tourism product requires a personnel training system that meets international standards. In this context, the study and critical analysis of foreign experience becomes a strategic objective. The purpose of this article is to analyze the variety of personnel training models, to identify the invariant principles underlying their successful operation, and to assess their potential for adaptation to the Russian educational system.

1. The diversity of national models: from European classics to Asian innovations

The analysis demonstrated that despite integration processes, personnel training systems in the tourism sector remain deeply rooted in national educational traditions and economic contexts.

European models exemplify a benchmark integration of theory and practice. **Switzerland**, the pioneer of hospitality education, has from the outset grounded it in operating enterprises. Leading institutions, such as the Swiss Hotel Management School (SHMS), are located directly at resorts, providing complete immersion in the professional environment. **Austria** has developed a complex yet coherent multilevel system with a distinctly articulated ‘through’ continuity across stages. Its cornerstone is **dual training**, whereby up to 80% of a student’s time is spent at a training enterprise, performing actual functional duties in exchange for a scholarship. This model, however, is primarily focused on training mid-level personnel (cooks, restaurant managers, assistants). **France** is characterized by strict regulatory control and a well-developed system of inter-institutional relations. Its system is distinguished by a clear hierarchical structure (ranging from vocational lyceums to doctoral programs) and varied educational pathways (short and long cycles).

The Anglo-Saxon model (United Kingdom, USA, Canada) shifts the focus to academic flexibility and managerial competencies. **United Kingdom** is the birthplace of the **modular approach**, where curricula are constructed from autonomous blocks (informational, practical, evaluative), allowing flexible customization of education to the needs of the student and the market. **USA** places strong emphasis on fundamental management theory, training “universal managers” capable of working across various industries. Less attention is paid to practical training, which is compensated by a well-developed system of career services at universities. **Canada** represents the most balanced and institutionalized ecosystem. The key role in it is played not by state standards but by market mechanisms and the professional community. Independent bodies, such as the Canadian Institute of Travel (CITS-ACTA) and the company

Emerit, conduct program accreditation and **qualification certification**, recognizing competencies acquired both through formal education and workplace experience. A unique feature is the synchronization of the academic calendar (three semesters per year) with tourist seasons, which facilitates the completion of extended paid internships.

The Asian experience, represented by **Thailand**, exemplifies the successful implementation and adaptation of the best global practices. The leading Asian Institute of Hospitality Management (AIHM) has structured its operations on a synthesis of the Swiss practice-oriented model (training based in the Minor Hotels chain) and international partnerships (Les Roches, Deloitte). The institute offers a comprehensive range of programs — from bachelor's degrees with mandatory internship semesters to short-term Executive Education courses for current professionals — demonstrating remarkable flexibility and responsiveness to industry requirements.

2. Invariant Principles of Effective Training Systems

Despite differences, all analyzed systems share a set of common principles that ensure their effectiveness:

1. **A strong practice-oriented approach.** A significant, and often predominant, part of the educational process is devoted to practice: internships at operating enterprises, work in training hotels, and case study resolution. This ensures a smooth transition for graduates into professional activities.

2. **Sustainable interinstitutional partnership.** An effective system is built upon the triad <education — business — state>. Employers not only provide internship placements but also participate in the development of standards, program accreditation, and instruction.

3. **Multilevel and flexible educational trajectories.** Systems offer a continuous vertical progression: from short-term certification courses to doctoral studies. There are mechanisms for the recognition of previously acquired competencies, which implement the principle of lifelong learning.

4. **Orientation towards international standards and mobility.** Programs include the study of foreign languages, intercultural modules, and provide opportunities for exchange semesters, thus preparing specialists to operate in a global environment.

5. **Independent quality assessment system.** In many countries (Canada, United Kingdom), trust in a diploma is ensured not primarily by state accreditation, but by recognition from authoritative professional associations and an independent qualification certification system.

3. Vectors for the Adaptation of Foreign Experience in the Russian System

The conducted analysis makes it possible to identify key directions for the modernization of the Russian system of personnel training for tourism:

1. Institutionalization of Sectoral Partnership. It is necessary to establish permanent sectoral personnel councils with real authority, uniting representatives of leading employers, educational institutions, professional associations, and government bodies. Their tasks include strategic forecasting of personnel needs, alignment of educational programs, and professional standards.

2. Widespread implementation of practice-oriented formats. An expansion of dual education on the Austrian-Swiss model is required, where the enterprise serves as an equal partner in the educational process. Legislative and financial incentives for companies to organize long-term paid internships are necessary. The establishment of a system of independent professional certification (analogous to the Canadian ‘Emerit’) is also promising, as it would complement the higher education diploma and recognize practical experience.

3. Flexibility and customer orientation of educational programs. Active implementation of the **block-modular principle** in program design is required, enabling students to develop individualized learning trajectories. Synchronization of university academic calendars with the seasonality of the tourism industry is necessary to facilitate internship completion. It is important to develop narrow specializations that are in demand by the market (ecotourism, the MICE industry, gastronomic tourism, etc.).

4. Enhancing the role of professional and public accreditation (PPA). Significant importance should be given to the results of PPA conducted by reputable industry associations. This will provide universities with a real incentive to align educational content and methods with the current demands of the industry.

5. Internationalization of education. It is advisable to develop dual-degree programs with leading foreign hospitality schools, invite foreign practitioners to deliver modules, and mandatorily include intensive language and intercultural training in the programs.

Conclusion

The international experience in personnel training for tourism represents not a set of disparate methodologies but holistic ecosystems founded on the principles of partnership, flexibility, and orientation towards the real sector. The key conclusion is that the effectiveness of the system is determined not by the degree of rigid state regulation but by the development and strength of links between its participants — educational institutions, business, and the state.

It is critically important for Russia to bridge the traditional gap between theory and practice in education. The adaptation of leading international practices, such as the development of dual education, the implementation of independent qualification certification, and the enhancement of the professional community’s role in managing education quality, can serve as a catalyst for systemic reform. This will not only raise the quality of specialist training but also cultivate a modern

professional ethos within the domestic hospitality industries, which is essential for strengthening Russia's competitive position in the global tourism market. Success will depend on the ability to create a vibrant educational environment responsive to industry demands, where the diploma is validated not only by knowledge but also by competencies recognized by professionals.

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当前银行系统发展中的问题：创新加速
**CURRENT ISSUES IN BANKING SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT.
INNOVATIVE ACCELERATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了俄罗斯和中国金融领域加速技术转型所带来的挑战。一方面，创新服务和银行产品的推出通过吸引更多客户，对银行业务产生了积极影响；另一方面，它也造成了民众和企业与银行沟通的困难，为金融和网络诈骗分子提供了可乘之机，可能威胁到银行保密义务的泄露，并削弱了公众对银行的信任。本研究旨在评估金融市场被迫数字化背景下银行业面临的脆弱性，并提出加强银行（包括新型银行）市场地位的措施。

关键词：银行体系，创新，数字化，技术，激增，经济增长，主权。

Abstract. *The article examines challenges generated by the acceleration of technological transformations in the financial sectors of Russia and China. The introduction of innovative services and banking products, on the one hand, positively influences banking business by attracting an increasing number of clients; on the other hand, it creates difficulties in communication between the population and entrepreneurs with banks, opens avenues for financial and cyber fraudsters, potentially threatens breaches of banking secrecy, and undermines trust in banks. The purpose of this study is to assess the scale of vulnerabilities in the banking sector amid forced digitalization of financial markets and to propose measures for strengthening banks' market positions, including neobanks.*

Keywords: *banking system, innovation, digitalization, technologies, surge, economic growth, sovereignty.*

The concept of the banking system and its significance for society is fundamentally linked to economic development, while the evolution of the banking system largely determines the nature of economic growth in a country. Economic theory identifies several types of economic growth, among which two principal types stand out: extensive and intensive. The former is realized through the involvement of greater quantities of resources (factors of production); the latter — through enhanced productivity and overall efficiency in resource utilization. The functions of the banking system comprise mechanisms (deposit-savings, credit-investment, payment-settlement) designed to improve business operations and enhance people's quality of life. However, nowhere is it stipulated that commercial banks must concern themselves with enterprise efficiency or with raising citizens' living standards. Banks, as business entities, will provide only those services and only in such volumes that generate greater profit for them. Thus, we observe spontaneous market development (in this case, the financial market), and as is well known, the "invisible hand of the market" establishes order through competition and self-regulation (capital flows) — via mass bankruptcies, overproduction, unemployment, recession, and other disruptions.

Consequently, the banking system as an immanent market element requires regulation and refinement, occasionally quite stringent (directive) in nature. This is corroborated by the fact that the banking sector may follow a trajectory of "self-development," temporarily detaching itself from the needs of production and the population — but with negative consequences. This phenomenon was previously discussed by the authors in published works [3]. The state must avoid miscalculating the intensity of regulation so as not to destroy the market nature of the banking system and the environment that sustains banking business. All the foregoing confirms that under contemporary conditions — characterized by a major technological transition — due attention must be paid to transformation processes within the banking system and the difficulties they generate in bank-client interactions.

Problems of digitalizing banking (and other financial) services are becoming increasingly acute, partly due to uneven development across economic sectors, the lag of citizens and businesses behind financial market professionals in terms of financial and digital literacy, and the fact that financial and cyber criminals are advancing at an accelerating pace. The problematic issues are not the digital technologies themselves or their implementation (including AI), but rather the readiness of the client base to adequately adopt and utilize all banking innovations — at exchanges, insurers, etc. — to their own benefit and that of society [2]. In this context, it is appropriate to speak of forming an adaptive model of the banking system — a transitional model toward a new technological paradigm. Simultaneously, one must consider the role the banking system ought to play in the economy and society — essentially, that of an "engine" of economic growth.

Since the early 21st century, academic literature has actively discussed ideas for accelerating the economy through enhanced investment influence via sound state investment policy — not only by the state but also by private companies, primarily large and medium-sized businesses. The term “financial surge” described a strategy of accelerated economic modernization through concentration of financial resources (state and business) in specific sectors of the national economy. It was frequently used to characterize the distinctive features of the “Asian Tigers” (Japan, South Korea, China, Singapore), which demonstrated exceptionally high growth rates [1]. It was asserted that the driver of socio-economic ascent — the accelerator of growth — lay in targeted investments and, broadly speaking, in restructuring the geography of the global economy. We shall not dispute the validity of this theory; we merely note that it has arguably exhausted its potential, possibly due to new phenomena of globalization.

The next stage in refining economic growth is the so-called “innovative surge,” a term denoting a mechanism for accelerated technology adoption in production, thereby providing impetus for global competition among nations and their capacity to ensure technological sovereignty. We emphasize that the forcing (acceleration, breakthrough) of innovations does not occur spontaneously — through certain economic clusters — but deliberately, via macro-regulation and state policy. Why does this occur? The answer lies in the scale of ongoing transformations and new challenges, risks whose consequences no one can yet predict.

The banking system serves as a powerful generator of financial resources required for economic growth and its acceleration (leap), with banks consistently at the forefront of adopting the latest achievements of the digital economy and, indeed, of digital society as a whole.

Several examples of banking innovations markedly distinguish banks from most other economic agents:

- Online banking (remote client servicing with a broad spectrum of operations and services);
- Biometric client identification;
- Robo-advisory services (regarding client accounts, investments, etc., based on AI);
- Digital currencies (e-wallets, including programmable ones);
- Digital scoring for credit approval decisions (based on instantaneous collection and processing of large datasets and diverse client information) [2].

Meanwhile, the regulator does not remain a passive observer; it actively shapes and promotes ideas of innovative banking by creating financial technology platforms and data repositories, facilitating their operation on principles of equal access, mutual interest, and security assurance.

In Russia, such projects include:

- The Mir payment card system;
 - The Unified Biometric System (UBS);
 - The Fast Payment System (FPS);
 - The System for Transfer of Financial Messages (SPFS — the domestic analogue of SWIFT);
 - The digital ruble (project operating in test mode);
 - Digital rights (digital financial assets, etc.);
 - Financial platforms (marketplaces);
 - Digital profiles for individuals and legal entities;
- Open APIs (phased implementation following the Open Finance model, with subsequent transition to the Open Data model);
- The Bank of Russia’s electronic regulatory platform (“regulatory sandbox”);
 - Cloud-based RegTech services.

Thus, the Bank of Russia initiates numerous projects and oversees their implementation, urging commercial banks not only to conduct their own developments within created ecosystems but also to actively collaborate with companies producing new technologies (“big techs”) [3]. According to the National Digital Infrastructure (NDI) Concept adopted in the Russian Federation in 2022, the principal components of digital transformation in the financial market are:

1. An electronic payment system ensuring easy and instantaneous transfer of funds between individuals, companies, and government agencies;
2. Digital client identification along with auxiliary services: electronic signatures and verifiable credentials;
3. Data exchange infrastructure enabling seamless and secure exchange of personal data, with user consent, between public and private sectors [4].

Credit institutions participate directly in developing the National Digital Infrastructure. For instance, the “Know Your Customer” platform enables banks to reliably and rapidly determine whether a prospective or existing client belongs to categories of criminalized or money-laundering agents.

Thus, by influencing credit institutions, the Central Bank addresses numerous tasks in the processes of economic transformation and transition to a new quality of economic growth. Primarily, this involves regulating money circulation, ensuring its transparency, predictability, and controllability, and tackling inflation. Additionally, the Bank of Russia successfully stimulates monetary savings in banks and redirects them toward sectors of greatest social and economic significance to achieve the state’s financial policy objectives. This is accomplished through indirect (market-based) rather than administrative instruments.

Chinese and Russian banking systems share many similar characteristics and currently perform comparable tasks. Both banking systems differ from others globally in their high concentration ratios and state participation (control):

• In the Russian Federation, approximately 2% of banks control up to 80% of the banking sector's assets, including major state banks (Sberbank, VTB, Gazprombank, Rosselkhozbank) and private banks (Alfa-Bank, Sovcombank, T-Bank);

• In the PRC, the lion's share of the market is held by the state-owned "Big Four" banks (Industrial and Commercial Bank of China — ICBC, Bank of China — BOC, Agricultural Bank of China — ABC, China Construction Bank — CCB).

China's banking system accumulates monetary resources three times the country's GDP, whereas Russia's banking system assets reach only 90% of GDP [5]. However, this indicator may be influenced by differing approaches to banking statistics in the two countries. In the Russian Federation, a strict legal definition of a bank exists (Art. 2 of the Federal Law "On Banks and Banking Activities"), and non-bank credit organizations are excluded from the two-tier banking system. In China, the banking system has a three-tier structure encompassing approximately 4,500 diverse credit institutions.

Both banking systems also share common shortcomings:

• Over-indebtedness of the population, substantial credit risks — particularly in unsecured consumer lending — and mediocre quality of retail loan portfolios;

• A large number of small, financially unstable credit institutions with low management standards and poor-quality credit portfolios;

• Not all banks maintain business plans or strategic planning systems, relying instead on tactical planning and budgeting.

Both countries' banking systems exhibit high levels of service digitalization, but China has a greater number of neobanks operating exclusively through digital banking without physical branches. In Russia, the digitalization level of financial services for enterprises stands at 80%, and for individuals at 87%, positioning the country among global fintech leaders.

China's electronic banking model emphasizes speed and convenience, actively leveraging cloud technologies and big data. The development of electronic banking in China has progressed from initially replicating models of developed nations to achieving global leadership. Today, China represents the world's largest fintech market, where digital payments and mobile applications have virtually displaced cash and plastic cards. Unlike the West, China bypassed the stage of widespread checkbook and credit card usage, transitioning directly from cash to mobile payments. The first digital giants emerged in China in December 2014: WeBank became the first fully digital bank without physical branches. Within a decade, dozens of such banks now operate in China, managing capital amounting to hundreds of billions of U.S. dollars.

The proliferation of financial ecosystems and QR code adoption has become ubiquitous in China: the primary drivers are not traditional banks but technology giants. Alipay (Ant Group) and WeChat Pay (Tencent) have transformed payments

into an integral component of daily human communication and shopping, with QR codes serving as the predominant standard. Mobile dominance manifests in smartphones becoming the principal financial instrument. In 2024, 73.2% of consumers utilized mobile payments, compared to merely 46.4% using bank cards [5]. China leads in implementing a state digital currency (CBDC). By the end of 2024, e-CNY transaction volume exceeded 7 trillion yuan (~\$986 billion).

Table 1 — Comparative analysis of financial digitalization development and consumer behavior: China, Russia [4,6]

Criterion / Parameter	China	Russia
1. Level of financial digitalization	Ultra-high, ecosystem-based. Dominance of mobile payments (Alipay, WeChat Pay) as infrastructure of daily life. Neobanks (WeBank, MYbank) — key market players in financial services	High, bank-centric. Active development of online banking and neobanks (T-Bank). Prevalence of card-based and online payments. Mixed (hybrid) service format remains popular
2. Key transformation driver	State strategy “Digital China,” technology giants (Big Tech), demand for maximum convenience	Regulator’s policy (Bank of Russia), bank competition, consumer demand for quality and security
3. Penetration of mobile / digital payments	>90% in cities; >1 billion users; share in retail payments >50%	70-80% online operations among active bank users; growing share of contactless and QR payments
4. Service format preferences	Fully digital, within super-apps. Physical branches — for exceptional cases	Mixed (hybrid) format. 60% prefer combination of online and offline; 30% — online only
5. Attitude toward neobanks / fintech	Trust as part of the ecosystem. Neobanks — natural and primary channel for youth and SMEs	Growing trust but caution. Neobanks associated with convenience, yet trust remains higher toward state banks (Sberbank, VTB, GPB)
6. Perception of cybersecurity and privacy	Paradox: high operational trust in platforms amid conscious compromise of “data for convenience.” Fear centers on direct financial losses	High vigilance. Active demand for personal data protection. Primary fear — cyber fraud and personal data leaks
7. Population’s financial literacy	Focus on advanced financial culture in digital environment. High acceptance of complex products (microloans, funds) via applications	Medium level (~61% per NAFI index). Growing share with high financial literacy. Challenges: misunderstanding of APR, lack of long-term personal financial planning

8. Population's digital literacy	Medium (Index ~7.2/10). Basic operation skills widespread. Advanced skills (AI, content creation) among 35%	Medium (71 points/100 per NAFI). Strong search and e-government skills. Weaker in content creation and collaborative work
9. Role of state and regulator	Strategic architect and strict controller. Sets frameworks ("14th Five-Year Plan"), encourages innovations (e-CNY), but strictly regulates Big Tech	Active regulator and initiator. Combines macroprudential regulation (NPL limits) with infrastructure development (FPS). Focus on consumer protection
10. Key socio-economic function of digital finance	Enhancing efficiency and convenience, building a digital society, ensuring technological sovereignty	Improving quality and accessibility of services for an already largely banked population, reducing costs

From Table 1, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. The countries occupy different stages of financial digital transformation, addressing fundamentally distinct objectives: quality enhancement (Russia) versus construction of a "digital life" ecosystem (China).

2. Divergent models of trust in banks: toward digital ecosystems (China) versus state institutions and major banks (Russia).

3. Interconnection between literacy levels and depth of banking system digitalization: literacy becomes a factor in developing more sophisticated financial markets (investments, InsurTech).

4. Role of the regulator: the state plays an active role but with differing emphases (strategist-controller — PRC; protector-moderator — RF).

This comparative analysis not only identifies differences but also reveals universal trends (growing importance of data, role of mobile devices) and nationally specific trajectories shaped by institutional environments, development levels, and cultural characteristics of the peoples.

Recognizing current challenges and prospective threats to banking systems, regulators in both countries have declared priority development directions and corrective measures: strengthening asset quality in banks as a counterbalance to high-growth dynamics; debt restructuring and consolidation of banking capital. In technological development, planned initiatives include enhanced application of artificial intelligence, big data, and blockchain — for risk assessment and improving client experience; and reinforcing cybersecurity.

Returning to the question of the fate of innovative surge in the banking systems of the analyzed countries, it should be noted that markets in both the RF and PRC exhibit "overheating" by the criterion of pace and volume of implemented innovations, as evidenced by intensifying risks and associated problems:

- Deterioration in banks' loan portfolio quality, rising concentration of banking capital (large-scale consolidation of rural banks and institutions in China; mergers and acquisitions of troubled banks by larger ones in Russia), consequently leading to stricter centralized regulation and diminished level and role of interbank competition;

- Proliferation of unethical banking practices in client servicing (mis-selling, non-transparent contracts, false advertising, etc.);

- Expansion of cyber- and financial fraudsters' activities, growing monetary losses among bank clients;

- Declining public trust in banking institutions.

Another problem related to forced innovation by commercial banks concerns the asymmetry in utilization of resource potential among individual banks, primarily those with state participation in capital. In effect, the largest state-owned banks, leveraging free resources — funds in federal and regional budget accounts — increase expenditures on innovation investments, markedly “pulling ahead” of other sector participants. These banks also expand spending on their ecosystems with financial support from state structures, pursuing the objective of attracting the maximum number of clients. This likewise violates principles of competitive struggle within the banking system, thereby narrowing consumers' choice of high-quality financial services.

What recommendations or development pathways can be proposed for banking systems amid rapid development and implementation of financial innovations? In our view, precise coordination is required between the pace of enhancing banking innovativeness and clients' financial literacy levels, as well as professionals' competency levels.

More broadly, it is necessary to develop an adaptive model of the banking system for the “transitional period,” utilizing specialized instruments for regulating innovative business processes and innovative banking services.

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全球贸易冲突期间报关服务的市场营销
**MARKETING OF CUSTOMS BROKERAGE SERVICES DURING
GLOBAL TRADE CONFLICTS**

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摘要：本文探讨了地缘政治和贸易冲突时期报关服务营销所面临的问题。文章以2021-2024年全球海运集装箱货运代理市场的剧烈变化为例，分析了当前国际贸易形势的不稳定性，并指出了报关服务营销领域面临的新挑战。作者认为，构建一种特殊的商业生态系统，促进全球物流公司与政府之间的紧密合作，是提高报关效率的契机。

关键词：营销，国际贸易，贸易冲突，报关服务，商业生态系统

Abstract. *The paper discusses the problems of marketing customs brokerage services in the periods of geopolitical and trade conflicts. The example of dramatic changes in the global ocean container freight forwarding market in 2021-2024 has been analyzed to demonstrate the instability of the current situation in international trade. New challenges in the area of customs brokerage service marketing have been identified. The authors consider the concept of a special type of business ecosystems allowing close partnership between global logistics companies and governments as a source of opportunities for efficient customs brokerage.*

Keywords: *marketing, international trade, trade conflicts, customs brokerage services, business ecosystem*

Introduction. Over the last four years, the world has been undergoing a drastic shift in international trade relations. This period of time is marked by ever strengthening protectionist trends and the use of trade barriers and sanctions aimed at reaching unilateral economic gains or geopolitical goals by some countries or supranational associations. Those processes gained in momentum with the start of the intensive military conflict between the Russian Federation and Ukraine in February 2022 and then grew in scale after the presidential elections of 2024 in

the USA and especially with the adoption of the *National Security Strategy of the United States of America* in November 2025 [1]. The above events caused considerable disruption of global trade and logistics and, therefore, created new difficult challenges for customs brokerage service providers. This paper presents an attempt to summarize the major consequences of such challenges and considerations regarding some opportunities for their overcoming.

Main discussion. The disruption of international trade markets in 2022 immediately following the beginning of the post-pandemic recovery has reshaped dramatically and continues to impact global flows of goods. The ocean container shipping sector was among the most severely hit industries. The changes in the situation are illustrated by Fig. 1 below. After a moderate decrease in 2022, the market dropped by over 4 million TEUs having lost 7% of its previous-year size in 2023. During the following year the market experienced considerable growth, and, according to early estimates, the level of 2021 was reached in 2025. The market landscape, however, underwent important changes shown in Table 1 and Fig. 2 demonstrating the dynamics of the scale of operations and market shares of top 4 players jointly accounting for about 25% of the total ocean container freight forwarding market size measured in Twenty-foot Equivalent Units (TEUs).

The data presented show that Chinese logistics company Sinotrans Ltd became the world's largest ocean container freight forwarder in 2024 (while being the 10th large global logistics business by 2024 gross logistics revenue) [5].

Source: [2].

Figure 1 — Global container freight forwarding volumes in 2021-2025 (2025 estimate).

The above-mentioned changes concerned not only volumes and market shares but also the global rankings of major players.

Table 1 — Positions of global top 4 players of ocean container freight forwarding market in 2021-2024

Company	Country	2021			2022			2023			2024		
		TEUs	Share of Global Size, %	Global Rank	Size, TEU	Share of Global Volume, %	Global Rank	TEUs	Share of Global Volume, %	Global Rank	TEUs	Share of Global Volume, %	Global Rank
Sinotrans Ltd	China	3770	5,96	2	3750	6,04	2	3890	6,74	2	4872	7,87	1
Kuehne + Nagel	Switzerland	4310	6,82	1	4613	7,43	1	4386	7,60	1	4310	6,96	2
DHL	Germany	2832	4,48	3	3142	5,06	3	3294	5,71	3	3314	5,34	3
DSV	Denmark	2204	3,49	4	2900	4,67	4	2665	4,62	4	2686	4,33	4

Sources: [3], [4].

Figure 2. Market share dynamics of global top 4 ocean container freight forwarders

Sinotrans constantly increased its share in global ocean container logistics operations in 2022-2024. The other 3 top players have declined in terms of market share since 2023.

Now, international trade and global logistics is characterized by swift and often unpredictable changes caused by economically and politically motivated decisions taken by powerful countries and supranational associations (mostly by USA and European Union). The resulting shifts in trade structure and geography are difficult to cope with even by large global private trade and logistics companies. Such situation creates certain threats and opportunities for the players of global customs brokerage service markets related to the following major factors:

- Frequently changed customs rules and regulations in major exporting and importing countries,
- Increasing lack of international collaboration between national customs authorities;
- Increasing flow of information to be taken into account immediately;
- Unpredictability of changes.

The impact of those factors is especially strong because global logistics companies, like most contemporary top market players, are not isolated businesses but business ecosystems described by J. F. Moore as communities of enterprises crossing the borders of industries and co-evolving their capabilities [6 — P. 76]. Therefore, their activities directly influence the performance of great number of market participants working in various sectors.

It is, however, worth noting that after market-oriented reforms in previously entirely or mostly state-controlled economies, like e.g. China, former USSR, some Middle East countries, etc., certain new types of ecosystems have been emerging, which has not yet drawn enough attention in the economic research literature, one of the rare exclusions being the paper dealing with China's Social Credit System published in 2022 [7]. It describes a publicly run organization called "state-controlled ecosystem." There is, however, another ecosystem type, being a business ecosystem including a number of private businesses organized around a leading organization which is either a public entity or a corporation under some kind of government control, e.g. a large public company with a government's majority share. Such ecosystem was described in a recent publication by a co-author of this paper as "administrated business ecosystem" [8]. Its structure is shown on Fig. 3.

In administered business ecosystems, regulatory and inspecting public entities, certification and standardization bodies as well as businesses that may be state-owned or controlled are core members of ecosystem communities.

In the situation of drastically changing market landscape caused by worsened international relations, the marketing function at enterprises participating in an administrated business ecosystem (hereinafter, ABE) may be more efficient than within a classical business ecosystem due to the access to insights and up-to-date sensitive information from government bodies as well as direct or indirect support provided by the government. On the other hand, the important role of ABEs in

a given economy may contribute to making the relevant nation’s customs and economic policy more pragmatic and less ideologically motivated as the government is directly interested in the financial stability of the ecosystems.

Source: [8]

Figure 3 — High-level structure of administrated business ecosystem

In the authors’ opinion, the above features of ABEs are likely to be one of the strengths that enabled Sinotrans Ltd. to successfully compete in the ocean container freight forwarding market as that company is a typical example of ABE. As most large logistics company, Sinotrans is also a customs brokerage service provider. It is a subsidiary of the publicly controlled China Merchants Group, which, as of August 2024, held a 59%-stake in Sinotrans’ capital, which allows align the activities of the latter with China’s logistics objectives [9]. As a result, deep partnership of the company with government’s bodies makes its marketing strategy more resilient in the current unstable geopolitical situation.

Conclusions. Customs brokerage market is highly sensitive to changes in the geopolitical situation and trade conflicts. The success of customs brokerage service marketing in the periods of international trade conflicts depends on the ability

of large logistics ecosystems to cope with fast-changing economic and regulatory environment and forecast future developments. Such ability is higher when global logistics market players work in close collaboration with governments of the relevant headquarter countries. It can be effectively reached in administrated business ecosystems (ABEs) led either directly by government's bodies or by businesses with majority shares owned by the state. The authors deem useful further research of the problems of marketing within ABEs and ecosystems in general.

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贸易碎片化与区域重组：上海合作组织出口格局结构性变化的证据
**TRADE FRAGMENTATION AND REGIONAL REORIENTATION:
EVIDENCE ON STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN SCO EXPORT
PATTERNS**

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摘要：本研究考察了在全球贸易日益碎片化的背景下，上海合作组织成员国对外贸易的结构性转变。研究利用应用程序编程接口（API）获取的公开年度贸易统计数据，构建了涵盖2010年至2023年十个成员国的国家-年份面板数据。分析考察了三个维度：出口至成员国的份额、以赫芬达尔-赫希曼指数衡量的出口目的地集中度以及出口伙伴分布的结构性变化。结构性转变的量化指标为结构性转变系数和詹森-香农散度，均以各国的基准年为基准年计算。研究结果表明，随着出口地理格局的不断重塑，成员国内部出口导向性逐渐增强。各国之间的格局仍存在差异，表明成员国之间存在不对称的调整路径和不同的区域一体化程度。

关键词：上海合作组织，结构性转变，出口地理格局，区域贸易一体化，贸易碎片化。

Abstract. *This study examines structural shifts in the foreign trade of the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation member states under conditions of increasing global trade fragmentation. Using open, publicly available annual trade statistics retrieved via an application programming interface, a country-year panel for ten member states covering 2010-2023 is constructed. The analysis considers three dimensions: the share of exports directed to member states, export destination concentration measured by the Herfindahl-Hirschman index, and structural changes in the distribution of export partners. Structural shifts are quantified using the coefficient of structural shifts and the Jensen-Shannon divergence, computed relative to each country's base year. The findings indicate a gradual increase in intra-organisational export orientation alongside an intensifying reconfiguration of export geography. Cross-country patterns remain*

heterogeneous, pointing to asymmetric adjustment paths and differing degrees of regional integration among member states.

Keywords: *SCO, structural shifts, export geography, regional trade integration, trade fragmentation.*

The global trading system has increasingly exhibited signs of fragmentation, reflected in the reconfiguration of trade links and the growing relevance of regional partnerships [1, 4]. In this context, the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO) provides an important institutional setting for examining how member states adapt their external trade structures [8]. While the notion of “integration” is often proxied by the intra-bloc share of trade, a deeper understanding requires measuring changes in the entire distribution of trade partners, i.e., structural shifts in export geography [7].

This study contributes by combining a simple integration proxy (intra-SCO export share) with distribution-based measures of structural shifts and concentration. We build a reproducible, fully automated pipeline using open API data, producing a compact empirical assessment suitable for cross-country comparison within the SCO.

Materials and methods

The empirical analysis is based on open annual trade statistics from the World Bank WITS TradeStats database obtained via the SDMX-JSON API [9]. The sample includes 10 member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (China, Russia, India, Pakistan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and Belarus) for the period 2010-2023. Due to limitations of publicly available series, the maximum observation year differs across countries (2021-2023). Trade flows are measured as total export values from each reporting country to partner economies without product-level disaggregation.

For each reporter i , partner p , and year t , export value is denoted as $X_{i,p,t}$, and total exports are defined as $X_{i,t} = \sum_p X_{i,p,t}$. The degree of regional trade orientation is measured by the intra-SCO export share:

$$\text{IntraSCO}_{i,t} = \frac{\sum_{p \in \text{SCO}} X_{i,p,t}}{\sum_n X_{i,p,t}}$$

Export market concentration is evaluated using the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index:

$$\text{HHI}_{i,t} = \sum_p \left(\frac{X_{i,p,t}}{\sum_p X_{i,p,t}} \right)^2$$

where higher values indicate greater dependence on a limited set of partner markets, while $1 - HHI_{i,t}$ reflects diversification. Aggregate dynamics are summarized using three series: an unweighted mean across reporters, an export-weighted mean with weights $X_{i,p}$, and a three-year moving average of the weighted series for descriptive smoothing.

To capture structural changes in the geography of exports, the full distribution of partner p shares is analyzed. The export share of partner is defined as $s_{i,p,t} = X_{i,p,t} / \sum_p X_{i,p,t}$. Structural shifts are measured relative to a country-specific base year $t_0(i)$, defined as the first available observation for reporter i , which preserves the sample under unequal time coverage. The coefficient of structural shifts is computed as

$$KSS_{i,t} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p |s_{i,p,t} - s_{i,p,t_0(i)}|,$$

and represents the proportion of exports that would need to be reallocated across partners to restore the base-year structure. As a complementary measure of distributional change, the Jensen–Shannon divergence is computed:

$$JSD_{i,t} = \frac{1}{2} \text{KL}(s_{i,\cdot,t} \parallel m) + \frac{1}{2} \text{KL}(s_{i,\cdot,t_0(i)} \parallel m), m = \frac{1}{2}(s_{i,\cdot,t} + s_{i,\cdot,t_0(i)}),$$

Where denotes the Kullback–Leibler divergence. While KSS provides an intuitive reallocation metric, JSD captures information-theoretic distance between partner distributions.

To relate dynamics to the period of intensifying global trade fragmentation, averages are reported for three subintervals: 2010–2014, 2015–2019, and 2020–2023. The earliest interval includes eight countries due to later data availability for Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, whereas the subsequent intervals cover all ten member states. Cross-country comparisons are additionally performed using the last available observation for each country, $t_{last}(i)$, to ensure full representation. Specifically, the integration–shift typology figure $IntraSCO_{i,t_{last}(i)}$ plots against $KSS_{i,t_{last}(i)}$, with computed relative to the country-specific base year.

Results and its discussion

The results first document the aggregate dynamics of regional orientation in SCO trade. The average intra-SCO export share increases steadily over 2010–2023, rising from **0.069** in 2010 to **0.112** in 2023 and reaching a peak of **0.122** in 2022, which indicates a gradual strengthening of intra-bloc linkages rather than a discrete shift (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Average intra-SCO export share of SCO member states, 2010-2023

To assess whether the rise in intra-SCO orientation reflects increasing dependence on a limited set of markets, export partner concentration is examined using the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index and three aggregation schemes: an unweighted mean across reporters, an export-weighted mean, and a three-year moving average of the weighted series (Figure 2). The export-weighted index displays a gradual decline over 2010-2023, indicating a moderate broadening of export destinations among the largest exporters, whereas the unweighted mean remains higher and more volatile, reflecting the greater sensitivity of smaller economies to discrete changes in partner composition. The moving-average series confirms that the downward tendency is persistent rather than driven by short-term fluctuations, implying that the strengthening of intra-SCO linkages documented in Figure 1 is not accompanied by rising overall concentration of export destinations (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Export destination concentration (Herfindahl–Hirschman Index), unweighted and export-weighted averages, 2010-2023

The time-series evidence is corroborated by period averages that jointly summarize regional orientation and structural change. The intra-SCO export share increases from **0.074** in 2010-2014 to **0.095** in 2015-2019 and **0.110** in 2020-2023. Over the same windows, the intensity of structural reconfiguration rises substantially: the average coefficient of structural shifts (KSS) increases from **0.060** to **0.109** and further to **0.147**, while the Jensen–Shannon divergence increases from **0.010** to **0.027** and **0.040**, respectively. The decomposition indicates that restructuring intensifies both within the SCO partner set and outside it: KSS computed within SCO partners rises from **0.083** to **0.124** and **0.177**, whereas the corresponding indicator for non-SCO partners increases from **0.058** to **0.105** and **0.140**. The earliest window is based on eight countries due to later data availability for Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, while the latter two windows include all ten members; the upward movement in structural-shift indicators remains evident in the periods with full coverage (Table 1).

Table 1. Average structural shift indicators and intra-SCO export share by period

Period	Countries (n)	Intra-SCO export share	KSS (overall)	JSD	KSS (SCO partners)	KSS (non-SCO partners)
2010-2014	8	0.074	0.060	0.010	0.083	0.058
2015-2019	10	0.095	0.109	0.027	0.124	0.105
2020-2023	10	0.110	0.147	0.040	0.177	0.140

Note: Indicators are averaged across available SCO member states within each period. Structural shift indices (KSS and JSD) are calculated relative to each country’s first available year (base year).

While aggregate dynamics provide a coherent picture of increasing intra-regional orientation and intensifying reconfiguration, they conceal substantial cross-country heterogeneity. Figure 3 presents a cross-sectional comparison based on each country’s last available observation, relating regional orientation (the intra-SCO export share) to structural shift intensity (measured relative to the country-specific base year). The dispersion across the two-dimensional space indicates that higher intra-SCO orientation can coexist with pronounced restructuring of export-partner distributions, whereas several weakly intra-oriented economies exhibit markedly different adjustment intensities, ranging from limited to substantial shifts (Figure 3).

The corresponding classification in Table 2 formalizes these differences using median thresholds for intra-SCO export shares and KSS. Tajikistan (**0.251**; KSS **0.198**, base year 2016), Kyrgyzstan (**0.169**; **0.166**, base year 2010), and Belarus (**0.151**; **0.223**, base year 2010) combine above-median regional orientation with above-median structural shift intensity. Uzbekistan (**0.148**; **0.088**, base

year 2017) and Kazakhstan (**0.128; 0.131**, base year 2010) exhibit above-median intra-SCO shares together with comparatively lower structural shift intensity. Iran (**0.124; 0.274**, base year 2010) and Russia (**0.089; 0.138**, base year 2010) display substantial structural shifts despite below-median intra-SCO export shares, indicating that major reconfiguration occurs primarily through changes in extra-bloc trade relations. Pakistan (**0.036; 0.114**), China (**0.032; 0.076**), and India (**0.018; 0.126**) are characterized by low intra-SCO shares and relatively low structural shift intensity, consistent with weak intra-bloc orientation and comparatively stable partner structures among large or globally diversified exporters (Table 2).

Figure 3. SCO countries: intra-SCO integration and structural shift intensity (last available year)

Table 2. SCO country typology by intra-SCO integration and structural shift (last available year)

Country	Year	Intra-SCO export share	HHI (partners)	KSS (vs base year)	Base year	Group
Tajikistan	2023	0.251	0.175	0.198	2016	High integration / High shift
Kyrgyzstan	2023	0.169	0.216	0.166	2010	High integration / High shift

Country	Year	Intra-SCO export share	HHI (partners)	KSS (vs base year)	Base year	Group
Belarus	2021	0.151	0.239	0.223	2010	High integration / High shift
Uzbekistan	2023	0.148	0.213	0.088	2017	High integration / Low shift
Kazakhstan	2023	0.128	0.181	0.131	2010	High integration / Low shift
Iran	2022	0.124	0.180	0.274	2010	Low integration / High shift
Russia	2021	0.089	0.167	0.138	2010	Low integration / High shift
Pakistan	2023	0.036	0.145	0.114	2010	Low integration / Low shift
China	2023	0.032	0.143	0.076	2010	Low integration / Low shift
India	2023	0.018	0.137	0.126	2010	Low integration / Low shift

Note: Countries are classified using median thresholds for intra-SCO export share and structural shift intensity (KSS). Values correspond to the last available year for each country.

Overall, the evidence indicates that the SCO average experiences a sustained increase in intra-bloc export orientation, while partner concentration does not increase and instead shows a slight decline over time (Figures 1-2). At the same time, structural shift measures rise markedly across successive periods, implying intensifying reconfiguration of export destinations (Table 1). Cross-country results underscore pronounced asymmetry in adjustment patterns, with some members combining relatively strong intra-SCO orientation and substantial partner-structure changes, others exhibiting significant restructuring without high intra-bloc orientation, and large exporters remaining weakly intra-oriented with comparatively stable export geography (Figure 3; Table 2).

The evidence is most consistent with a dual adjustment process rather than a simple “regionalisation” narrative [5]. The upward trajectory of intra-SCO export orientation combined with a mildly declining concentration profile implies that greater intra-bloc engagement has not been achieved through narrowing market access. Instead, the pattern indicates that intra-SCO trade has expanded within a broader rebalancing of export portfolios, where regional ties strengthen while overall destination structures remain, on average, non-more-concentrated (Figures 1-2) [6, 7]. Importantly, combining an integration proxy (intra-SCO share) with concentration and distribution-based shift measures (HHI, KSS/

JSD) allows distinguishing gradual regional reorientation from deeper structural reconfiguration of export geography.

The structural-shift measures sharpen this interpretation by indicating that the recent period is characterized by intensified reallocation of partner shares, not merely higher intra-SCO shares. The increase in KSS and JSD across successive windows implies that export geography deviates further from baseline structures, and the decomposition suggests that this reallocation involves both intra-SCO and extra-SCO partner sets (Table 1). Hence, fragmentation-related pressures appear to operate through the simultaneous reinforcement of regional channels and re-shuffling across non-SCO markets, rather than through substitution of global diversification by intra-bloc dependence [2].

Cross-country patterns underscore asymmetric integration outcomes. The integration–shift space shows that high regional orientation can coincide with substantial partner-structure change, while some countries undergo pronounced restructuring without strong intra-SCO orientation (Figure 3). This implies that intra-bloc trade may serve as an adaptation margin for some members, whereas for others adjustment is driven mainly by extra-bloc rerouting. The typology further indicates that large, globally diversified exporters tend to remain weakly intra-oriented and comparatively stable, while several smaller economies display stronger regional orientation alongside more intensive reconfiguration (Table 2). Overall, the SCO should be viewed as a channel of adjustment whose relevance is heterogeneous across member states within a broader, fragmentation-related transformation of export geography.

Conclusion

The study provides a compact, reproducible assessment of structural shifts in the export geography of SCO member states using open WITS TradeStats API data for 2010-2023. The results indicate a gradual increase in intra-SCO export orientation accompanied by a slight decline in partner-market concentration, suggesting that regional reorientation has not been driven by growing dependence on a narrow set of destinations. At the same time, distribution-based indices (KSS and JSD) point to intensifying reconfiguration of export partner structures, affecting both intra-SCO and extra-SCO linkages. Cross-country comparisons reveal pronounced heterogeneity: some members combine relatively strong intra-bloc orientation with substantial structural change, whereas others restructure primarily through extra-bloc markets, and large exporters remain weakly intra-oriented with comparatively stable partner distributions [3]. Future work can extend the analysis by incorporating product-level trade structures and additional controls to better identify the mechanisms behind observed shifts.

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分析海关政策对俄罗斯经济发展的影响在当代挑战下
**ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF CUSTOMS POLICY
ON THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF RUSSIA
UNDER CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES**

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摘要：本文分析了制裁和全球贸易变化背景下，海关政策对俄罗斯经济的影响。文章探讨了海关政策监管的理论和实践层面，以及其对对外贸易关系、财政收入和国内生产商竞争力的影响。基于统计分析，文章提出了改进海关政策的新方向。

关键词：海关政策，对外贸易，制裁压力，进口替代，海关数字化，关税监管，经济一体化。

Abstract. *This article analyzes the impact of customs policy on the Russian economy under the conditions of sanctions and changes in global trade. The theoretical and practical aspects of regulation and its influence on foreign trade relations, budget revenues, and the competitiveness of domestic producers are examined. Based on statistical analysis, new directions for policy improvement are identified.*

Keywords: *customs policy, foreign trade, sanctions pressure, import substitution, customs digitalization, tariff regulation, economic integration.*

In the context of global economic changes, customs policy is acquiring new significance, extending beyond simple fiscal control. Today, it serves as a strategic resource enabling the economy to mitigate the impact of external crises. By regulating trade flows through tariffs and special regimes, the state can adjust the structure of foreign trade, support domestic producers, and replenish the budget. However, in an environment of prolonged sanctions and structural shifts in the global economy, the existing methods of customs regulation require thorough analysis and updating [1].

To understand its role, it is important to note that as part of the system of public administration, customs policy encompasses a set of measures to influence the scale, direction, and conditions of international trade, employing both tariff and non-tariff methods. Its key tasks are protecting the domestic market, filling the state treasury,

and creating favorable conditions for national exports. However, in implementing these tasks, a fundamental dilemma arises: the need to shield local producers from foreign competition conflicts with the objective of enhancing their competitiveness and integrating them into global technological chains. This contradiction is particularly intensified under the influence of external sanctions restrictions.

Russia's foreign trade statistics clearly illustrate the consequences of these external factors. For example, in 2023, the country's foreign trade turnover volume declined, which was a direct reflection of the impact of sanctions and the restructuring of global logistics links. More recent data merely confirms this trend. According to the Federal Customs Service (FTS RF), Russia's foreign trade turnover for January — November 2025 amounted to \$622.7 billion, which is 4.1% lower than during the same period in 2024. Exports decreased by 5.3%, while imports declined by 2.4%. The trade balance remained positive but contracted by 11% over the nine months of 2025, amounting to \$101.7 billion [2]. Such a reduction adversely affects economic dynamics, diminishing export opportunities and limiting access to imported components and technologies essential for the development of advanced industries.

An analysis of the foreign trade structure reveals key vulnerabilities of the Russian economy while simultaneously highlighting prospective directions for its development. The most significant issue remains the commodity dependence of exports: more than half, namely 54.6%, of export revenue is still provided by mineral products, such as oil and gas. However, the monetary volume of this sector decreased by 16% over the eleven-month period, underscoring the risks associated with the volatility of global markets and foreign policy restrictions.

In contrast to this trend, there is an encouraging dynamic in non-commodity sectors. Exports of machinery and equipment (+23.3%), chemical products (+22.6%), and metals (+17%) have shown significant growth [3]. The steady increase in these commodity groups indicates a real potential for gradual diversification of national exports and reducing dependence on commodity markets.

On the import side, there is still a structural dependence on imported technologies and high-tech products. Almost half of all imports, or 48.2%, are made up of machinery and equipment, which is crucial for industrial modernization. The 8.9% decrease in imports of this category is a cause for concern, as it may reflect both logistical difficulties and growing challenges in updating the country's fixed capital, which could slow down its technological development in the long run [3].

In response to these challenges, there has been a significant reorientation of trade flows. The geography of trade has undergone a dramatic shift. As of the end of the first eleven months of 2025, Asian countries accounted for 73.3% of Russia's total trade volume. However, trade with Europe has decreased by 9.6%, reflecting the impact of sanctions and a deliberate reorientation [3]. One of the adaptation tools has been the mechanism of parallel imports, which has allowed

for the continued supply of certain goods despite the restrictions. However, this measure is gradually becoming more restrictive as domestic production develops. For example, in 2025, the Ministry of Industry and Trade excluded laptops and servers from the list of goods for parallel import, as well as MFPs from a number of brands (Brother, Toshiba, etc.), arguing that there was a sufficient volume of similar products from Russian manufacturers [4].

The development of parallel imports is closely linked to the overall strategy of import substitution. It has evolved from a temporary measure into a long-term government policy that has been legislated and is leading to the restructuring of the entire industrial landscape. This is evident in the launch of over seventy-two new large-scale production facilities in 2025, each with investments exceeding one billion rubles. The industries experiencing significant growth include engineering, chemistry, metallurgy, and IT.

Specific results confirm the scale of the transformations. In microelectronics, for example, the first Russian cluster systems for producing chips using a 65-nanometer process were created and launched, which laid the foundation for the formation of an independent element base. In mechanical engineering, progress was expressed in the localization of key production components, such as disc brakes for KAMAZ vehicles, and in establishing a full cycle for the production of special equipment, such as vacuum excavators in Tver. At the same time, a key law was adopted in the digital field, obliging critical information infrastructure entities to switch to domestic software, which creates a powerful incentive for the development of Russian IT products. This shows that import substitution is transforming from a set of individual measures into a holistic technological and production ecosystem.

However, the import substitution policy faces internal barriers. For example, the export of Russian microelectronics is hindered by the complex procedures for obtaining a FSTEC license for each individual shipment, which reduces competitiveness in foreign markets [2]. At this stage, integration associations play an important stabilizing role. Russia's participation in the EAEU, aimed at unifying customs tariffs and simplifying transit, helps to maintain trade within the union [2]. However, the integration framework is not fully capable of compensating for the losses incurred due to the decline in trade with Western countries, necessitating the adaptation of customs policies to the new reality.

The impact of sanctions on the Russian economy has become a permanent factor that directly affects foreign trade through the blocking of financial transactions, restrictions on access to markets, and disruptions in logistics routes. Experts note that while the impact of various restrictions varies, they collectively create systemic challenges, particularly in the high-tech and financial sectors [4]. In response to these challenges, not only have trade routes been reoriented, but new formats of cooperation have emerged. In particular, barter

transactions between Russia and China have become an innovative solution to the problem of circumventing Western payment systems, demonstrating the depth of transformation in trade mechanisms.

However, even with key partners, the dynamics indicate new challenges. Data on trade between Russia and China shows a slowdown in growth and a decline in 2025, marking the first time in five years [4]. Experts attribute this trend to the introduction of increased customs fees on certain goods and a general decrease in global demand for Russian exports. This dynamic highlights the limitations of a rigid protectionist model and emphasizes the importance of developing a more adaptive tariff system that can quickly adapt to changing market conditions.

Thus, the impact of customs regulation on the Russian economy is complex, affecting the budgetary, trade, and structural spheres. The fiscal role of customs payments remains significant for filling the budget in the context of external financial constraints. However, high import duties on technologies and components can slow down the technological renewal of industries and reduce their competitiveness. According to international studies, high trade barriers have a negative impact on economic growth in the long term, while trade liberalization stimulates growth.

Given the complex nature of today's challenges, the modernization of customs regulation requires a holistic approach that harmoniously combines fiscal and protectionist instruments with incentive measures. The strategic goal of this transformation is to create conditions for technological progress and strengthen the competitiveness of domestic producers in both domestic and foreign markets. To achieve this goal, it is crucial to establish an adaptive tariff system that can respond to the needs of the economy in a differentiated manner. This mechanism involves setting preferential rates for the import of critical technologies, components, and equipment, while simultaneously implementing protective barriers for finished products that do not promote knowledge transfer and modernization of production processes.

At the same time, there is a need for deep digitalization of the entire logistics and administrative infrastructure related to foreign trade. The creation of end-to-end digital platforms for supply chain management and the full automation of customs procedures will significantly increase transparency, speed, and predictability of processes. The implementation of modern systems for analyzing large data sets and modeling trade flows should serve as the foundation for making informed decisions in this area. By relying on up-to-date analytics and predictive scenarios, government agencies will be able to adjust the parameters of customs and tariff regulation, promptly responding to changes in the economic environment and identifying new growth opportunities. Thus, the updated system is intended to become not just an administrative barrier, but an intelligent tool for structural adaptation of the economy in a global context of instability.

Furthermore, strengthening national institutions responsible for foreign trade and deepening integration with friendly countries will help enhance the resilience of the economy in a stable global environment.

In conclusion, it can be noted that customs policy continues to be one of the central economic tools for regulation. At the moment, its impact is formed at the intersection of several factors: the fulfillment of fiscal objectives, structural adjustment in response to the transformation of global trade, and the neutralization of external restrictions. To enhance the effectiveness of this tool, it is not enough to rely solely on protectionist barriers; it is necessary to implement adaptive mechanisms that stimulate technological innovation and enhance economic stability in the long term. The strategy should combine both fiscal interests and strategic objectives to increase exports of high-tech products.

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恐慌引发的层级联盟纳什均衡转变：制度傲慢与交易成本容忍度的类型学
**PANIC-INDUCED NASH EQUILIBRIUM SHIFT IN
HIERARCHICAL COALITIONS: A TYPOLOGY OF
INSTITUTIONAL ARROGANCE AND TRANSACTION COST
TOLERANCE**

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摘要：本文提出了一种统一的层级联盟恐慌诱发纳什均衡转移（PNE）模型，该模型融合了博弈论、行为学和制度学的视角。其核心创新在于将“恐惧”形式化为一个战略性经济变量，并引入了制度傲慢（ α ）的类型学— α 是一个可衡量的参数，用于定义行动者对交易成本和声誉风险的容忍度。该模型识别出三种类型：低 α （偶然参与者，立即退出）、中 α （核心稳定，需要破坏内部纽带）和高 α （外部霸权，风险阈值突破后理性退出）。该模型表明，恐慌转移并非通过直接的资源对抗发生，而是通过弱势行动者对认知和制度环境的内生性改造而实现的。这项研究对制度经济学、行为博弈论以及监管、公司和公共治理体系中非对称冲突的战略分析做出了贡献。

关键词：恐慌引发的纳什均衡；制度傲慢；交易成本容忍度；不对称冲突；霸权；联盟稳定性；恐惧作为战略变量；层级组织。

Abstract. *The article proposes a unified model of panic-induced Nash equilibrium shift (PNE) in hierarchical coalitions, integrating game-theoretic, behavioral, and institutional perspectives. The core innovation lies in formalizing “fear” as a strategic economic variable and introducing a typology of institutional arrogance (α) — a measurable parameter defining an actor’s tolerance for transaction costs and reputational risk. Three types are identified: low α (accidental participant, immediate exit), medium α (core stability, requires internal bond disruption), and high α (external hegemon, rational exit upon risk threshold exceedance). The model demonstrates that panic shift occurs not through direct resource confrontation, but via endogenous modification of cognitive and institutional environments by a weak agent. The study contributes to institutional economics, behavioral game theory, and strategic analysis of asymmetric conflicts in regulatory, corporate, and public governance systems.*

Keywords: *panic-induced Nash equilibrium; institutional arrogance; transaction cost tolerance; asymmetric conflict; hegemon; coalition stability; fear as strategic variable; hierarchical organizations.*

1. Introduction

Modern institutional coalitions — cartels, regulatory alliances, integrated networks — exhibit remarkable resilience to traditional forms of pressure. Classical game theory explains this through stable Nash equilibria in repeated interactions, where defection incurs punishment [1, p. 286]. However, real-world conflicts reveal a paradox: such coalitions often collapse under pressure from agents with minimal resources. This paper argues that the key lies not in resource asymmetry, but in institutional arrogance (α) — a structural property determining how actors perceive risk, cost, and legitimacy.

We integrate three insights: (1) fear as a strategic variable [2, p. 1124], (2) transaction cost tolerance shaped by past status [3, p. 702], and (3) the role of internal/external hegemons in coalition dynamics [4, p. 93]. The objective is to formalize the panic-induced Nash equilibrium shift (PNE) and provide a typology of α that predicts coalition vulnerability.

2. Theoretical Foundations

Classical game theory assumes fixed payoff structures and hyper-rational agents [1]. Yet behavioral economics shows that under uncertainty, agents overweight losses and react more strongly to reputational threats than to potential gains [2, p. 263]. Institutional economics adds that transaction costs (TC) — coordination, monitoring, enforcement — are not static but shaped by organizational memory and status [3]. Crucially, perceived TC tolerance may diverge from actual costs when institutions rely on past success rather than current efficiency. Finally, asymmetric conflict theory demonstrates that weak actors win not by direct opposition, but by changing the rules of the game [4]. Our model synthesizes these strands into a dynamic framework of equilibrium shift.

3. Panic-Induced Nash Equilibrium (PNE) Model

Consider a coalition of two strong players, G1 and G2, with payoffs:

	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>
<i>C</i>	+5, +5	-10, 0
<i>D</i>	0, -10	-2, -2

(C, C) is a stable equilibrium. A weak agent m cannot alter payoffs directly but can increase individual fear of coercion:

$$F_i = P(H) \cdot S \cdot k_i \cdot (1 - \alpha_i)$$

where:

$P(H)$ = probability of hegemon intervention,

S = potential damage,

k_i = vulnerability coefficient (public exposure),

α_i = institutional arrogance. When

$$F_i > V_{cartel}$$

(fear exceeds coalition benefit), the payoff matrix shifts: cooperation becomes irrational. G_1 defects, triggering G_2 's exit. A new equilibrium (D, D) emerges — the panic-induced Nash equilibrium (PNE).

The hegemon accelerates but is not necessary: even without external intervention, repeated signals raise $P(H)$ and F_i .

4. Typology of Institutional Arrogance (α)

We classify α into three types based on empirical observation:

4.1. Low α (0.0-0.3): Accidental Participant

Recent or random coalition entry, Participation in ≤ 1 coalition,

Flat hierarchy, no institutional memory.

Response: Immediate exit (Tdecision \rightarrow min) because coalition is not “owned.”

Vulnerability: High — first to defect.

4.2. Medium α (0.4-0.7): Core Stability

Participation in ≥ 2 coalitions,

Multi-level hierarchy (≥ 3 levels),

Strong internal identity,

“Honor code” protecting lower ranks,

Internal hegemon coordinates decisions.

Response: Resists external pressure initially but collapses when internal bonds fragment. Strategy: Two-stage attack: (1) expose regulatory violations to create internal conflict, (2) activate internal hegemon to restructure or exit.

4.3. High α (0.8-1.0): External Hegemon

Always possesses external hegemon status (regulatory, financial, legal power),

Ideal compliance, high public visibility,

Professional risk management. Response: Rational, delayed exit when:

$$P_{coalition} < R_{public} + R_{collusion}$$

where $R_{collusion}$ = risk of being seen as complicit.

Key insight: Non-use of hegemonic power becomes evidence of collusion \rightarrow exit is in- evitable.

5. Institutional Arrogance as Transaction Cost Tolerance

We define acceptable transaction costs as:

$$TC_{acceptable} = f(\alpha, Rpast)$$

where R_{past} = accumulated status/resources.

Critically,

$$\frac{\partial TC_{acceptable}}{\partial TC_{real}} \approx 0$$

— perceived tolerance does not adjust to rising real costs. Thus, hierarchies with high α systematically choose strategies with escalating TC, misinterpreting procedural complexity as stability.

This creates hidden fragility: when

$$TC_{real} \gg TC_{acceptable?}$$

panic shift occurs.

6. Conclusion

The PNE model reveals that coalition stability is not determined by resources alone, but by the alignment between real risks and perceived tolerance, mediated by institutional arrogance. The typology of α provides a predictive tool for:

Antitrust policy (identifying cartel fragility),

Corporate governance (protecting minority stakeholders), Public administration (designing effective oversight).

By formalizing fear and arrogance as economic variables, this work bridges game theory, institutional economics, and strategic practice — offering a new lens on power asymmetry in the 21st century.

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中美在全球绿色能源领域的竞争
U.S-CHINA COMPETITION IN GREEN ENERGY
ON THE GLOBAL STAGE

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摘要：本文旨在分析中美两国在全球绿色能源领域的战略竞争。作者考察了历史背景、制度模式以及决定两国在太阳能、风能、储能系统和电动汽车基础设施等领域竞争地位的关键因素。研究表明，中国通过集中计划、大规模生产和供应链控制取得了主导地位，而美国则在技术创新和高科技解决方案方面保持领先。研究强调了这场竞争的综合性，它融合了经济、技术和地缘政治等多个层面，并探讨了其对全球能源转型的影响。

关键词：绿色能源，可再生能源，美国，中国，技术领先，太阳能，风能，储能系统，电动汽车，低碳转型，创新。

Abstract. *The article is dedicated to analyzing the strategic rivalry between the USA and China in the sphere of green energy at the global level. The author examines historical prerequisites, institutional models, and key factors determining the competitive positions of the two countries in segments such as solar and wind energy, energy storage systems, and electric vehicle infrastructure. It is shown that China has achieved dominance through centralized planning, large-scale production, and control over supply chains, while the USA maintains leadership in technological innovation and high-tech solutions. The research emphasizes the comprehensive nature of the competition, combining economic, technological, and geopolitical aspects, and its impact on the global energy transition.*

Keywords: *green energy, renewable energy, USA, China, technological leadership, solar energy, wind energy, energy storage systems, electric vehicles, low-carbon transition, innovations.*

At the beginning of the 21st century, the global energy system entered a phase of structural transformation, driven simultaneously by environmental, economic, and technological factors. In this context, renewable energy has transitioned from being an auxiliary segment to a key element of the global economic system. According to the

International Renewable Energy Agency, in 2024, the aggregate increase in renewable energy capacity reached record levels — approximately 585-741 GW (15-18% per year). This dynamic is considered the largest in the entire history of observation and reflects a systemic shift in the priorities of leading states in the energy sector.

The growing share of “clean” energy is also confirmed by global electricity production statistics. According to the analytical center Ember, in 2024, the combined share of low-carbon sources — including renewable energy sources (hereinafter — RES) and nuclear generation — exceeded 40% of the global energy balance for the first time. This indicates the gradual displacement of fossil fuels and a shift in focus towards developing technologies in the “green” energy sector to meet national needs.

Thus, against the backdrop of the transition to a low-carbon development model, a new configuration of relations between countries is forming in the global market, centered on competition for technological, industrial, and geopolitical leadership in the renewable energy sector. This is most pronounced in the rivalry between the People’s Republic of China and the United States of America — the two states with the greatest influence on global energy and the largest economic resources.

Over the past two decades, China has become the key production center in the global “green” industry. State support programs, industrial policy, and massive investments have allowed the country to occupy a dominant position in the markets for solar modules, wind turbines, and battery systems. The USA, in turn, retains leadership in fundamental research, high-tech innovation, and the development of a private entrepreneurial ecosystem, forming a more technologically oriented path for the development of the RES sector. The adoption of major packages such as the Inflation Reduction Act has strengthened the US desire to maintain independence from external supplies and strengthen its own industrial base.

Consequently, the rivalry between the two powers extends beyond purely technological or commercial competition. It is acquiring a comprehensive nature, including the struggle for control over supply chains of critical materials, influence on developing markets, scientific and technological superiority, and shaping the regulatory architecture of global energy. As a result, the confrontation and cooperation between the USA and China will largely determine the pace, direction, and sustainability of the global transition from one type of energy to another in the coming decades.

Historical Context of Green Energy Development in the PRC and the USA

To fully understand the modern competitive strategies of China and the USA in the renewable energy sector, it is necessary to consider the historical context of the development of this industry in both countries. A historical retrospective allows for identifying institutional, political, and economic prerequisites for the formation of national approaches in the field of RES and assessing their impact on current competitive positions.

The formation of China's state strategy in the field of RES began in the early 21st century, when, amid economic growth, the limitations of the traditional energy model, primarily focused on coal, became evident. One of the first significant initiatives was the China Township Electrification Program, launched in 2001. The program provided for the electrification of rural areas based on a combination of small hydropower, solar photovoltaic systems, and wind installations. It became one of the first large-scale projects for introducing renewable energy sources at the national level.

In 2005, the Law on Renewable Energy was adopted, which became a key regulatory act establishing the priority of RES development in state energy planning. This document set target indicators, mechanisms for mandatory connection and electricity purchase, as well as a system of support tariffs for energy producers using renewable sources.

The further development of the industry occurred within the framework of national planning, especially concerning five-year plans, which defined long-term priorities in industrial and energy policy. In particular, starting from the 12th Five-Year Plan (2011-2015), an emphasis on the development of wind, solar, and bioenergy was already observed. This laid the foundation for forming large-scale production chains and the international export activity of Chinese companies in the "clean" energy sector.

In the United States, the prerequisites for RES development were significantly different. Policy in this sphere was formed in the context of a market economy with an orientation towards private investment and technological innovation. One of the first steps were legislative initiatives at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries aimed at stimulating research in alternative energy sources and improving energy efficiency. In 1980, the Energy Security Act was passed, giving impetus to funding research in RES and related technologies. Subsequent Energy Policy Acts (1992 and 2005) provided production tax credits to support the development of wind, biomass, and other alternative technologies¹.

Support mechanisms from states and the private sector also played a significant role: tax incentives, subsidies, and grants for the deployment of solar and wind installations, among others. However, unlike China, US federal policy in this area long lacked a centralized program that could serve as an analogue to the Chinese law of 2005. American promotion of RES was more fragmented and depended on a combination of market incentives and regional initiatives.

Comparing the historical trajectories of the two countries, fundamental differences in institutional models can be identified. China relied on centralized state planning and direct support measures, which contributed to the rapid buildup of

¹ Campbell 2010: 4-7

production capacity and the creation of an extensive export base. On the other hand, the American model was more focused on market mechanisms and private capital participation, which fostered the development of competitive technological solutions but led to the creation of a branched, less centralized sector.

As a result of the chosen development trajectory, by the beginning of the third decade of the 21st century, both countries had become key players in the global RES market. Regarding strengths, it is worth noting that China is a global producer and exporter of RES components. The USA, in turn, acts as a source of technological innovation with a large domestic market for high-tech solutions.

Key Drivers of Competition at the Current Stage

The transition to a low-carbon economy increases structural demand for electricity and corresponding technologies to implement this transition: solar and wind generation, storage systems, electrification of transport and industrial processes. State climate policy and private investments create a multiplier effect — incentive measures (government procurement, tax credits, tariff schemes) contribute to increased installation volumes and form large sales markets. They, in turn, attract investments in production and research and development (R&D). Research shows that major legislative packages (e.g., infrastructure and climate incentives in North America after 2022) significantly accelerate the deployment of RES and increase competitive pressure on manufacturers in the international market¹.

Political instruments (direct subsidies, tax credits, government procurement, and infrastructure support) are a key factor determining the competitiveness of national industries. The Chinese model relies on a combination of centralized planning, subsidization, and credit support for large industrial clusters. This approach has allowed for the creation of significant export-oriented production potential in the areas of PV modules, turbines, and batteries². American policy is focused on stimulating demand and localizing production. Numerous assessments indicate that the IRA (Inflation Reduction Act) boosts investments in RES production and installation in the states.

Technological superiority remains a key factor in long-term competitiveness. This includes improving the efficiency of photovoltaic cells, reducing the specific cost of batteries, developing perovskite technologies, and solid-state batteries. Studies of patent activity, volumes of private and public investment show an increase in Chinese investment in applied technologies. At the same time, the USA still maintains an advantage in basic scientific research and high-tech niches.

Trade measures (antitrust and anti-dumping investigations, export relations, tariffs), as well as foreign policy strategies, influence the formation of the

¹ Bistline, Brown, Domeshek 2014: 2-9

² Guilhot 2022

competitive field. In response to the expanding expansion of Chinese manufacturers, many states and coalitions have already introduced or are considering introducing instruments aimed at limiting dependence on Chinese supply chains. Simultaneously, the PRC pursues an active foreign economic policy, expanding investments and exports of “green” technologies to developing regions. This approach, according to contemporary analytical reviews, helps in forming new competitive alliances and creates financial incentives.

Key Segments of Competition between China and the USA

Solar Energy. Solar energy is at the core of the global transition to a low-carbon economy and therefore is one of the segments with the highest level of competition between the PRC and the USA. Over the past two decades, China has built a vertically integrated full-cycle production chain: from quartz raw material extraction and polysilicon production to the output of solar panels, high-efficiency modules, and inverters. The key fact of China’s dominance is the combination of massive production capacity and strong support programs from the state through electricity subsidies, preferential lending, tax incentives, export promotion, and strategic industrial policy.

The USA, in contrast, does not possess comparable production clusters, creating dependence on the Asian market. The main focus of the American industry is on high-tech niche segments, such as thin-film solar cells or components for smart grid systems. However, the lack of mass production leads to higher costs, complicating competition in the global market.

It is important to emphasize that the Chinese model of dominance is based not only on low production costs but also on control over the supply of intermediate goods: wafers, cells, and silicon. Thus, China’s share in global polysilicon production exceeds 80%, and in wafer manufacturing reaches almost 97%.

As countermeasures and to reduce dependence on Chinese-made components (and thus stimulate localization), the USA has developed a set of measures — tariffs, anti-dumping investigations. However, their effectiveness is limited by structural factors: the absence of domestic supply chains, high labor and energy costs, and the fragmentation of private investments¹.

Wind Energy. The second area of rivalry is wind energy. In this field, China demonstrates comprehensive dominance in both onshore and offshore wind energy. This has been made possible by the formation of large industrial clusters that combine manufacturers of blades, gearboxes, generators, towers, control systems, and offshore platforms. Their existence ensures technological and logistical efficiency, reduces equipment costs, and facilitates rapid scaling. Moreover, the PRC pursues

¹ Gross, Sall 2025

a policy of active investment in offshore wind farms, where the cost of a single facility is higher, but this is compensated by its energy output and durability¹.

The American offshore sector is developing slowly due to regulatory barriers, complexities in permitting procedures, resistance from local communities, and high costs compared to Europe and China.

Technologically, both countries are moving towards increasing turbine capacity. China has already commissioned models exceeding 15 MW for offshore projects, while the USA relies more on importing European equipment or localized assembly. At the same time, the United States actively invests in software development, wind forecasting systems, and grid optimization.

The institutional difference plays a key role. In China, long-term quotas and industry development coordinates are determined by the government, creating predictable outcomes for business. In the USA, development depends on a combination of federal and regional incentives, which change depending on the incumbent administration, reducing the stability of the investment cycle.

Energy Storage Systems. Energy storage systems (energy batteries, ESS) are a fundamental element of the global energy infrastructure. Without large-scale ESS, it is impossible to ensure the stable operation of solar and wind power plants. Leadership in this segment also belongs to China, thanks to control over key resources (graphite, lithium, nickel, manganese), a developed recycling system, and the presence of the world's largest battery companies (CATL, BYD).

The main advantage of China lies in the ability to produce batteries on a scale that reduces costs to minimal global levels. The country has also developed unique recycling chains that allow for the repeated extraction of lithium, cobalt, and nickel, reducing dependence on external supplies².

Despite having technological centers and active private companies, the USA is in a catch-up position. Dependence on imports of almost all graphite products³ — a key anode material — significantly increases the cost of American batteries. Primarily, the United States invests in creating “post-lithium” technologies (sodium-ion, solid-electrolyte batteries), but these developments have not yet reached industrial maturity.

Electric Vehicle Infrastructure. Electric vehicles are the most public and politicized component of the energy transition, as they are directly related to end-user needs. In the 2020s, China formed the world's largest EV market, supported dozens of manufacturers — from state-owned to private — and created a powerful charging infrastructure. A key feature of the Chinese model was a unified

¹ Lu, McElroy, Peng, Liu, Nielsen, Wang 2016

² Bhuwalka, Ramachandran 2025: 5-8

³ Bhuwalka, Ramachandran 2025: 5

technological standard, which allowed for the construction of numerous charging stations across the country.

Simultaneously, China is developing a strategy of international expansion. Electric vehicles are supplied to countries in Europe and Asia, Latin America, and other developing markets, where competition with the USA is particularly noticeable. Chinese brands have many advantages: low cost, a wide selection of models, and their own standardized batteries. All this makes them competitive even in the face of import tariffs.

In the USA, the EV market has long been associated with private initiatives. The most famous has been the company Tesla, with its unique software, autonomous control, and integration of batteries and grids. However, dependence on a single company makes the industry vulnerable, and charging infrastructure remains fragmented due to the lack of a unified standard¹.

The growth rate of the EV market in the USA fluctuates depending on changes in the political course of the administration. Thus, Democrats are more inclined to increase investments in this area, while Republicans remain loyal to “traditional” methods. Shifting priorities in favor of traditional hydrocarbons or weakening climate incentives naturally leads to a decrease in demand and investment activity.

Conclusion

The prospects for the development of the global green energy market in the coming decades are determined not only by technological trends but also by the strategic rivalry between the world’s largest economies. This study concludes that the competitive interaction between China and the USA in this sphere is systemic, multi-level, and long-term. It includes the struggle for production control, resource base, innovation leadership, and global markets.

As of now, China holds dominant positions due to industrial development, centralized planning, vertical production integration, and control over critical materials. The USA retains leading positions in high-tech niches, innovations, software solutions, and intelligent management systems but faces challenges in scaling up due to import dependence and the domestic political situation.

The global rivalry between China and the USA in the sphere of green energy reflects a broader process of forming a new world order, where innovations, access to resources, technological sovereignty, and the ability to control energy chains become central elements. Despite differences in development models, both countries are inevitably interdependent participants in the global energy transformation. The speed and effectiveness of global decarbonization, as well as the stability of the future world economy, largely depend on the nature of their competitive interaction.

¹Shuai, Zhao, Wang, Cheng 2022

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基于交通通信和一体化平台创建的产业发展理论和方法论基础
**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS
OF INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT BASED ON THE CREATION
OF TRANSPORT COMMUNICATION AND INTEGRATION
PLATFORMS**

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摘要：本文探讨了基于交通通信与集成平台构建的产业发展的理论和方法论基础。文章对通信与集成平台进行了定义，概述了其发展的目标、宗旨、原则和方法，并指出了未来研究的重点方向。

关键词：方法论，发展，交通，通信与集成平台，产业。

Abstract. *This article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations of industrial development based on the creation of transport communications and integration platforms. It defines communications and integration platforms, outlines the goals, objectives, principles, and methodology for their development, and identifies priorities for further research.*

Keywords: *methodology, development, transport, communications and integration platforms, industry.*

At the beginning of the 21st century, digital technologies have become an integral part of the strategic initiatives of organizations across various industrial sectors. With the growth in data volume, increasing complexity of processes, and the need for prompt decision-making based on complex information flows, the necessity arises to integrate information systems within a unified architecture. However, the mere implementation of a digital solution does not guarantee its effectiveness — this is achieved through the necessary combination of a scientifically grounded methodology for integrating digital transformation processes, the creation of highly efficient transport systems, and conditions conducive to industrial development, which together form the basis for the development of regional transport communication and integration platforms [2].

Currently, there are several definitions in academic literature that allow transport communication and integration platforms to be considered from different perspectives. In particular, N. O. Saltrukovich defines an integration platform as an institutional and economic mechanism that ensures the coordination of production and transport processes. In our opinion, this approach is relevant; however, it predominantly emphasizes the organizational aspect of the studied process, overlooking the innovation and technological aspect of platform development, which is a key trend in contemporary industrial development [3].

In the work of Stępniaś C., Jelonek D., Wyrwicka M., Chomiak-Orsa I., transport communication and integration platforms are understood as multifunctional infrastructural nodes that integrate resources, information flows, and service functions. This definition emphasizes spatial integration and interregional connectivity, allowing platforms to be regarded as the basis for forming an economic continuum [6].

In the definition by Giuffrida M., Perotti S., Tumino A., Villosio V., the emphasis is on the investment component: if the transport system acquires the properties of an integration platform, its role in accelerating investment flows and forming new production linkages inevitably increases. This approach highlights the pattern of investment acceleration but requires supplementation by a socio-economic dimension.

The analysis and synthesis of these approaches allows us to speak of 'communication-integration platforms' as a new form of infrastructural development of the transport system, which can be defined as a multifunctional organizational-economic system ensuring sustainable interaction between industrial regional complexes and transport infrastructure based on an established system of investment centers, resource exchange, information sharing, and provision of service support. Their key feature is that they go beyond narrowly defined transport functions and form the economic basis of spatial integration, enabling the coordination of production, information, and distribution processes across regions and industries, ensuring sustainable intra- and interregional communication.

As noted by V. V. Tsyganov, the theoretical basis for platform formation is the theory of large transport systems, which establishes the conditions for its demand and effectiveness. For the platform to be genuinely functional and enable the solution of a complex range of industrial growth challenges, it is necessary, during its formation, to consider the characteristics and development trends of transport as a large-scale production-technical, informational, economic, and social system, which constitutes a significant element of the national economy [4].

In general, when discussing the methodological foundations of industrial development based on the creation of transport communication and integration platforms, such a methodology, in our view, should incorporate several key elements that ensure its scientific integrity and practical applicability. The purpose of developing the methodology is to create a scientifically grounded conceptual framework that

ensures the coordinated development of industry and transport infrastructure in the context of digital transformation.

This methodology should not only integrate information systems and transport processes but also establish institutional economic mechanisms capable of accelerating information and investment flows, ensuring the spatial connectivity of industrial complexes and regions, and promoting the innovative development of transport infrastructure. Among the elements forming the foundation of this methodology are the formulation of goals and objectives, the definition of principles, and the methods for developing communication and integration platforms.

Thus, the purpose of creating transport communication and integration platforms is to establish a multifunctional organizational and economic system that ensures sustainable interaction between industrial production and transport infrastructure based on digital integration, investment acceleration, and spatial connectivity of regions. Such a system should serve as the core of industrial development, capable of coordinating production, informational, and distribution processes, thereby creating conditions for the formation of a unified economic continuum and enhancing the competitiveness of the national economy.

The tasks facing the institutional system of regional governance in the formation of transport communication and integration platforms include:

- the development of principles for digital integration of transport and production processes within a unified information systems architecture;
- the development of a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of digital solutions, enabling their performance to be compared with the goals of industrial development and the sustainability of regional economies;
- the establishment of organizational and economic mechanisms for coordinating production, distribution, and transport flows to ensure sustainable interregional communication;
- the institutionalization of investment centers and service provision, serving as key nodes of spatial integration and accelerating investment processes;
- consideration of innovation-technological and socio-economic factors, determining the demand and functionality of the platform in the long term;
- building a system of strategic management of transport infrastructure, aimed at increasing the efficiency of industrial development and accelerating the processes of digital transformation.

Among the principles that define the methodological foundations for the formation of transport communication and integration platforms, the following can be distinguished:

- the principle of systemness, implying the consideration of the platform as a multi-level production-technical, informational, and socio-economic system; organization of an effective, integrated system for controlling the functioning of

information and material flows, the movement of which ensures the establishment of supply for certain types of products [1];

— the principle of integration — the unification of digital technologies, transport infrastructure, and institutional mechanisms into a single architecture that enables the transport enterprise's activities to be optimally adapted to the prevailing market environment, increase profit share, and obtain clear advantages over direct competitors [1];

— the principle of innovation — focusing on the implementation of intelligent solutions and adapting to the dynamics of industrial development; the principle of spatial connectivity — ensuring sustainable interregional communication and coordination of production processes;

— the principle of investment acceleration — creating conditions to expedite investment flows and establish new production linkages;

— the principle of sustainability — considering long-term socio-economic factors that guarantee the platform's functionality;

— the principle of strategic management — developing management mechanisms for transport infrastructure aimed at increasing the competitiveness of industry and aligning regional economic development strategies.

Regarding the methodology for creating transport communication and integration platforms, it should be founded on methods for the strategic justification of regional economic development (scenario analysis, strategic planning, institutional forecasting); Methods of economic-mathematical modeling (optimization models, simulation modeling, correlation-regression analysis) that enable the identification of patterns and forecasting the effectiveness of integration processes; Methods of financial and economic analysis (assessment of investment attractiveness, risk analysis, calculation of sustainability indicators); Methods of institutional and organizational design (cluster analysis, supply chain modeling, development of organizational structures) that provide opportunities for coordinating managerial decisions and establishing investment centers; Methods of managing large transport systems that create the prerequisites for comprehensive regulation of production-technical, informational, and distribution processes (systems analysis, theory of large transport systems).

This set of methodological approaches establishes conditions for the scientifically grounded design of communication-integration platforms that ensure sustainable industrial development, spatial connectivity of regions, and accelerate the transition of transport infrastructure to an innovation-investment development model.

Thus, the goals and objectives of the methodology establish a scientifically coherent foundation for designing transport communication integration platforms, while the outlined principles and proposed methodology form a conceptual practical framework that creates conditions for the alignment of strategic,

organizational-economic, and technological decisions. Given the relevance of the issues raised in this article, further research will focus on developing tools to evaluate the effectiveness of platform solutions, refining economic integration mechanisms, and formulating economic models for managing transport infrastructure in the current context of regional economic development.

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俄罗斯在全球农业碳信用体系中的地位
**RUSSIA'S POSITION IN THE GLOBAL SYSTEM OF
AGRICULTURAL CARBON CREDITS**

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摘要：本文分析了俄罗斯在全球农业碳信用市场中的地位。尽管该领域增长潜力巨大，但仍面临着项目可信度低和交易成本高昂等挑战。俄罗斯拥有大片具有高碳封存潜力的废弃土地，并已建立了国家碳信用市场。然而，目前该市场主要由技术项目主导，农业项目所占份额极小。要充分发挥这一潜力，需要解决方法论、经济和整合方面的障碍。

关键词：碳信用，农业碳封存，俄罗斯，自愿碳市场，废弃土地，气候项目。

Abstract. *This article analyzes Russia's position in the global agricultural carbon credit market. Despite high growth potential, the sector faces challenges related to project credibility and high transaction costs. Russia, possessing vast abandoned lands with high carbon sequestration potential, has established a national carbon unit market. However, it is currently dominated by technological projects, with agricultural initiatives constituting a minimal share. Realizing this potential requires addressing methodological, economic, and integration barriers.*

Keywords: *carbon credits, agricultural carbon sequestration, Russia, voluntary carbon market, abandoned lands, climate projects.*

The global carbon credit market, and specifically its agricultural component, represents a high-potential growth area. Presently, this sector forms a substantial segment of the voluntary carbon market, whose function is to direct capital towards projects aimed at greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction and enhanced sequestration [1].

The global agricultural carbon credit market exhibits robust growth dynamics, with a projected value of \$912.9 million and a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17.74% [2]. The sequestration potential varies significantly across practices, ranging from 0.56 Mg C/ha/year for cover cropping to a 19% average

increase in soil organic carbon stocks, reaching up to 17.2 Mg C/ha/year under optimal agroforestry conditions [3].

Agricultural carbon projects are represented by diverse categories, each with distinct characteristics and sequestration potential. Beyond soil carbon sequestration, key project types include agroforestry, biochar application, and integrated crop-livestock systems [4]. These practices target the reduction of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O emissions while enhancing carbon storage in both soil and biomass [5]. Consortia like the IFACC (Initiative for the Carbon Conservation of Land) are already sequestering substantial volumes of carbon (21 million tonnes of CO₂e) and have outlined plans to scale this impact multifold by 2025, all while maintaining agricultural productivity [6].

Despite optimistic forecasts, the carbon credit market is undergoing a period of significant reassessment. Criticism regarding the integrity of projects has led to a 61% decline in total market value [7]. This trend directly impacts the agricultural sector, where concerns over the reliability of accounting, permanence, and additionality of soil carbon sequestration are most acute. The opacity of verification processes and fears of “double counting”, where a single carbon removal unit is claimed by multiple sellers, are undermining buyer confidence and calling into question the economic viability of investments. In response to these challenges, key market standards such as Verra have begun publishing new methodologies for their most significant project types, including those targeting emission reductions in agriculture. This indicates the market’s attempts to self-regulate and raise the quality standards for projects.

The agricultural carbon sequestration market was estimated at USD 155 million in 2023 [8]. It is projected to grow at a CAGR of 17.74%, reaching a value of USD 912.9 million in the near future. This upward trajectory is further corroborated by regional data. For instance, the European regenerative agriculture market, a key component of this sector, was valued at USD 3657.85 million in 2024 and is forecast to reach USD 4720.91 million by 2033 [9]. These figures indicate growing interest from investors, corporations, and governments in leveraging agriculture as a tool to meet decarbonization targets.

A critical barrier to the widespread adoption of agricultural carbon practices is the high cost of transaction expenses. These costs encompass verification, certification, documentation, and marketing. For small and medium-sized farmers, who represent the majority of potential market participants, these expenditures can be prohibitively high relative to the potential benefits. A study conducted in Denmark demonstrated that transaction costs significantly impact the economic feasibility of supplying carbon credits from cover cropping [10]. This creates a risk that the benefits of participating in the carbon market will accrue predominantly to large-scale agricultural enterprises, while smallholder farmers remain excluded. Addressing this

issue requires mechanisms of public support, simplified registration procedures for small projects, and the development of aggregation models capable of distributing transaction costs across a greater number of participants.

Russia has taken steps to establish its own, albeit still isolated, voluntary carbon unit market, enabled by the adoption of Federal Law No. 34-FZ “On Conducting an Experiment to Limit Emissions of Certain Types of Greenhouse Gases in Certain Subjects of the Russian Federation” on March 6, 2022 [11]. The market was launched in September 2022, with Kontur JSC authorized as the operator of the national carbon unit registry. The establishment of this market is part of a broader state strategy aimed at enhancing the country’s carbon sink capacity: the goal is to increase greenhouse gas absorption to 1.2 billion tonnes of CO₂e by 2050 and achieve carbon neutrality by 2060 [12].

According to McKinsey analysis, afforestation of abandoned agricultural lands is projected to play a central role in enhancing Russia’s carbon sink capacity. Other research also supports that forest restoration on these territories could become a significant element of the country’s climate strategy, contributing not only to carbon sequestration but also to biodiversity conservation. The process of natural revegetation (spontaneous afforestation) of these lands already leads to substantial carbon uptake, and it can and should be leveraged as part of a climate change mitigation strategy [13]. Empirical data confirm the high sequestration potential of abandoned lands. A study conducted in the Tyumen region provides concrete quantitative estimates. The research established that the average soil carbon sequestration rate on abandoned fields in the upper layer (0-5 cm) is 0.66 Mg C/ha/year [14]. It is important to note that this process is not uniform over time. A clear decline in sequestration rate was observed as the overgrown territories age. For fields abandoned recently (1-10 years ago), sequestration rates were significantly higher, at 1.04 Mg C/ha/year. In contrast, for areas that have been undergoing natural revegetation for 11-20 years, this figure dropped to 0.26 Mg C/ha/year. This indicates the existence of a “peak” period of intensive sequestration, occurring shortly after agricultural activity ceases, when the soil, previously depleted by intensive farming, begins rapidly restoring its organic matter stocks. It was also noted that soil carbon stocks on abandoned fields, as well as on adjacent meadows and forests, are significantly higher than on the same soil types that remain under active agricultural use.

As of February 5, 2026, the national Registry had registered 68 climate projects. However, the share of agricultural projects remains minimal: the project classification lists only 2 projects under “Agriculture” out of 68. The total volume of carbon units planned for issuance stands at 91,277,127, with 34,307,743 units in circulation. The market is currently dominated by technological emission avoidance projects rather than those focused on carbon removal [15].

Russia possesses a unique resource in the form of vast areas of abandoned agricultural land, whose natural reforestation demonstrates high carbon sequestration rates. This potential is recognized by the state as pivotal for achieving climate goals. Its practical realization, however, requires overcoming a series of barriers. These include the development of scientifically robust and internationally accepted accounting methodologies, the reduction of high transaction costs for monitoring and verification, and, in the long term, the integration of the resulting carbon units into the global demand system.

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全球和俄罗斯钢铁行业危机分析
**ANALYSIS OF CRISIS IN THE GLOBAL AND RUSSIAN STEEL
INDUSTRY**

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摘要：钢铁冶金是俄罗斯经济最重要的部门之一，是国内许多其他工业部门发展的基础。本文探讨了俄罗斯钢铁冶金的现状和发展前景，以及该行业对国民经济的影响。文章分析了全球钢铁冶金的发展趋势，以及亚洲和中东地区冶金业对全球钢铁生产的影响。基于静态数据分析，文章得出结论：俄罗斯钢铁冶金存在危机现象。研究结果强调了该行业成功发展对国家经济的重要性。

关键词：钢铁冶金，炼钢，钢铁需求，产能过剩，发展战略

Abstract. *Ferrous metallurgy is one of the most important sectors of the Russian economy, serving as the foundation for the development of many other sectors of domestic industry. This article examines the state and development prospects of Russia's ferrous metallurgy, as well as the industry's impact on the national economy. The trends in the development of global ferrous metallurgy and the influence of metallurgy in the regions of Asia and the Middle East on global steel production are analyzed. Based on the analysis of static data, a conclusion is drawn regarding the presence of crisis phenomena in Russian ferrous metallurgy. The research results highlight the importance of the successful development of the industry for the country's economy.*

Keywords: *ferrous metallurgy, steel melting, steel demand, excess production capacities, development strategy*

Ferrous metallurgy is one of the strategically important sectors of the Russian economy. The industry serves as a foundation for the development of many other sectors — shipbuilding, aviation, transport and heavy engineering, the defense-industrial complex, rail transport, energy, construction, and others. The contribution of metallurgy to the Russian Federation's gross domestic product is up to 5%, to the added value of the manufacturing industry — 17.4%, and to exports — 10%. As a consumer of products and services from natural monopoly

entities, ferrous metallurgy uses 5.3% of electricity and 5.8% of natural gas from the total domestic consumption of the country, while its share in freight railway transportation is 15%¹.

At the same time, the role of metallurgy in the domestic economy can be assessed in two ways: on the one hand, ferrous metallurgy serves as an indicator of economic growth, since the utilization of metal production capacities depends on the demand from related industries — consumers of metallurgical products. According to experts, one job in metallurgy creates seven jobs in related sectors. On the other hand, the level of development of metallurgy (in particular, by such an indicator as steel melting per capita) can be used to assess the national economy's level of development and its capacity to meet the country's demand for major types of products. The average global level of steel melting per capita in 2024 amounted to 215 kg. For comparison, in the European Union countries, the value of this indicator was 291 kg; in Asian countries — 283 kg (including South Korea — 924 kg, China — 601 kg, Taiwan — 746 kg, Japan — 419 kg, India — 103 kg, other Asian countries — 80 kg); in CIS countries — 203 kg (including Russia — 304 kg); in North American countries — 221 kg (including USA — 261 kg); in Middle Eastern countries — 197 kg (including Qatar — 1,397 kg, UAE — 6,456 kg); in South American countries — 95 kg; in African countries — 25 kg.

Domestic ferrous metallurgy is integrated into the global economic system, since Russia is one of the significant players in the global metal products market. Therefore, in addition to the state of the Russian economy, the industry is significantly influenced by processes occurring in the global market overall and in global ferrous metallurgy specifically.

Over the past 45 years, substantial changes have occurred in global ferrous metallurgy. According to the World Steel Association (WSA), in the 1980s, 717 million tons were produced. tons of steel (for comparison, 28 million tons were produced in 1900). The leading steel-producing countries included the USSR (21% of global steel production), Japan (16%), USA (14%), Germany (6%), China (5%), Italy (4%), France and Poland (3%), Canada and Brazil (2%). In 2025, according to WSA data, global steel production reached 1,849 million tons. The composition of the leading countries changed drastically — China took first place by a wide margin (52% of global steel production), while the shares of other countries in the top ten ranged from 2% to 9% — India (9%), USA, Japan, and Russia (4%), South Korea (3%), Turkey, Germany, Brazil, and Iran (2%). Compared to 1980, the composition of countries in the list of the top 10 steel producers

¹ Development Strategy of the Metallurgical Industry of the Russian Federation for the Period until 2030. Approved by the Order of the Government of the Russian Federation dated December 28, 2022, No. 4260-r

has fundamentally changed — now, in addition to China, countries such as India, South Korea, Turkey, and Iran have firmly established their positions on this list.

It should be noted that in recent years, the growth rates of global steel production have slowed from 6.2% per year during the period 2000-2005 to 0.2 percent in 2020. At the same time, in 2021 a historic record in steel production was noted at 1,963 million tons. Over the past four years, the global volume of steel production has decreased on average by 1.5% annually.

The development of Chinese metallurgy has a significant impact on the balance of power in the global steel market. If, during the period from 1980 to 2025, global steel production increased 2.6 times, from 717 to 1,849 million tons (+1,132 million tons), then in China, during the same period, production volumes grew more than 26 times. In 1980, China produced 37 million tons of steel (5% of the world total), and in 2025-961 million tons (52% of the world total).

Figure 1.

Source: WSA, author's calculations

Thus, the increase in global steel production by 1,132 million tons, or 82%, is attributable to China's rise as the largest player in the global steel market (Fig. 1). Since the mid-1990s of the last century, China has become a global leader in pig iron and steel production.

For many years, domestic metal consumption in China has been the primary driver of growth in metallurgical production in the country. The highest annual production growth rates in the Chinese steel industry occurred between 2001 and 2007, averaging 21% per year. In 2008-2013, the average annual growth rate of steel production in China declined to 9%. Over the past five years, production volume in China decreased from 1,065 million tons in 2020 to 961 million tons in 2025. The cause of the decline in production in China is

a decrease in domestic demand. The additional domestic demand for steel was primarily driven by the Chinese government's unprecedented national economic stimulus program since 2009, funded by multibillion-dollar investments in the construction of cities, automobile and railway roads, and other infrastructure. In recent years, the authorities sharply reduced the pace of capital investments, leading to the first decline since the early 1980s. a reduction in domestic demand for metal products.

The decline in metal demand in China exerts unprecedented pressure on the global steel market. Considering that, according to CISA estimates, China's total production capacities exceed 1.2 billion. tons per year, the reduction in domestic market demand channels the excess metal supply to external markets. In 2024, according to WSA data, China exported approximately 12% of its production volume, which ultimately negatively affects metallurgists' finished product prices¹.

Excess production capacities in steelmaking constitute a significant negative factor in the global market. The consequence of surplus capacities is numerous trade conflicts and increased protectionist policies. Ferrous Metallurgy is strategically important for most metal-producing countries. In such situations, national governments support the development of their domestic industry, often through subsidies. Ultimately, this may lead to the artificial support of inefficient enterprises.

According to experts' estimates, the global surplus of steel production capacity may grow from 551 million tons per year in 2023 to 630 million tons in 2026. Meanwhile, the principal criticism is directed at Chinese producers, where metallurgist enterprises, especially state-owned ones, receive financial support from the government during unfavorable periods. Therefore, steel production in China remains excessive².

Thus, in the coming years, an intensification of China's export expansion is to be expected, placing most producers in the global steel market in a vulnerable position. Only specialized high-quality steel grades from other producing countries can effectively compete with inexpensive steel rolled products.

Overall, global steel production has been declining since 2021, reflecting decreased demand in the world market due to global instability and a slowdown in economic growth worldwide. Already, analysts note a decline in metal prices to a 3-4-year low. Among the top ten steel-producing countries, according to WSA data, production growth in 2025 is observed only in India (+10%), Turkey and the

¹ China Iron & Steel Association (CISA) — China Association of Pig Iron and Steel Producers

² Excess steel production capacities are the biggest obstacle to the global market-<https://www.metalinfo.ru/ru/news/164907>

USA (+3%), and Iran (+1%). The remaining countries showed a decline in production volumes compared to the previous year, ranging from 2% to 9%.

In Russia, the volume of smelting decreased by 4.5% as of 2024. Domestic metallurgists have found themselves in a difficult situation. Russia remains a major producer of ferrous metals, although in recent years it has faced challenges related to fluctuations in the external market, global competition, and sanction pressure due to geopolitical instability. In 2025, Russian metallurgists have not yet reached the pre-crisis production volumes of 2021. According to Rosstat, in 2025 steel production volumes amounted to 87% of the 2021 level, finished rolled products to 86%, and steel pipes to 99% (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of production of the main types of ferrous metallurgy products in Russia

million tons											
	1990	2007	2008	2009	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025*	2025 to 2021, %
Pig iron	59	51	48	44	52	54	52	54	51	50	94
Steel**	90	72	69	60	74	78	72	75	71	68	87
Finished rolled ferrous metals	64	60	57	52	62	66	61	65	60	57	86
Steel pipes	12	9	8	7	11	11	13	14	13	11	99
Metallurgical coke	39	34	32	27	27	28	25	26	24	23	81
Iron ore concentrate	91	99	93,6	86,3	100	101	95	91	90	92	91

* *preliminary data*

Source: Rosstat

An additional negative impact on the industry is caused by a decline in domestic demand due to the slowdown in the development of the national economy amid the high key rate of the Bank of Russia. By the decision of the Board of Directors of the Bank of Russia dated December 19, 2025, the key rate was reduced from 16.5% to 16%. However, according to analysts, the impact of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation's key rate reduction may positively affect the Russian economy only after several months. The time lag between the key rate reduction and the response of the real economic sector to this measure is approximately 3-4 months.

It should be noted that for metallurgists, the recent crisis is not a new phenomenon. Crisis phenomena in ferrous metallurgy occur cyclically every 4-6 years.

This does not impede the fundamental stability of the industry or the solution of its pressing tasks, such as modernization and digitalization of production, enhancement of product quality, and development of new technologies and markets. However, given the importance of the industry for the Russian economy as a whole and the scale of the challenges faced by domestic metallurgists, the state can exert a stimulating influence on the recovery of domestic demand for metal, since positive industry performance creates conditions for national economic growth.

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数字化转型和社会责任型企业项目的融资
**DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND FINANCING OF SOCIALLY
RESPONSIBLE BUSINESS PROGRAMS**

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摘要：环境和社会因素的融合是企业 and 个体企业实现可持续发展的基础。从实践角度来看，数字化转型激励企业通过在生产和社会领域开展创新，建立新的社会和环境项目。数字化转型增强了利益相关者对企业的积极认知。融资为企业实施社会和环境项目创造了新的机遇。

关键词：融资，企业，数字化转型，创新，社会和环境项目。

Abstract. *The integration of environmental and social components constitutes the foundation of sustainable development for corporations and individual enterprises. From a practical perspective, digital transformation motivates corporations to establish new social and environmental projects by launching innovations in both production and social domains. Digital transformation reinforces positive stakeholder perceptions of the company. Financing creates new opportunities for companies in implementing social and environmental programs.*

Keywords: *financing, corporation, enterprise, digital transformation, innovations, social and environmental programs.*

Digital transformation enhances company resilience under conditions of uncertainty and improves financial performance, thereby directly enabling companies to expand the scope and volume of financing for social and environmental programs. Large manufacturing companies achieve substantial economic efficiency through digital transformation and activate mechanisms for strengthening corporate social responsibility. Consequently, the confirmed experience of operating manufacturing companies demonstrates the objectively existing synergetic effect of digital transformation and the expansion of corporate social responsibility horizons.

Thus, the circle of stakeholders interested in companies' provision of non-financial information has expanded considerably. In particular, consumers and investors demonstrate interest in the environmental, social, and governance aspects

of corporate operations (ESG). For instance, stock exchanges have introduced mandatory ESG disclosure requirements for all registered companies.

According to research findings by Chinese economists, a 1% increase in the level of digital transformation expands the scope of corporate social responsibility by 0.124% [1]. Digital transformation implemented in existing corporations encompasses all operational domains. Financial decisions concerning the financing of social and environmental programs are not overlooked.

Experts observe that in both Russian and international practice, reporting and information regarding the implementation of sustainable development goals remains highly diverse and unstructured. Therefore, comprehensive systematization of data regarding the diversity and financing of socially responsible business programs is required [2].

In practice, information concerning the financing of environmental, social, and charitable programs at Russian manufacturing companies is incorporated within non-financial reporting. During the preparation of the master's thesis, the author examined theoretical aspects and practical materials pertaining to social reporting. It should be noted that social reporting has been the subject of academic research throughout the past decade.

In a number of scholarly publications, the social (non-financial) report is presented as an instrument for communicating information to society and stakeholders regarding social and environmental outcomes, accounting for indicators of the company's economic performance [3]. Recently, the social report has been regarded as a public document that consolidates information concerning the social dimensions of a company's operations and its commitments in the social and environmental spheres [4]. This represents a form of periodic summary demonstrating corporate social responsibility.

Within the framework of the research, a collection of social responsibility reports was examined employing specific selection criteria:

- longitudinal reconstruction of social responsibility reporting (2017-2024) — JSC «Federal Freight Company»;

- standardization of IT-organization reporting with emphasis on activity-specific characteristics — ICL Services, a Russian company providing international-level IT services;

- demonstration of international experience with identification of national social responsibility characteristics — JSC «Uzbektelecom» (Republic of Uzbekistan).

As the study results demonstrate, at the initial stage (2017), JSC «Federal Freight Company» incorporated the fundamental activity modules into its social responsibility report: responsible management; economic sustainability; social responsibility [5]. The aspects of social responsibility were distributed into submodules: personnel, social partnership, occupational health and safety and

environmental security, and interaction with society. Furthermore, a clear relationship was established between economic and financial performance indicators and the key areas of social responsibility.

By 2024, JSC «Federal Freight Company» had substantially expanded its social responsibility initiatives [6]. The sustainability report, encompassing human resource policy, social policy, occupational health and environmental protection, and participation in the life of regions of presence, was incorporated into the integrated report. The social motivation system was expanded to include the following areas: health support and enhancement of work capacity for employees and their family members; expansion of non-state pension provision; improvement of housing conditions, including mortgage subsidization for employees; provision of targeted support beyond legislative requirements in the form of benefits and guarantees.

Such a personalized approach and the strengthening of financial indicators have enabled JSC «Federal Freight Company» to annually increase the financing of social programs. Thus, in 2022, the company financed social programs totaling 221.1 million rubles; in 2024-259.9 million rubles. Accordingly, over the three-year period, the increase amounted to 17.5%.

An even greater increase of 20.1% was demonstrated by financing for voluntary medical insurance of employees and non-working pensioners. In 2022, financing amounted to 30.7 million rubles; in 2024-37.2 million rubles. Financing of social programs in the form of non-state pension provision in 2024 was implemented in the amount of 28.3 million rubles. Financing of charitable programs in 2024 amounted to 92.7 million rubles.

To establish a direct correlation between the volume of financing for social and charitable programs at JSC «Federal Freight Company» and the financial stability of the corporation. An analysis of financial indicators for the period 2022-2024 demonstrates revenue growth of 27.9%; profit growth of 29.8%. Accordingly, the strengthening of the corporation's financial foundation expands the scope for socially responsible business practices at JSC «Federal Freight Company».

A thorough examination of the corporate social responsibility report of ICL Services with the motto 'Business is always a responsibility to society' demonstrates comprehensive goals and objectives in the sphere of social responsibility [7]. However, these standards do not contain information regarding the financing of social programs. Consequently, this report is declarative in nature.

International experience in the formulation of social responsibility reports warrants examination. The 2024 report of JSC «Uzbektelecom» serves as an illustrative example. This represents a leading company in the telecommunications services market that provides digital services and develops an ecosystem of digital products for businesses and citizens of Uzbekistan. The components of the environmental and social programs system are conventionally identified. Notably,

projects pertaining to social support and enhancement of employee quality of life are accompanied by corresponding financing data.

In 2024, the financing of social programs by JSC «Uzbektelecom» totaled 141.5 billion sum [8]. Among the principal types of financing: allowances and supplements for climatic and hazardous working conditions; material assistance (retirement, marriage, disability); compensation for additional leave; payment for training; assistance to retirees; sanatorium and resort vouchers; financial resources for employee medical treatment.

The synthesis of the presented materials on social responsibility permits the identification of several aspects as positive practices recommended for implementation: an expanded range of social programs; reference to engagement with communities in regions of operational presence; information on financing volumes over time (3-year period); integration with the company's financial performance indicators.

The presentation of the spectrum of social programs enables other business entities to utilize this resource for making managerial decisions regarding the expansion of program portfolios. Program-specific financing breakdowns enable comparative analysis of the financial capacity of a particular company against the examined report. Revenue and profit, along with their respective growth rates, facilitate rational financial planning and inform financial decisions concerning increased funding allocations in subsequent calendar years.

Nevertheless, the examined social responsibility reports do not emphasize the necessity of applying digital technologies in financing social programs. From our perspective, digital transformation serves as a key driver for activating and expanding the scope of corporate social responsibility.

Within the context of digital transformation, corporations establish information software support systems that reflect the nature of social programs; managerial decision-making regarding corporate participation in program implementation; documentation support with designation of the responsible structural subdivision; calendar report on financing.

Currently, artificial intelligence (AI) is being implemented and applied on an expanded scale across all sectors of the Russian economy. According to expert calculations, by 2030 the projected economic effect from AI implementation will amount to 8 to 13 trillion rubles per year, which is comparable to approximately 6% of GDP [9].

Such scale is justified by the high rates of widespread AI implementation. Among technologies, generative AI exerts the greatest influence. It is well established that **generative artificial intelligence** (Generative Artificial Intelligence), unlike traditional AI, generates **novel original content** based on the analysis of large data volumes.

In the near term, generative AI is acquiring a horizontal platform form. This signifies not only formulating responses to inquiries, but also executing

predetermined actions. Moreover, as specialists demonstrate, generative AI contributes to enterprise cost reduction; supports the creation of new value through the optimization of business processes; facilitates the development of new product types; fundamentally transforms business models.

By the end of 2025, 71% of Russian companies are utilizing generative AI [10]. Moreover, more than 80% of implementing companies anticipate reductions in operational expenses and revenue growth, as well as profit increases. The aggregate economic effect of AI implementation in Russian companies' operations will be demonstrated across sectoral divisions (figure).

Figure — Aggregate Economic Effect Based on AI Implementation in Business Models of Russian Companies (%) [11]

The mining and metallurgical industry actively employs AI technologies. The overall sectoral share in GDP growth attributable to AI technology utilization is approximately 1% respectively: up to 0.9% for traditional AI technology applications; up to 0.8% for generative AI utilization. It is reasonable to assume that mining and metallurgical companies need to more actively develop and implement AI in their business processes.

In focusing on the development of practice-oriented innovation, an initiative is advanced concerning the creation of communication content between corporations/enterprises financing social and charitable programs and the recipients of

assistance. The construction of such content is feasible through analogous processing of client support inquiries based on the ‘question-answer’ pair model.

The operationalization of content is proposed utilizing Large Language Models (LLM) for extracting structured information throughout the implementation and completion phases of social or charitable project financing. It is widely recognized that LLM represents a subsequent stage developed on the basis of universal foundational AI models. Subsequently, graphical representations are formulated based on financing outcomes and the satisfaction of program participant needs.

Based on the obtained results, managerial and financial decisions are developed concerning the feasibility of corporate/enterprise participation in financing specific social or charitable programs; by financing volume; by distribution across the intra-year period; on reporting regarding designated use; on calculating the potential for increasing financing volume.

Overall, the digital transformation of Russian business through the application of AI technologies should extend to the financing of social and charitable programs. Thereby enhancing the contribution of Russian business toward advancing Russia’s national development goals.

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文明冲突还是全球化对抗：欧洲的宗教维度与伊斯兰教
**CLASH OF CIVILIZATIONS OR ANTAGONISM OF
GLOBALIZATIONS:
CONFESSIONAL DIMENSION AND ISLAM IN EUROPE**

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摘要：在当今世界，全球化与文明的互动尤为重要。本文认为，全球化不仅是文明影响的结果，文明本身也是全球化发展的产物。文明的发展并非必然伴随着负面进程；每一种文明都建立在文化、宗教、精神价值观和理想之上，蕴含着发展的潜力。本文分析了全球化在现代宗教信仰发展中的作用，并考察了欧洲穆斯林的现状。文章指出，欧洲穆斯林社群面临着不同的发展趋势，主流群体倾向于开放交流，而部分群体则容易走向极端化。

关键词：全球化；文化；价值观；文明互动；单极全球化；多极全球化；宗教信仰；伊斯兰教

Annotation: *In the modern world, interaction of globalizations and civilizations is especially relevant. The present article argues that not only globalization is the result of civilizational impacts but civilizations are the product of the development of globalization. Civilizations in general do not entail negative processes; every civilization is based on culture, religion, spiritual values and ideals bearing the potential for development. The article analyzes the role of globalization in the development of modern-day confessions, and considers the pattern of Muslims in Europe. It stipulates that the Muslim communities in Europe face different trends, with mainstream circles open to interaction while some groups are prone to radicalization.*

Key words: *globalization; globalization; culture; values; interaction of civilizations; unipolar globalization; multipolar globalization; confessions; Islam.*

The 21st century is gaining momentum. The world is changing rapidly and mercilessly. The relations among nations and people are growingly dominated by transnational networks and social institutions, movements and relations that infiltrate into virtually every sphere of human life. The circulation of goods and capitals, information and technologies, knowledge and weapons, financial and human resources, other material and immaterial objects has grown faster. Modern narratives offer to continents and nations material and human resources, new symbols and knowledge, products of social and spiritual creativity. Time and space rupture is taking place, and the connection between them is no more determined by a certain location. We witness changes in the sense of life and cultural landscape, models for behavior and consumption, new value guidelines, and growing uncertainty in the non-linear world caused by the increasing speed of social time [1, 2, 3].

In these circumstances, various sets of knowledge and beliefs, thoughts and feelings, hopes and inclinations provide societies with new ideas and concepts, determine complicated interaction with the world, culture, and life. New values and orientations, situational demands and intuitive visions, individual and collective experience are emerging; scenarios for future lifestyle, decisions and actions are being designed. The development in communications, information circulation and digitization are becoming a global phenomenon influencing politics and culture, economy and demography, religion and private lives of millions.

Politicians and journalists, public and religious figures, opinion leaders and managers, marketing and informatics professionals call the present epoch the globalization era, considering it through the prism of objective processes of technical and technological, social and informational, economic and political, cultural and religious, demographic and ecological, military and financial integration and unification, presupposing free circulation of goods and services, capitals and workforce, and open access to raw materials.

Globalization is an objective process entailing crucial changes and some positive consequences for Humankind. It stimulates elimination of multiple barriers on the road to future and thus to constantly growing interconnection of social subjects. Artificial intellect and transnational networks, social institutes, movements and relations interfere into virtually every human activity. In spite of geographic distances, all the subjects of global politics grow unprecedentedly closer. The Internet has opened access to nearly any information, determined its availability, and widened opportunities for creativity. Implementation of nanotechnologies, robotics and genetics, neural networks and AI have increased the value of intellectual resources in social life, and helped transforming humans into its crucial subjects capable to resist numerous

natural and artificial cataclysms successfully. A significant feature of globalization is the intervention of social connections into technical and technological, organizational and communicational, military and demographic, legal and financial spheres, as well as interconnections via widespread networks of social communication.

However, it is not as easy as it seems. On the one hand, globalization has brought significant positive results (increasing technological progress; strengthening of the global market; expansion of information space; discovery new perspectives of choosing life strategies and priorities for everyone). But on the other hand, the problems for Humankind entailed by globalization are equally obvious: erosion and devaluation of traditional values and the socialization mechanism for generations; interruption of their preeminence; loss of national and cultural identity; uncontrolled expansion of migration flows; effects of mass culture on people; deterioration of physical, mental, and social health caused by increasing social, class and economic inequality in the climate of social uncertainty.

As a result, alien elements constantly intervene into language and education, science and religion, family and collective memory without links to historic traditions and experiences of previous generations. We observe the struggle between not only intellects and knowledge, ideas and principles, technical possibilities and technological solutions but also, first of all, traditional values against disorder and chaos, entropy and semantics of the new worldview. The revision of basic values of worldview irreparably undermines social and moral health, preconditions the self-destruction of the society, widens the gap between generations, supports social anomy and increasing national and religious intolerance.

As social reality demonstrates, further progress in the cognition of modern and future societies requires the search for new structures capable to replace outgoing narratives. This function can be performed by civilizations as vital elements of the global composition — complicated, sophisticated, paradoxical, but at the same time sustainable social constructions able to become basic for modern ideology and geopolitics, drivers for social relations within a new world configuration. They can fill the analytic, ideological and constructive vacuum caused by the collapse of a number of social theories, thus becoming a coherent system of shaping, generating and transferring the senses of societal development [1, 2, 3].

Gradually, civilizations have begun to be seen as certain integrity, a set of material, spiritual, mental, moral, aesthetic and other values. Their principal characteristics are living space and time continuance, language and mentality, historic memories and durability in comparison with other societal and historic entities. Such an approach allows formulating the idea of the discreteness of history as well as of the possibility to classify civilizations into certain types.

However, in various regions, certain differences started appearing gradually in the structure of civilization clusters. Diversity of options, aspects and focuses of

research positions and interpretations has manifested itself in relation to existing structures. It has been happening in the conditions of uncertainty and risk, increasing responsibility for every decision which consequences could be rather complicated for every social system. In the process of civilizational development, Human Being has been also transforming, as well as their spiritual and moral imperatives, axiological orientations, alongside with changes in personal understanding and consideration of their place in civilization.

Thus, historic development within certain geographic area led to newer, more complicated types of civilizations, with new social, economic, political, cultural, psychological and technologic characteristics. These types were named local civilizations.

Local civilizations are sustainable systems of human unifications, societal areas limited by certain time and space, possessing definite parameters of cultural, economic, social, political, technologic, axiological, financial, informational, communicative, military, religious and ethic development. They are based on common values, ideals and mentality, technologies and information, uniting societal subjects together. Every local civilization possesses a certain structure, which was formed gradually and is based on its genetic roots and preeminence from previous systems.

Such civilizations are different in economy and culture (norms, customs, traditions, symbols), specific vision of the meaning of life, justice, destiny, the role of labor and leisure. They may differ in values, mentality, life principles, cuisine, types of houses, clothes etc., and develop constantly. American scholar Samuel Huntington argues that civilizations have century-long historic, traditional, religious and linguistic differences. They possess long histories and are able to strengthen with time and engage in the clash of civilizations. Among those exposed to clashes, the researcher specified the Western, Slavic Orthodox, Sinic, Islamic, Hindu-Buddhist, Japonic, Latin American and Sub-Saharan African civilizations. The harshest and most slaughterous conflicts are to occur along the borderlines separating them. According to the author, the wars of the recent centuries have been caused exactly by this reason [5].

However, it is not completely so. History proves that Muslims fight each other much more fiercely than against non-Muslim nations. The differences within the Islamic world are so profound and the conflicts so bitter and unsolvable that it can hardly be spoken about existing and sustainable religion-based solidarity. Muslim nations have been engaged in endless wars lasting for years: for example, between Pakistan and Bangladesh, South and North Yemen, Libya and Chad, Iran and Iraq. These bloody conflicts have been the background for intractable disputes between Muslim and non-Muslim states, as in the case of India and Pakistan, or Arab countries and Israel. At present, every Muslim state zealously defends its national interests seen by them as more vital than common loyalty to Islam.

S. Huntington concludes that the clash of civilizations in the modern era could become the dominating factor of global politics. The fault lines between civilizations are the lines of future wars [5]. Especially fearsome is his main conclusion that «...the clash of civilizations is the major threat to the global piece» [5, c. 8].

This concept seems a major mistake of the prominent academic: civilizations will never be at war against each other [6]. Recently, there have been a lot of wars, but whatever severe they have been, they have not involved clashes of cultures and civilizations. Numerous wars of recent centuries have occurred in the framework of one civilization. Moreover, they have not been clashes of cultures, religions, or sciences, while globalization has had almost no impact on their beginning, course and outcome.

Actually, there are states and public movements, political parties and opinion leaders that consider globalization as the cause of their grievances, and see their aim in eliminating globalization as a theory and phenomenon, lifestyle and ideology. Moreover, in the course of globalization, which is an extremely controversial process, completely new political and cultural configurations and paradigms emerge.

One of the major anti-globalist forces is religion, which strongly resists globalization and especially globalism, as its ideological basis. Confessions act as the sole real alternative to globalism, both at conceptual and practical level. That is why no segment of the modern world experiences such a powerful pressure as religion.

The principal enemy of 'global globalization' as Western-style globalization, is Islam which could be considered as a supra-national socio-cultural and politically-religious phenomenon. It unifies people recognizing their affiliation with a single historic and spiritual community, even with all differences in culture, mentality, national and religious traditions. Ummah is not simply a local Muslim community but a global communion of hundreds of millions of people whose way of life is imbued with Islam, its values, norms and provisions. Islam is oriented at the world as a given reality and represents a unique societal philosophy of everyday life.

As any other religion, Islam by itself cannot pose a threat to Humankind. The moral norms that Muslims are to follow are rather numerous. They include, for instance, truthfulness, sincerity, honesty, modesty, aversion to malice and hatred, inclination to devote all someone's time and life to kind deeds. Followers of Islam are to abstain from any actions corrupting and destroying their personality, avoid anything harmful to soul and body: prohibited food, alcohol, tobacco, narcotics, gambling. The Quran, the holy book of Islam, calls on to realize that all human achievements depend on Allah's mercy and benevolence [7].

Islam painfully reacts to attempts of imposing an alien ideology, and resists the Western liberal model of globalization. Moreover, most Muslims negatively perceive globalization, because it entails its own complex of societal philosophy, a massive flow of ideas controversial from the Islamic point of view and claiming to transform the mass consciousness.

In this context, one of the most relevant topics is the role of the Muslim community in Europe looking for its new identity in the landscape of dramatic social, economic, political and civilizational changes. Its consideration is important for understanding a number of paradigms: from the failures of multiculturalism and the deep split in the European societies nowadays to forecasting possible scenarios for the Western civilization.

Surveys reveal the rise of fundamentalism in the European Muslim communities [8, p.36]. Anyway, at the same time there is a tendency of distancing from religion among a certain part of the European Muslims and adoption of Western values by them. In most EU countries, Muslim communities demonstrate similar trends, including radicalization of their segment; increasing contradictions in their relations with the titular population; a crisis of multiculturalism (alongside with some success). Muslim immigrants in the EU face the necessity to adopt their identities to an alien civilizational context. That is why Islam is so important for a growing number of European Muslims: it is the axis of their identity.

A crucial aspect of this problematic is the link between these tendencies and the growing threat from international terrorism. The mainstream circles of the Muslim communities in Europe firmly reject extremism and terrorism, and their position is very important for the struggle against them. Meanwhile, certain circles within the European Muslim communities are prone to radicalization. It is enough to remember the cases of young European Muslims joining various Jihadist paramilitary structures acting in Syria, Iraq and some other countries of that region. Some of them afterwards returned to Europe, which is definitely a factor of tension and a threat to national security [9].

Islam is a doctrine defending the Muslim community from alien ideas and views, so in a hypothetic conditions of the multipolar world, it purposefully resists the Western way of globalization and is capable to establish its own Islamic model of globalization. The objective of such a model is to confront the collective West, to reshape the ideological basis of the Islamic world, to offer original roads of Islamic modernization and renewal, and to create anti-Western globalization. Similar globalization models are being designed by Russia, China, India and some other powers, which correlates with the theory of states-civilizations. It is especially worth underlining that these states-civilizations, with great prospects for the future, constitute a social space for interaction between personalities and organizations, roles and processes, connections and meanings reflecting political and economic, social and ideological, demographic and other norms and principles, historic traditions, value-based orientations, developed horizontal and vertical links determining the establishment of necessary and satisfactory conditions for guaranteeing national security and sovereignty, the correspondence of the living standards of individuals, social groups and societies to their objective and subjective needs.

Nowadays, an armed clash of civilizations is unreal. However, it seems quite possible between states, even parts of one civilization. Emergence of specific political, ethnic, religious and intercultural conflicts multiplying in recent years hardly corresponds to the theory of the clash of civilizations. Moreover, it does not correspond this theory. It is not reasonable to limit all these conflicts to it. A lot, if not everything, depends on leaders of nations and political movements, even on hypothetical «global government». The U. S. President's desire to incorporate Canada and Greenland, Venezuela and Panama into the United States can hardly be seen as the clash of civilizations. Such examples are numerous.

Conclusion

Being an objective process, globalization encourages and generates a broad range of trends worldwide, including rather constructive and perspective ones. These transformations are of special interest, as they not only change the picture of the world very profoundly but also influence the emerging international order.

In our view, wars between civilizations are impossible. Regardless what is in the heart of a certain civilization — religion or science, show or moral, — all civilizations are based on human cultural and spiritual values. All moral systems promote humanism, kindness, love and piece; all of them correspond to the interests of various nations. Basic elements of any civilization possess a potential uniting people regardless of their nationality, and thus support the interaction between civilizations and cultures.

The processes of globalization are the object of constant intervention from some states and political forces interested in achieving their economic, military and geopolitical targets. When these actors dictate their conditions to other countries and nations, they impose globalization an artificial character. An eloquent proof to this thesis is the events occurring nowadays in a number of regions of the world and bringing painful ordeal to many nations.

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堪察加议会在公共权力体系内监督和控制国家项目实施方面的作用

**THE ROLE OF THE KAMCHATKA PARLIAMENT
IN MONITORING AND CONTROLLING THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF NATIONAL PROJECTS WITHIN THE PUBLIC
AUTHORITY SYSTEM**

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摘要：本文介绍了堪察加边疆区立法议会在公共权力体系内，借助民间社会机构的参与，对该地区国家项目实施情况进行监督和控制的机制。文章列出了2019年至2024年堪察加边疆区区域项目实施的资金规模，并提出了加强该地区国家项目实施的途径。

关键词：公共权力体系，国家和区域项目，议会监督和控制，民间社会机构，公共和教育组织，资金规模，生活质量改善，居民福利。

Abstract. *This article presents the mechanism for monitoring and controlling the implementation of national projects in the region by the Legislative Assembly of Kamchatka Krai within the system of public authority, with the involvement of civil society institutions. The volume of funds utilized in the implementation of regional projects in Kamchatka Krai from 2019 to 2024 is presented. Approaches to enhancing the implementation of national projects in the region are proposed.*

Keywords: *public authority system, national and regional projects, parliamentary monitoring and control, civil society institutions, public and educational organizations, volume of funds, quality of life improvement, residents' welfare.*

In the current geopolitical and geoeconomic context, a new level of interaction between federal state authorities and the subjects of the Russian Federation is required, with particularly close integration of the public authority system in the regions.

In accordance with Part 3 of Article 132 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation, local self-government bodies and state authorities form a unified system of public authority in the Russian Federation and interact to most effectively address tasks in the interests of the population residing in the respective territory [1].

Federal Law No. 414-FZ of December 21, 2021, “On the General Principles of the Organization of Public Authority in the Subjects of the Russian Federation” (hereinafter the Federal Law) was enacted to further develop the new provisions of the Constitution of the Russian Federation concerning the unified system of public authority and is aimed at enhancing the organization of public authority in the Russian regions [2].

The principle of unity of the public authority system entails the ‘coordinated action of various levels of public authority as a single entity for the benefit of citizens’ (Conclusion of the Constitutional Court of the Russian Federation dated 16.03.2020 No. 1-Z) [3].

Therefore, for these purposes, the Federal Law specifically provides the following:

— in accordance with the constitutional foundations of the unity of public authority, an updated model for the organization and functioning of public authority bodies in the territories of the subjects of the Russian Federation is being established;

— public authorities may appeal to the State Council to ensure the conciliation procedures established by the Constitution of the Russian Federation and to resolve disagreements between federal state authorities and the state authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation;

— in order to enhance the guarantees for the activities of deputies of the legislative body of a subject of the Russian Federation, it is stipulated that all regional deputies hold state positions of that subject, regardless of whether they work on a permanent basis or without interrupting their primary occupation;

— By analogy with deputies of the State Duma and municipal deputies, the Federal law establishes a mechanism of responsibility for engaging in activities incompatible with the status of a deputy, in the form of a warning or dismissal from the position held in the legislative body.

— In order to unify the legislative procedure, a procedure is established for the legislative bodies of the subjects of the Russian Federation to submit draft laws to the State Duma [2].

One of the developers of the Federal Law, State Duma deputy P. V. Krashennikov, notes: ‘The main goal of the new law on public authority is to establish feedback between the federal government, regions, and municipalities.’ The unity of the public authority system implies the coordinated actions of various levels of power as a single entity for citizens, society, and the state. The constitutional enshrinement of this principle is an important step toward

improving governance in the state. The provisions of the law are aimed at creating conditions for comprehensive and sustainable socio-economic development of the country and each of its subjects separately, in the interests of citizens, society, and the state” [4].

The integrative model of governmental bodies enables closer cooperation in the implementation of national projects within the region.

On May 7, 2018, the President of Russia, Vladimir Putin, signed Decree No. 204 “On National Goals and Strategic Objectives for the Development of the Russian Federation through 2024.” In accordance with the national goals, this Decree defined twelve national projects [5]. Their implementation is primarily aimed at improving the quality of life of every citizen in each constituent entity of Russia.

In his Address to the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation on February 20, 2019, President of Russia V. V. Putin stated: “At the same time, I want to emphasize and reiterate: our development projects are neither federal nor, even more so, departmental. They are precisely national. Their results must be visible in every constituent entity of the Federation, in every municipality. Here, «on the ground», the main bulk of specific tasks is being implemented» [6].

It was planned to allocate more than 108 billion rubles from budgets at all levels for the implementation of regional projects in Kamchatka Krai during 2019–2024. Three main directions were chosen: Human capital — 86,158.83 million rubles (79.8% of the total funding volume for regional projects); Comfortable living environment — 13,725.11 million rubles (12.7%); Economic growth — 8,119.59 million rubles (7.5%) [7].

Figure 1. The volume of funds utilized for the implementation of national projects in Kamchatka Krai in 2019–2024 (billion rubles)

During this period, 13 national projects were implemented in Kamchatka Krai. State authorities and local self-government bodies of Kamchatka Krai implemented the regional component of 45 federal projects. The actual volume of financial provision for the activities of regional projects planned for 2019-2024 is presented in Figure 1.

Thus, the actual volume of financial support for regional project activities, planned for 2019-2024, amounted to 52.3 billion rubles, within which funding was executed from the following sources:

- federal budget — 30.1 billion rubles;
- regional budget — 17.5 billion rubles;
- extrabudgetary funds (Territorial Development Fund) — 4.7 billion rubles.

The allocation of such substantial funds for the implementation of regional projects necessitated strengthening parliamentary oversight over their expenditure and the quality of the work performed. It should be noted that the significance of parliamentary oversight is derived from an important document of the Inter-Parliamentary Union — the Resolution adopted at the 137th Assembly of the Inter-Parliamentary Union.

In paragraph 5. The Resolution contains a strong call for ‘parliaments to strengthen their capacity to exercise oversight over the executive branch, management, and expenditure of budgetary funds within the framework of a system of checks and balances’ [8].

Decisions on parliamentary oversight were adopted by the Federation Council and the State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation.

Therefore, pursuant to the decision of the Presidium of the Legislative Assembly dated 05.02.2019 No. 6918, a working group on parliamentary oversight of the implementation of the regional components of national projects (hereinafter, the Working Group) was established, which organized work along four main directions:

- direct parliamentary oversight of the implementation of regional projects within the committees’ areas of competence;
- continuous cooperation between committees and the executive authorities of Kamchatka Krai in the implementation of regional projects;
- cooperation with civil society institutions in monitoring and controlling the implementation of regional projects;
- educational and informational activities.

Targeted work is carried out in each of these areas, and a system of interaction between members of the Working Group and the Department for National Projects and Strategic Activities of the Administration of the Governor of Kamchatka Krai (hereinafter referred to as the Department for National Projects) has been established. Communication between the deputy corps and the administrators and implementers of regional projects has been established.

The permanent Committees of the Legislative Assembly of Kamchatka Krai have been entrusted with responsibility for monitoring the implementation of the regional components of national projects within their respective areas of competence.

A system of continuous interaction has been established between the Legislative Assembly, the Kamchatka Krai project office, executive bodies of state authority in Kamchatka Krai, educational (scientific) institutions, and public associations for the implementation of regional projects and the provision of their informational support.

The algorithm of parliamentary oversight over the implementation of national projects in Kamchatka Krai includes: analysis of the fulfillment of planned indicators; briefing deputies at meetings of standing committees with information from curators, heads, and administrators of regional projects on the progress of project implementation, including the volume of financial support allocated for their realization; holding “parliamentary hours”; conducting webcast meetings with local self-government bodies; and organizing field activities together with deputies of representative bodies of municipal formations, including inspections of construction sites within the framework of national projects.

Thus, in 2020 alone, deputies at all levels participated in monitoring the implementation of regional projects. This involved more than 60 deputies from representative bodies of local self-government across all municipal districts of Kamchatka Krai, 20 deputies of the Legislative Assembly of Kamchatka Krai, and deputies of the State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation. Monitoring and control were conducted over the construction of 25 facilities and the execution of more than 35 activities within the framework of national projects in Kamchatka Krai.

The significance of Kamchatka parliamentarians’ participation in facilitating civil society oversight, as stated in Resolution 137 of the Inter-Parliamentary Union Assembly, corresponds to their practical activities; paragraph 6 calls on parliaments to ‘strengthen the participation of citizens and the public in the democratic process and encourages efforts by parliaments to continue modernizing working methods to facilitate the involvement of civil society and citizens in their deliberations’ [8].

At the meeting of the Council for Strategic Development and National Projects on October 24, 2018, President of Russia V. V. Putin stated: “I repeat, it is extremely important to establish an effective feedback mechanism, to align our actions with the interests of the people, and to do everything to ensure that they are direct participants in our development projects. It is necessary to more broadly utilize the accumulated experience of civil control...» [9].

Therefore, based on the recommendations of the deputies of the Legislative Assembly, a new format of interaction between public authorities and civil society institutions has been in effect since 2022. Deputies at various levels, together

with executive authorities and local self-government bodies, the Department for National Projects, representatives of the Kamchatka Krai Prosecutor's Office, customers and contractors, as well as people's auditors from the Public Chamber of Kamchatka Krai and representatives of the All-Russian People's Front, visit construction sites directly and oversee the implementation of activities. Proposals from citizens are collected, identified deficiencies are promptly eliminated, or necessary adjustments are made to project implementation.

For example, in 2022 alone, during site visits to the construction of the sports and health complex "Vodnik" (hereinafter referred to as SHC), being built within the framework of the regional project "Sport is the Norm of Life," and the new building of secondary school No. 33, constructed within the framework of the regional project "Modern School" in Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky, it was found that the design and estimate documentation did not include landscaping of the adjacent territory and access roads. Thanks to the efforts of the deputies, the landscaping works at the FOC territory were completed, as well as all landscaping of the secondary school grounds and road repairs leading to it; additionally, the sports ground was equipped. There are other positive examples as well [10].

Following the analysis of the work of such off-site monitoring meetings, the deputies of the Legislative Assembly prepared the following proposals:

— The regional government should prepare an appeal to the Government of the Russian Federation regarding the amendment of the rules for substituting one facility under construction within a national project with another similar facility under construction within investment activities in the subject, transferring the relevant authority from the federal level to the level of the Far Eastern Federal District or the corresponding constituent entity of Russia;

— The Governor of the Krai to appeal to the Council for Strategic Development and National Projects under the President of the Russian Federation with a proposal to explore the possibility of incorporating already under-construction social infrastructure facilities into the regional components of national projects and allocating funds for these purposes from the federal budget.

These proposals were supported by the Government of the Krai and are currently under consideration at the federal level.

In 2024, the first stage of the implementation of national projects was completed: 18 deputies of the Legislative Assembly and more than 80 deputies of the representative bodies of local self-government from all districts, municipalities, and urban okrugs continued to monitor and control the construction of 59 facilities and the execution of 135 activities within the framework of the implementation of national projects in Kamchatka Krai.

This approach aligns with the statements made by the President of the Russian Federation, V. V. Putin, in his Address to the Federal Assembly of the Russian

Federation on February 29, 2024, stating that ‘over the past few years, we have succeeded in building a management system, as well as implementing national projects on new principles, based on large data sets and modern digital technologies for risk control, comprehensive information accounting, continuous refinement of projects and programs, relying on feedback from citizens.’ Indeed, the main focus is the “assessment by people,” that is, how “their lives improve” [11].

On May 7, 2024, President of Russia V. V. Putin signed Decree No. 309 “On the National Development Goals of the Russian Federation for the Period until 2030 and Looking Ahead to 2036,” which defined the necessity of developing national projects related to the economy, social sphere, and technological leadership [12]. This means that the implementation of national projects will continue in the long term in all constituent entities of the Russian Federation.

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the activities of the Legislative Assembly of Kamchatka Krai concerning parliamentary monitoring and control over the implementation of national projects in the region are conducted through continuous cooperation and interaction with the Government, other state authorities of Kamchatka Krai, local self-government bodies of the municipalities in the region, public organizations, and civil society institutions [13].

Such a comprehensive and thorough consideration of national projects by the deputies, involving all stakeholders, enables the exercise of governmental powers to be as effective as possible and ensures the high-quality resolution of the tasks set by the President of Russia, V. V. Putin, regarding the socio-economic development of the region and the improvement of the life and welfare of its residents.

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善意原则作为打击侵犯人权行为的基础：对上海合作组织成员国法律体系的整合潜力

**THE PRINCIPLE OF GOOD FAITH AS A BASIS FOR COUNTERING
ABUSE OF RIGHTS: INTEGRATION POTENTIAL
FOR THE LEGAL SYSTEMS OF SCO COUNTRIES**

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摘要：本研究致力于对诚信原则进行理论和法律分析，将其作为打击滥用权利的关键工具，并评估其融入上海合作组织成员国法律体系的潜力。研究表明，诚信原则可作为区分合法行使主体权利与形式上合法但对社会有害、破坏跨境交易信任的行为的普遍标准。以俄罗斯、中国和哈萨克斯坦的规范模式为例，论证了在不统一国家法典的情况下，制定打击滥用权利的最低共同标准的可能性。研究还提出了立法协调方向，包括统一一恶意行为的定义和指标、建立可比的后果（包括拒绝法律保护 and 补偿措施），以及在上海合作组织法律平台内发展专家和学术交流。

关键词：诚信、滥用权利、拒绝法律保护、跨境流动、法律一体化、上海合作组织、立法协调。

Abstract. *This study is devoted to the theoretical and legal analysis of the principle of good faith as a key instrument to counteract abuse of rights, including an assessment of its integration potential for the legal systems of SCO member states. As a result of the study, the author substantiates that good faith serves as a universal criterion for distinguishing the lawful exercise of subjective rights from formally legal, yet socially harmful conduct that undermines trust in cross-border transactions. Using the normative models of Russia, China, and Kazakhstan as examples, the possibility of forming a minimal common standard for counteracting abuse of rights without unifying national codes is demonstrated. Directions for the harmonization of legislation are proposed, including the alignment of definitions and indicators of bad faith, the establishment of comparable consequences (including denial of legal protection and compensatory measures), and the development of expert and scientific interaction within the legal platforms of the SCO.*

Keywords: *good faith, abuse of rights, denial of legal protection, cross-border turnover, legal integration, SCO, harmonization of legislation.*

Introduction

The expansion of economic cooperation and growth of mutual investments in the Eurasian space increase the significance of the prohibition of abuse of rights as a guarantee of good faith turnover and predictability in law enforcement. For the SCO member states, comprising ten countries [1], this issue becomes particularly relevant, not least because cross-border transactions and disputes inevitably confront differences among national legal systems, as well as risks of using legal means contrary to their intended purpose.

Abuse of rights is particularly dangerous because it creates the effect of ‘legality without justice,’ where the subject, outwardly complying with formal requirements, pursues an antisocial goal (to cause harm, circumvent mandatory restrictions, or create an imbalance of interests) or attains such a result. For this reason, countering abuse of rights is not merely the concern of specific legal branches but a systemic prerequisite for trust in justice and rights protection mechanisms, especially in cross-border private law relations.

Simultaneously, within the framework of the SCO, formats of legal and expert interaction are being consistently developed, including cooperation through ministries of justice and the organization of joint events. All this collectively allows the principle of good faith to be regarded as a potential ‘common denominator’ for the convergence of approaches to unfair conduct without rigid unification of national codes.

The aim of the study is to substantiate a theoretical and legal model of the correlation between good faith and abuse of rights, as well as to define the direction for harmonizing minimum standards to counteract abuse of rights within the legal systems of SCO states. The scientific novelty consists in proposing a framework integration model focused on the functional comparability of legal consequences and indicators of bad faith.

Good Faith and Abuse of Rights: A Theoretical and Legal Model

In classical legal theory, good faith is regarded as an interdisciplinary normative standard of conduct that ensures the harmonization of private interests with the social purpose of law. Meanwhile, some scholars differentiate the principle of good faith into subjective and objective components [2].

In our view, it performs a dual function. Firstly, it establishes a positive model of appropriate conduct for participants in transactions; secondly, it serves as a criterion for assessing the limits of exercising subjective rights. In Russian law, the requirement of good faith is enshrined in the general provisions of civil legislation, in particular in Article 1 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, and is expressed as an obligation to act in good faith when establishing, exercising, and protecting rights [3].

Abuse of rights, in turn, represents the limit of exercising good faith, beyond which the actions of a market participant are assessed as acting in bad faith. Its qualifying features include a formal reliance on a subjective right (or procedural possibility) and simultaneously contradicting the goals of law and the principle of good faith, manifested by the intent to cause harm, circumvention of the law with an unlawful purpose, or other forms of bad faith. This construction is reflected, in particular, in Article 10 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation [3].

As rightly noted by Odegnal E. A.: “The principle of good faith in Article 1 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation denotes the proper exercise and protection of civil rights and the fulfillment of civil duties as good faith behavior, whereas Article 10 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation considers the improper exercise of subjective civil rights as bad faith behavior, exceeding the established limits of normal rights use and exercise” [4].

The key theoretical implication is that a subjective right is not an absolute freedom but a legally defined competence limited by purpose and good faith. Therefore, the sanction for abuse of rights is logically expressed primarily in the denial of protection of the right (in whole or in part), as well as in the imposition of adverse consequences on the violator, including the obligation to compensate for the damages caused, as legislatively established in paragraph 4 of Article 10 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation [3].

At the international level, a comparable approach is demonstrated by the UNIDROIT Principles of International Commercial Contracts, which establish the obligation to act in good faith and honesty in international trade and prohibit excluding or limiting this obligation by agreement of the parties [5]. This confirms that good faith is capable of performing an integrative function in cross-border transactions as a supranational standard of conduct, compatible with various legal traditions.

Comparative Overview of Regulatory Approaches in the Legal Systems of SCO States

The Russian model features a high degree of normative specificity in prohibiting abuse of rights, clearly outlining key forms (intent to cause harm, evasion of the law for unlawful purposes, and other manifestly bad faith exercise of a right), as well as prescribing consequences, including denial of legal protection and other measures of response. Moreover, judicial interpretation holds significant importance, as Resolution No. 25 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation, dated 23 June 2015, directs courts to apply general provisions on good faith and the inadmissibility of gaining advantage through bad faith conduct when evaluating contentious situations [6].

The Chinese model establishes the principle of good faith as the foundation of civil activity, requiring honesty and fulfillment of obligations; this is explicitly provided for

in Article 7 of the Civil Code of the People's Republic of China [7]. At the same time, the Civil Code of the People's Republic of China explicitly prohibits abuse of civil rights that causes harm to national interests, public interests, or the lawful rights and interests of others, as provided in Article 132 [7]. This thereby confirms the universal principle that 'formal realization of rights is an inadmissible social effect,' upon which the doctrine of abuse of rights in various legal systems is based.

The Kazakhstani model is characterized by the imperative requirement to exercise rights in good faith, reasonably, and fairly, as well as by the presumption of good faith in the actions of participants in civil legal relations, enshrined in paragraph 4 of Article 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan [8]. The significance of the presumption lies in enhancing the effectiveness of protection against bad faith conduct; thus, when there are sufficient indications of abuse, the burden of disproving the relevant claims practically shifts to the party whose behavior raises doubts about good faith.

It seems that the overall conclusion of the comparative analysis is that despite differences in normative formulations and legal-technical devices, the fundamental idea of prohibiting abuse of rights and the role of good faith as a criterion delimiting the boundaries of rights exercise are functionally comparable. This creates the prerequisites for developing a minimum common standard to counter abuse of rights within the SCO space.

Integration potential and directions for harmonizing minimum standards

Complete unification of civil legislation within the SCO framework appears unrealistic, given the diversity of legal families and institutional traditions. At the same time, an effective alternative may be harmonization at the level of principles and practice-oriented recommendations (the 'soft law' model), based on good faith as a common value-normative category.

It is proposed to consider the minimum common standard for countering abuse of rights as a combination of three interrelated components.

Firstly, the definitional component should be noted, consisting of the consolidation (in model recommendations) of the understanding of abuse of rights as the exercise of a subjective right in contradiction with good faith and the purpose of the right, including the intent to cause harm, as well as evasion of the law with an unlawful objective. This formula appears to correspond to the key provisions of national codes and can be used as a basis for comparability in resolving cross-border disputes.

Secondly, let us consider the evidentiary framework. It consists of aligning indicators of bad faith as an open list of signs that enhance the predictability of law enforcement. In our opinion, it is advisable to include the following indicators:

- contradictory behavior (deliberate creation of false expectations for the counterparty);
- disproportionality between the chosen legal remedy and the declared aim;

- use of the right as a tool of pressure;
- artificial creation of obstacles to performance;
- systematic refusal to cooperate despite obligations to assist.

We consider these indicators universal, enabling adaptive responses to new forms of abuse in digital and cross-border contexts.

Thirdly, the sanction block — that is, functionally comparable legal consequences of abuse of rights — includes the following legal effects:

- denial of legal protection (full or partial);
- restorative measures and compensatory effects (including compensation for damages);
- the deprivation of a person's ability to invoke the formal legality of their own conduct to gain an advantage.

In cross-border relations, the order of applying such consequences is particularly significant, as it influences the parties' trust in judicial protection, including the enforcement of rulings.

The practical implementation of harmonization is achievable through joint scientific projects, exchanges of judicial and arbitration practices, the preparation of bilingual glossaries of key categories (good faith, abuse of rights, evasion of the law), as well as the development of expert recommendations within existing platforms of legal cooperation of the SCO. This format ensures synergy among research approaches and supports integration without replacing national legal identity.

Conclusion

The principle of good faith is a conceptually and normatively significant instrument for countering abuse of rights. It establishes a connection between the formal legal admissibility of behavior and its social purpose, and also enables the qualification of situations where a right is exercised contrary to its purpose, including in cross-border transactions.

A comparative analysis of the regulatory models of Russia, China, and Kazakhstan confirms the functional comparability of key elements: recognition of good faith as a general standard of conduct, establishment of a prohibition on abuse of rights, and the possibility of refusing the protection of a right as a fundamental sanction.

For the legal systems of the SCO member states, the integrative potential of good faith is manifested in the possibility of developing a minimal common standard for countering abuse of rights based on harmonizing definitions, indicators of bad faith, and comparable legal consequences, as well as through the development of scientific and expert cooperation. It appears that implementing the specified directions will contribute to enhancing the predictability of cross-border turnover, strengthening trust, and achieving the goals of synergy and integration in scientific research among SCO member states.

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俄罗斯和美国网络犯罪打击体系的全面比较分析
**COMPREHENSIVE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CYBERCRIME
COUNTERACTION SYSTEMS IN RUSSIA AND THE USA**

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摘要：本文旨在通过对俄罗斯联邦和美国这两个技术先进且地缘政治地位重要的国家打击网络犯罪的方法进行比较分析，来解决网络犯罪这种现象的非法跨国性质问题。通过对两国网络犯罪打击体系的比较分析，本文识别了共同存在的问题和各自特有的问题，并提出了改进网络犯罪打击措施的建议。

关键词：网络犯罪，监管框架，法律法规，打击网络犯罪的问题与前景，国家特征。

Abstract: *The article is devoted to an attempt to solve the problem of the illegal transnational nature of such a phenomenon as cybercrime by applying a comparative analysis of approaches to countering cybercrime in technologically advanced and geopolitically significant powers, namely, in the Russian Federation and the United States. The comparative analysis of cybercrime counteraction systems in these countries helped identify common and specific problems, as well as develop recommendations for improving cybercrime counteraction measures.*

Keywords: *cybercrime, regulatory frameworks, legal regulation, problems and prospects of countering cybercrime, specific national characteristics.*

Global digitalization and the rapid development of information and communication technologies in the 21st century have led to the formation of a fundamentally new cyberspace environment which has become not only an instrument of economic and social progress, but also an arena for the commission of illegal acts.

Cybercrime is one of the most serious threats to national and international security, economic development, and the rights of citizens. According to Interpol, the total amount of losses from cybercrime reaches trillions of dollars annually, which is comparable to the gross domestic product of entire countries, and the projected costs are expected to more than double in the coming years.

The transnational nature of this phenomenon makes it dramatically more difficult to combat it, as modern cybercriminals coordinate actions from different jurisdictions, use infrastructure in several countries simultaneously, and harm victims around the world.

The comparative analysis of approaches to countering cybercrime in such technologically advanced and geopolitically significant powers as the Russian Federation and the United States of America, which, according to the World Cybercrime Index, are among the key sources of cyber threats and at the same time are the most attractive targets for cyber attacks, is of particular importance. The political and legal context of modern international relations between Russia and the United States adds additional complexity to cyber security issues. On the one hand, there is an obvious need for cooperation in combating common threats. On the other hand, there remain significant differences in approaches to regulating the Internet, protecting personal data, and ensuring national digital sovereignty. These contradictions are directly reflected in the formation of national strategies to counter cybercrime.

The problems of cybercrime are studied by both foreign and domestic researchers, but the degree of development of individual aspects varies significantly. In the United States, cyber security issues are handled by specialists from the FBI, the Department of Justice, the National Security Agency, as well as numerous research centers (RAND Corporation, Center for Strategic and International Studies). In Russia, the main centers for the study of cybercrime are the scientific departments of relevant bodies (the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Federal Security Service (FSS), the Investigative Committee) and universities (Moscow State University, St. Petersburg State University, universities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs). The purpose of this article is a comprehensive comparative analysis of cybercrime prevention systems in Russia and the United States and the identification of common and specific problems, as well as the development of recommendations for improving counteraction measures. The concept of “cybercrime” has undergone a complex evolution reflecting changes in technology and public consciousness. Historically, the original term was “computer crime” which appeared in the 1970s and referred to illegal actions related to the use of computer systems. In the 1980s, with the proliferation of personal computers and computer networks, the concept expanded to “computer information crimes.” The current stage of the concept’s development is associated with the formation of global cyberspace and the beginning of mass Internet use in the 1990s. It was during this period that the term

“cybercrime” appeared which reflects a qualitatively new phenomenon — criminal activity carried out not just using computers, but within a specially created digital environment — cyberspace. The Russian legal doctrine is dominated by the definition of cybercrime as a criminal activity aimed at violating the established procedure for the circulation of computer information, carried out using computer tools and telecommunication technologies. In the American legal tradition, the emphasis is on illegal acts committed using computers or computer networks, while computers themselves can be both the target and the instrument of a crime.

A feature of modern cybercrime is its high adaptability to changing conditions. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a sharp increase in phishing attacks related to the virus, and in the context of sanctions pressure on Russia, attacks on the financial sector intensified. Extensive regulatory and legal frameworks have been established in Russia and the United States to counter cybercrime, which continues to develop actively [3].

Criteria	The Russian Federation	The USA
Leading authorities	Department “K” of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, FSS	Department of Justice, FBI
Coordinating body	Interdepartmental Working group of the Prosecutor General’s Office	Joint National Task Force on Cyber Investigations (NCIJTF)
Specialized divisions	Cyber warfare of the Russian Federation	FBI Cyber Division (CyD)
Private sector involvement	Kaspersky Lab and other companies	Voluntary information exchange programs with businesses through ISACs
International cooperation	Mainly bilateral formats, the SCO, the CSTO	Participation in the Budapest Convention, G7, Five Eyes
Military cyber structures	Cyber warfare as part of the Russian Armed Forces	U.S. Cyber Command (USCYBERCOM)

Fig.1. Comparative description of institutional systems for countering cybercrime in Russia and the United States.

After analyzing the legislative systems of Russia and the United States, it is possible to identify significant differences in approaches to legal regulation of the fight against cybercrime. The chronological difference is evident in the fact that the United States began to form a legislative framework much earlier — the first specialized laws were adopted in the 1980s, whereas in Russia active lawmaking in this area began only in the 2000s. The conceptual difference lies in the fact that American legislation focuses on the protection of information systems and networks, whereas Russian legislation focuses on the protection of information as an

object of legal relations. The structural difference is that in the United States there are many specialized laws regulating certain aspects of cyber security, whereas in Russia the model of several framework laws prevails, which are then specified by secondary legislation. The international legal difference is evident in the attitude towards international treaties: the United States is a party to the Budapest Convention, while Russia does not participate in this agreement and is developing alternative international initiatives.

Considering the current problems and prospects of countering cybercrime in Russia and the United States, it should be noted that one of the key problems in Russia is the exponential growth in the number of cybercrimes. According to the statistical reports of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Russian Federation, 294,000 cybercrimes were recorded in 2019, 572,124 in 2020, and 715,155 cases in 2021. Such a sharp increase is due to both objective factors (the COVID-19 pandemic and the transition to remote forms of work and education) and subjective ones (the psychology of a criminal who decides to commit illegal acts in a virtual environment that he would not dare in the real world) [1, C. 287-292].

Technical and technological changes also remain a major challenge. In 2025, there has been a surge in attacks on Russian enterprises exploiting software vulnerabilities. For example, the Cloud Atlas cybercrime group attacks agro-industrial enterprises using vulnerabilities in Microsoft Office (CVE-2017-11882). There is also a 43% increase in attacks on ERP systems of Russian companies in the first half of 2025 compared to the same period in 2024 [2].

Staffing issues are also a significant challenge for the Russian cybercrime counteraction system. There is an outflow of qualified specialists to the private sector and abroad, which weakens the potential of law enforcement agencies. In the United States, one of the main problems is the complexity of the legislative process and political polarization, which makes it difficult to adopt the necessary regulations. As noted in the research, several cyber security bills are presented at each session of Congress, but only a few of them receive support from both factions and become laws. The international nature of cybercrime poses challenges to law enforcement. Criminals exploit the freedom of movement of goods, services, data, and capital over the Internet, which requires international cooperation. Although the United States has ratified the Budapest Convention and supports the processes of international harmonization of legislation, there remains a problem of effective coordination with partners from different jurisdictions. Rapid technological development requires constant updating of the technical capabilities of law enforcement agencies. To address this issue, the Department of Justice and the FBI have increased funding for cyber security activities by 23% to increase the capacity to detect, prevent, and neutralize malicious cyber attacks [4].

The problem of interaction between the public and private sectors remains relevant, despite the adoption of the Cyber security Act of 2018 which provides for protection from liability for certain types of information about cyber threats. There remains a need for a balance between the need for information exchange and the risks of violating antimonopoly legislation [5].

The legal issues relate to issues of jurisdiction and the applicability of national legislation to transnational cybercrimes. Cases where criminals operate from countries that do not cooperate with the United States are particularly difficult. The analysis makes it possible to identify both general and specific problems in countering cybercrime in Russia and the United States.

Fig. 2. Promising areas for improving the fight against cybercrime in Russia and the United States.

Common problems include:

- rapid technological development and adaptability of cybercriminals;
- the transnational nature of cybercrime;
- lack of qualified personnel in law enforcement agencies;
- the complexity of investigating and proving cybercrimes;
- the need for a balance between security and the rights of citizens.

Specific problems of Russia:

- dependence on foreign software and hardware;
- international sanctions and restrictions in the field of high technologies;
- the relatively recent formation of a cybercrime counteraction system;
- high level of cybercrime activity.

Specific problems of the USA:

- political polarization and complexity of the legislative process;
- contradictions between the interests of law enforcement agencies and IT

companies;

- the global nature of American IT companies and the legal complexities involved;
- high concentration of critical information infrastructure in the private

sector.

Based on the analysis, promising areas for improving the fight against cyber-crime in Russia and the United States can be identified:

For the United States of America:

Harmonization of legal regulation: elimination of contradictions between federal and state legislation; creation of uniform standards in the field of cybersecurity for all sectors of the economy; improving the mechanisms for the extradition of cybercriminals.

Strengthening public-private partnerships: development of effective mechanisms for the exchange of information on cyber threats; creating incentives for private companies to invest in cybersecurity; development of cybersecurity standards for critical infrastructure.

Improvement of the personnel training system: expanding cyber education programs at all levels; creation of a system of continuous professional training of specialists; developing programs to attract and retain talented professionals in the public sector.

For the Russian Federation:

Despite their political differences, Russia and the United States have a common interest in combating transnational cybercrime. Promising areas of cooperation could be:

1. Creation of operational cooperation mechanisms to counteract the most dangerous cyber threats.
2. Development of common standards and protocols in the field of cyber security.
3. Joint research and development in the field of cyber security technologies.
4. Exchange of best practices in the field of legislative regulation and law enforcement.

Development of the national IT industry: acceleration of import substitution in the field of mission-critical software; stimulating the development of domestic solutions in the field of cybersecurity; supporting research and development in the field of advanced technologies.

Improvement of legal regulation: development of specialized legislation on the regulation of artificial intelligence and the Internet of things; clarifying the composition of cybercrimes, taking into account modern realities; creation of flexible regulatory mechanisms capable of quickly adapting to new threats.

Institutional capacity-building: improving the status and resource provision of cybercrime units; creation of a unified national system for monitoring and responding to cyber incidents; development of a system of interagency cooperation and information exchange.

Development of international cooperation: active participation in international initiatives to combat cybercrime; strengthening bilateral and multilateral cooperation within the SCO, BRICS, and CSTO.

Fig. 3. Practical recommendations to improve the fight against cybercrime.

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犯罪学与犯罪预防：现代方法与技术
**CRIMINALISTICS CRIME PREVENTION: MODERN
APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES**

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摘要：本文探讨了当代犯罪预防领域所采用的方法和技术。文章分析了基于犯罪学和社会学数据的犯罪预防方法，以及信息技术在提高犯罪预防效率方面的作用。文章特别关注传统方法与现代数字工具的融合。

关键词：犯罪预防，犯罪，预防措施，数据分析，方法。

Abstract. *The article examines contemporary approaches and technologies employed in the criminalistic prevention of crimes. The article analyzes methods of crime prevention based on criminological and sociological data, alongside the role of information technologies in improving the effectiveness of crime prevention. Particular attention is paid to the integration of traditional methods with modern digital tools.*

Keywords: *criminalistic prevention, crime, preventive measures, data analysis, method.*

Criminalistic prevention of crimes is a crucial aspect of combating crime and constitutes a set of methods and practices aimed at preventing criminal activity before its occurrence. In contemporary conditions, where the crime rate changes under the influence of various factors, the implementation of effective prevention strategies becomes essential to ensure societal security. In the context of rapid technological advancement and changes in the social environment, it is necessary to adapt approaches to crime prevention by employing modern tools and methods [1].

Criminalistic Prevention is based on theoretical concepts that explain the causes of crimes and the factors contributing to their commission. These theories assist in identifying target groups and areas for the implementation of preventive measures. The most important among these concepts are:

— The theory of social disintegration assumes that crimes emerge in societies with low levels of social integration and support.

— The choice theory emphasizes that offenders make rational decisions by assessing the risks and benefits of committing a crime [2].

There are numerous methods of criminalistic crime prevention, which can be categorized as follows:

1. Information and education: organizing seminars, training sessions, and campaigns to enhance citizens' legal awareness regarding potential threats and methods of their prevention.

2. Social programs: the creation and financing of specialized programs to support youth, vulnerable population groups, and other categories at risk of involvement in criminal activity;

3. Participation of law enforcement agencies: active cooperation between the police and society, as well as the implementation of projects for crime prevention at the local level [1].

The implementation of these methods necessitates the use of modern approaches to criminalistics-based prevention. Contemporary approaches to criminalistics-based prevention can be categorized into three groups:

1. Preventive policing is based on proactive measures aimed at preventing crimes before they occur. This includes patrolling, engagement with local communities, and active interaction with citizens.

2. Social programs aimed at reducing crime rates include educational initiatives, employment programs, and rehabilitation. These measures help eliminate the root causes of crime and promote social integration.

3. Data Analysis. The use of data analytics to identify criminogenic zones and predict crime has become an important tool in criminalistics-based crime prevention. Predictive analytics systems enable law enforcement agencies to concentrate efforts on the most vulnerable areas [2]. This approach highlights the applied technological innovations, namely:

— Big data and artificial intelligence technologies, which play a key role in modern criminalistics-based crime prevention. Artificial intelligence can analyze vast amounts of data, identify patterns, and predict potential crimes.

— Geographic information systems, which allow visualization of crime data on maps, helping law enforcement agencies better understand the spatial aspects of crime and develop targeted measures.

— Monitoring social networks and online platforms, providing the opportunity to detect potential threats and criminal intentions at early stages. This enables law enforcement agencies to respond promptly to emerging risks [2].

However, the implementation of digital technologies in recent years has led to a fundamental transformation in the qualitative content of social life. Currently,

a significant volume of processes in the economy and production relations is governed by principles based on innovations in digital implementation. Thus, technological changes radically transform not only the methods of committing crimes but, most importantly, the modes of communication among criminal elements.

Such 'tasks' can only be resolved through the application of specialized knowledge in the fields of science and technology, as well as the use of modern equipment designed for this purpose. Let us consider solutions to problems by applying specialized knowledge in linguistics, utilizing artificial intelligence. Accordingly, the creation of automated servers with information control, incorporating artificial intelligence equipped with pre-installed words and phrases aimed at preparation or incitement to commit crimes, will be directed to automated workstations of linguistics specialists, significantly reducing the volume of information requiring analysis by experts.

However, with the development of applications, messengers and platforms have emerged, access to which is restricted for competent authorities and agencies. A solution to this problem may be the continuous professional development of educators at all levels (school, university) and supervisors in the field of linguistics. This will enable the prevention of crimes at their inception and the transmission of information to competent authorities with considerable anticipation.

Regardless of technological advances, active citizen participation in crime prevention remains a crucial aspect of criminalistic warning. Communities can organize groups for order observation, known as vigilantes, cooperate with law enforcement agencies, and exchange information about criminal intentions [3].

Interaction among authorities, law enforcement agencies, and the population contributes to the creation of a safer environment. Programs aimed at strengthening trust between the police and the community are generally the most effective.

Studies show that in some cities, implemented crime prevention programs have led to a significant reduction in crime rates. One example is the model of the "Preventive Police" in Norway, where the focus is on the proactive prevention of crimes through active dissemination of information and community participation [3].

Criminalistic prevention of crimes requires a comprehensive approach that combines traditional methods with modern technologies. The integration of data analytics, social programs, and preventive measures can significantly improve the effectiveness of crime prevention. It is essential to continue researching and implementing new technologies to adapt to the evolving conditions and challenges of modern society.

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从社会价值论的角度研究现代法治国家作为一种转型类型的国家
**SOCIO-AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY
OF THE MODERN RULE-OF-LAW STATE
AS A STATE OF A TRANSITIONAL TYPE**

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摘要：本文论证了运用社会价值论方法分析现代法治国家的必要性。作者考察了传统形式法律定义在描述国家法律现象动态本质方面的局限性。文章提出了法治国家作为“转型型”国家的概念，其本质体现在将社会冲突不断转化为法律惯例的过程中。文章分析了法律作为一种机制，如何通过文化价值体系来确保社会妥协并使国家强制行为合法化。此外，文章还探讨了数字时代国家的功能转型，重点关注安全与自由之间的平衡。

关键词：法治国家，社会价值论方法，转型型国家，法律惯例，社会妥协，合法性，法律转型，数字化转型，安全。

Abstract. *The article substantiates the necessity of applying a socio-axiological approach to the analysis of the modern rule-of-law state. The author examines the limitations of classical formal-legal definitions in describing the dynamic nature of state-legal phenomena. A concept of the rule-of-law state as a state of a “transitional type” is proposed, the essence of which is revealed in the continuous process of transforming social conflicts into legal conventions. The role of law as a mechanism for ensuring social compromise and legitimizing state coercion through a system of cultural values is analyzed. The article also explores the functional transformations of the state in the digital era, focusing on the balance between security and liberty.*

Keywords: *rule-of-law state, socio-axiological approach, state of a transitional type, legal convention, social compromise, legitimacy, transformation of law, digital transformation, security.*

In modern legal science, the concept of a “rule-of-law state” (Rechtsstaat) serves as a fundamental category for understanding the interaction between public authority and civil society. Historically, this concept evolved through the prism of

classical liberal theories formed during the Modern Era and the Enlightenment. The traditional approach, dating back to the seminal works of I. Kant and R. von Mohl, emphasizes the formal supremacy of the law, the strict separation of powers, and the guarantee of individual rights as the primary restrainers of monarchical or bureaucratic arbitrariness [2]. These classical theories successfully formulated the normative ideal of the state, establishing a benchmark for political development in Western democracies.

However, modern political and legal realities demonstrate the need to expand the methodological toolkit to explain the functional transformations of the state in the 21st century. Classical theory (*Rechtsstaat*) describes an ideal model — the “ought,” focusing on static institutions and formal procedures. Meanwhile, the practice of state-building faces the necessity of managing complex social conflicts, economic crises, and technological shifts in the conditions of the “is.” As B. A. Kistyakovskiy rightly noted, law represents a complex social phenomenon rooted in the culture, psychology, and values of society, extending far beyond written statutes [3]. In this regard, there is an urgent need for a new approach such as socio-axiological provides that allows for the investigation of the rule-of-law state as a dynamic system of a transitional type, capable of adapting to the fluid nature of modern social relations.

The socio-axiological approach implies a comprehensive and multidimensional analysis of the rule-of-law state, integrating sociological realism with axiological idealism. The sociological aspect reveals the state as a functioning mechanism for coordinating the interests of various social groups, classes, and corporate entities. It focuses on the actual behavior of subjects, the implementation of norms, and the effectiveness of legal institutions in resolving conflicts. Simultaneously, the axiological (value-based) aspect views the state as a system that legitimizes its existence by appealing to universally significant ideals of justice, freedom, and human dignity. This dual perspective allows researchers to bridge the gap between the formal declaration of rights and their actual realization.

Within this methodology, law functions simultaneously as an instrument of coercion and a value orientation that shapes the legal consciousness of citizens. V. S. Nersisyan, in his libertarian-legal theory, emphasized that law embodies formal freedom, and the content of this form depends entirely on the specific historical context and the balance of social forces at a given moment [6]. Consequently, the study of the modern rule-of-law state requires an analysis of how abstract legal values are translated into the fabric of daily social relations. This approach treats the state not as a rigid structure of coercion, but as a cultural and historical form of organizing social life, where the validity of law rests on its acceptance by the community.

The central thesis of the research asserts that the modern rule-of-law state possesses the ontological nature of a state of a transitional type. This term characterizes the essence of modern statehood, extending beyond the limited understanding of

transitionality as a temporary phase between authoritarianism and democracy. A state of a transitional type operates as a system in a permanent search for a dynamic equilibrium. It constantly balances public interests, such as national security, social stability, and general order, with private interests, including freedom of enterprise, privacy, and individual autonomy. This model involves the continuous harmonization of the necessity for legal coercion with the requirement for conventional consent from the governed.

As researchers point out, the establishment of a rule-of-law state constitutes an endless process of the self-limitation of power by law [5]. Transitionality signifies the perpetual transformation of forceful methods of governance into legal procedures. In archaic or totalitarian systems, conflict is resolved through direct violence or suppression. In contrast, the rule-of-law state transfers conflict into the plane of legal discourse, making the “transition” from force to law its primary operational mode. This state is never fully “complete”; it remains in a constant state of becoming, adapting its legal framework to new challenges such as migration, economic globalization, and technological disruption.

In the conditions of the increasing complexity and fragmentation of the social structure, the conventional compromise becomes the foundational basis for the stability of the rule-of-law state. Socio-axiological analysis highlights the contractual nature of the interaction between power and society as the core of this compromise. Power and society maintain a functional pact, within which society accepts legislative restrictions and taxation in exchange for guarantees of security, predictability of life, and the protection of property. J. Rawls defined such relationships through the concept of an “overlapping consensus,” where different social groups agree on common political principles of justice, even while holding divergent moral, religious, or philosophical beliefs [7].

Another crucial characteristic of this convention is the systemic reduction of violence in social regulation. As the rule-of-law state develops, functions of direct suppression, characteristic of the class-based approach, yield to functions of arbitration and mediation. The state assumes the role of a neutral moderator ensuring procedural justice, thereby preserving the integrity of the social fabric. In this transitional period, law also performs a vital ideological function. A. I. Klimenko notes that legal ideology serves as a necessary instrument for the legitimation of power, creating a profound sense of the correctness and justice of the existing order among legal subjects [4]. The axiological component fills legal norms with real content, preventing them from deteriorating into formal bureaucratic schemes and ensuring voluntary compliance based on respect for the law rather than fear of punishment.

The transitional nature of the modern state manifests most acutely in the functional transformation of its security apparatus. The classic liberal model viewed the state primarily as a “night watchman,” protecting rights with minimal interference.

However, modern risks—ranging from international terrorism to pandemics—compel the state to expand its protective functions, often at the expense of individual liberties. This creates an antinomy where the state must restrict rights to protect the very subjects of those rights. The socio-axiological approach interprets this not as a deviation, but as a feature of the transitional type, where the legal system must constantly renegotiate the boundaries of acceptable state intervention.

This transformation leads to the intellectualization of policing and governance. In the conditions of the information society, primitive coercion loses economic and political efficiency. Consequently, the state shifts to using methods of “soft power,” preventive monitoring, and information influence to shape a compliant legal culture. The law enforcement function evolves from punitive to service-oriented, yet it simultaneously acquires new technological capabilities for surveillance. The challenge for the transitional state lies in maintaining these expanded security powers within the constitutional framework, preventing the slide into a “police state” under the guise of public safety.

A significant factor influencing the structural transformation of the modern state is digitalization. The integration of digital technologies into public administration alters the traditional mechanisms of interaction between the citizen and the state. Bureaucratic hierarchies are increasingly supplemented or replaced by algorithmic governance and digital platforms. This shift offers the potential for greater transparency and efficiency but also poses risks to the axiological foundations of the law. The depersonalization of decision-making through artificial intelligence challenges the principle of human-centric justice.

In the context of the transitional state, digitalization acts as a catalyst for both centralization and decentralization. On one hand, it provides the state with unprecedented tools for control and resource management. On the other hand, it empowers civil society with new channels for communication and oversight. The legal state must therefore develop new “digital rights” and conventions that extend the rule of law into the virtual space. This involves protecting data privacy and ensuring “algorithmic due process,” essentially expanding the social contract to cover the digital domain.

The socio-axiological approach provides a robust framework for expanding the understanding of the modern rule-of-law state, presenting it as a living, developing organism rather than a static ideal. The concept of a “state of a transitional type” explains the inherent complexity and contradictions of modern political processes, in which high legal ideals coexist with rigid management practices and expanding security measures. The essence of the modern rule-of-law state manifests in its capacity to transform social antagonisms into legal procedures through continuous conventional dialogue. The ability to maintain this delicate balance through a system of shared values and adaptive legal procedures acts as the ultimate criterion for the viability of the state in modern conditions.

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调解协议的法律性质

THE LEGAL NATURE OF THE MEDIATION AGREEMENT**Aldushina Oksana Sergeevna***Senior Lecturer**Donbas State University of Justice*

摘要：本文探讨了调解协议的法律性质这一争议性问题。作者对比了调解协议作为民事交易的概念，并强调了其复杂性，其中可能包含程序性特征。文章论证了调解协议具有复杂且多面的性质，兼具实体法律特征和执行程序特征。

关键词：调解协议，调解，公证，可执行性，替代性争议解决方式。

Abstract. *The article examines the controversial issue of the legal nature of the mediation agreement. The author juxtaposes the concepts of the mediation agreement as a civil law transaction and emphasizes its complex nature, which may also include procedural characteristics. The article substantiates the conclusion that the mediation agreement has a complex, multifaceted nature, combining substantive legal and enforcement-procedural features.*

Keywords: *mediation agreement, mediation, notarization, enforceability, alternative dispute resolution.*

The peaceful settlement of disputes is an objective that the Russian legislator aims to achieve. To this end, the institution of mediation was introduced into the legislation of the Russian Federation. According to the principal normative act, the Federal Law dated July 27, 2010, No. 193-FZ ‘On Alternative Dispute Resolution Procedure with the Participation of a Mediator (Mediation Procedure)’ (hereinafter — Federal Law ‘On Mediation’), mediation is defined as ‘a method of dispute resolution with the assistance of a mediator based on the voluntary consent of the parties, aimed at achieving a mutually acceptable solution’ [1].

The outcome of such a procedure is a mediation agreement — an agreement concluded by the parties through negotiations with the assistance of a mediator.

It should be noted that the mediator maintains impartiality and also keeps confidential all information disclosed during the mediation process. In this regard, for persons seeking to avoid disclosure of any dispute, mediation appears to be a more advantageous procedure compared to litigation, as any court decision becomes public.

The subject matter of a mediation agreement today may include installment performance, the possibility of future compensation in non-monetary form (goods, services), the recording of mutual concessions, the amount of alimony payments, and the like. At the same time, the parties' freedom is not absolute. The agreement must not contradict mandatory legal norms, violate public interests, or infringe upon the rights and lawful interests of third parties.

According to N. G. Kirdyapina, a mediation agreement represents not only the recording of the reached compromise but also a stable foundation for its voluntary enforcement, which advantageously distinguishes mediation from other dispute resolution methods [2, pp. 35-39].

Since mediation may be conducted with the consent of the parties (as it is a voluntary procedure) both before applying to the court (Article 12 of the Federal Law 'On Mediation') and during judicial proceedings, including arbitration (in addition to the Federal Law 'On Mediation,' the parties in this case must be guided by the relevant procedural code (the APC, CPC, or CAS)), the mediation agreement may be considered as:

- a transaction with all its legal consequences. Depending on the terms of the transaction, the parties must be guided by the rules of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation applicable in the specific case. At the same time, upon the request of the parties who have reached an agreement, notarization of the mediation agreement is allowed. In this case, the document acquires the force of an enforceable instrument;
- a settlement agreement (if it is concluded after the parties have already applied to the court), while its preparation is not the final stage of dispute resolution. Only when the court verifies the legality of the agreement and the absence of violations of rights and interests will it approve the document and terminate the proceedings — this will mark the conclusion of the dispute.

Nevertheless, the question of the legal qualification of the mediation agreement as a civil law transaction remains ambiguous. Its legal nature determination holds not only academic but also practical importance, defining the procedure for its conclusion, challenge, and enforcement. Several approaches to comprehending the essence of this phenomenon have emerged in contemporary doctrine, evolving alongside legislative changes.

Materials and methods

Considerable scholarship by modern researchers addresses the legal nature of the mediation agreement and, more broadly, the procedure of mediation. For example, analyses of the works of N. I. Minkina, K. V. Korshakova, M. A. Doli, and A. A. Furtak allows the conclusion that the legal nature of the mediation agreement is complex. Methodologically, general scientific methods (systemic, comparative-legal) and private-law methods (dogmatic analysis of contract and procedural agreement institutions) were employed.

Results and its discussion

One of the foundational studies that laid the theoretical groundwork for understanding the essence of the mediation agreement is the dissertation by A. A. Furtak [3]. In his dissertation research, the author consistently defends the thesis on the civil-law nature of the mediation agreement. A. A. Furtak characterizes it as a civil law transaction of a special kind, arguing that it is based on the mutual will of the parties aimed at establishing, modifying, or terminating rights and obligations [3].

The author places special emphasis on the fact that the mediation agreement serves as a tool for the self-regulation of private relationships. Its nature as a transaction is determined by its objective — to resolve an existing legal dispute, which aligns it with the institution of a settlement agreement, but in its non-procedural (material) aspect. The researcher emphasizes that the obligatory nature of the agreement prevails over its possible procedural consequences.

Undoubtedly, in relation to disputes involving disagreements arising in the contractual sphere and obligatory legal relations, that is, disputes arising in the civil-law domain, the mediation agreement acquires a civil-law character. This is also emphasized in Article 12 of the Federal Law ‘On Mediation’: ‘a mediation agreement concerning a dispute arising from civil legal relations, reached by the parties as a result of the mediation procedure conducted without referring the dispute to a court or an arbitral tribunal, constitutes a civil-law transaction aimed at establishing, modifying, or terminating the rights and obligations of the parties.’

At the same time, mediation agreements possess procedural-legal characteristics: they affect the right of access to the court, determine the parties’ conduct in relation to dispute resolution, and may provide for the suspension or termination of judicial proceedings.

Thus, N. I. Minkina develops the idea that a mediation agreement is a “special legal instrument for dispute resolution.” She draws attention to the fact that the legislative establishment of the possibility of notarial certification of mediation agreements has conferred upon them the status of acts of preventive justice. The researcher emphasizes that the legal nature of the agreement is determined by its functional purpose: it is not merely a transaction, but a legal form of final conflict resolution, endowed with enhanced evidentiary and enforcement force. Thus, the author arrives at the quite logical conclusion that «the mediation agreement has a mixed legal nature at the intersection of both substantive and procedural law norms». Furthermore, N. I. Minkina points to the diverse sectoral substantive-legal nature of the agreement (civil, family, labor, etc.) without restricting it solely to the general understanding of a civil-law transaction, depending on the specific disputed legal relations regulated by this agreement and the conditions it contains.

When considering the legal nature of the mediation agreement, it should also be noted that it may be concluded ‘as a result of a compromise reached on disputes

arising from civil, administrative, and other public legal relations, including those related to entrepreneurial and other economic activities, as well as disputes arising from labor and family relations,' as follows from Article 1 of the Federal Law 'On Mediation.' Thus, it can be concluded that the mediation agreement may also have a public-law character.

K. V. Korshakova and M. A. Some scholars emphasize that the legal nature of the agreement can shift from purely substantive to mixed. The authors underscore the importance of the volitional aspect: the mediation agreement is not imposed externally but is a product of consensus, thereby preserving its private-law core even when acquiring public-law features (enforceability). Thus, although the authors speak of the mixed nature of the mediation agreement, they emphasize that its legal nature remains essentially civil-law in character.

Therefore, after reviewing the views of various authors concerning the legal nature of mediation agreements, it can be concluded that such agreements are transactions exhibiting characteristics of both civil law and public law. Furthermore, mediation agreements possess procedural law characteristics. Thus, the mediation agreement has a mixed legal nature, the character of which depends on its subject matter, as well as on the stage (pre-trial or judicial) of dispute resolution at which it is concluded.

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数字教育支持工具的多维性：分类方法
**MULTIDIMENSIONALITY OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT
TOOLS: APPROACHES TO CLASSIFICATION**

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摘要：本文致力于探讨如何系统化支持教育过程的数字化工具。文章论证了对这些工具进行分类的必要性，认为这是将其有效融入教学实践的前提条件。基于系统性的方法，本文提出并详细分析了一个三级分类体系，该体系涵盖了三种基本类型的工具：技术、设备和内容。针对每种类型，文章分析了科学文献中使用的一系列关键分类标准，从而揭示了它们的多维性及其在教育生态系统中的功能作用。

关键词：支持教育过程的数字化工具，教育技术，教育设备，教育内容

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the problem of systematizing digital tools for supporting the educational process. The necessity of their classification as a condition for effective integration into pedagogical practice is substantiated. Based on a systematic approach, the article proposes and analyzes in detail a three-level typology that includes three fundamental types of tools: Technologies, Devices, and Content. For each type, a range of key classification criteria used in scientific literature is analyzed, which allows revealing their multidimensionality and functional role in the educational ecosystem.*

Keywords: *digital tools for supporting the educational process, educational technologies, devices for education, educational content*

The effective integration of digital support tools into the educational process requires a clear understanding of their nature and interrelationships, as well as a strict correlation between their use and educational goals. In this context, the basis for this study is a systematic approach aimed at developing and revising the classifications of these tools.

We consider digital support for the educational process as a form of indirect interaction between its subjects. This interaction is aimed at the effective

achievement of educational results and combines pedagogical support with digitalization processes. As with any system, we can identify the basic structural elements of this pedagogical phenomenon, which can be organized by classification.

The paper proposes a classification that is designed to perform several important functions. First, it helps to systematize the terminology used in the field of digitalization of education, providing a more accurate understanding of the nature and functional purpose of various tools. Second, it provides educators with a methodological basis for the informed selection and application of technologies in accordance with specific pedagogical tasks and the development of methodological materials and recommendations for their use.

The relevance of the work is due to the essential need for comprehensive research on the digital transformation of the educational sphere, including analysis of the effectiveness of tools, trends, and prospects for their development.

Earlier in our research, we formulated a classification system for digital tools supporting the educational process, in which all tools are divided into three fundamental types: Technologies, Devices, and Content [12]. The systemic relationship between these types is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Interrelationship between types of digital tools supporting the educational process (Developed by the author)

The first type of digital tools for supporting the educational process to be considered is **digital educational technologies**. In the conventional sense, these include a set of processes for the targeted processing of data using electronic devices and systems that ensure their generation, storage, processing, and transmission in digital form.

It is worth noting the dual nature of the “Technologies” category. In a narrow sense, they act as an independent element of the proposed classification. In a broad sense, digital technologies permeate the entire digital support system, being both the basis for the functioning of devices and the inherent principle of content existence. For example, modern devices such as 3D printers or smartphones are themselves the product and material embodiment of a complex of advanced digital technologies. In parallel with this, content processing — its creation, accumulation, storage, application, and so on — is also implemented through specialized digital technologies [4]. Thus, digital technologies act as a cross-cutting, infrastructural element of the system.

Let us focus on the key grounds for the classification of digital educational technologies used by various authors and research teams.

The key criterion is the functional purpose in working with data: its creation, processing, transmission and storage, use, or combined interactive functions. This approach is based on the essential capabilities of the technology itself. Another similar classification of technologies is based on identifying the dominant function or principle of their actions in the ecosystem (e.g., platform, connection tool, analytics tool, interaction tool). This is a higher-level generalization than functional purpose.

The presence and degree of implementation of cognitive functions in technology also plays a significant role. An important criterion is the ability of technology to analyze, interpret information, and make decisions, i.e., its proximity to human intelligence. This divides technologies into cognitive (AI-based) and non-cognitive.

Technologies can be divided according to the level of the subject of application: individual user (student, teacher), individual educational organization (university, school), or national/regional level. Another basis for classification is the competencies that are formed. This approach is focused on the outcome of education and allows us to evaluate the contribution of technology to the development of specific groups of skills in students: hard skills (specialized, subject-oriented) or soft skills (universal, social, and personal).

Finally, technologies are grouped according to the specific activities of the participants in the educational process that they serve. Traditionally, these are divided into educational, teaching and methodological, research, educational, or administrative and managerial. This criterion is integrative and links technology to specific practices in educational organizations [1].

The classifications presented demonstrate the evolution of views on digital technologies in education from a purely technical description of their functions in relation to data to their interpretation in the context of the educational system. The range of classification bases reflects the multidimensionality of the phenomenon of digital technologies, which can simultaneously be a tool, an environment, a resource, and an agent of change in education.

Educational devices represent the next type of digital support for the educational process that we have identified. This instrumental component of digital support for learning consists of hardware and software complexes designed to perform specific operations with data and ensure interaction for educational purposes.

The classification criteria presented below consider educational devices from different, mutually complementary perspectives: from their internal technological essence and basic function in information processing to their role in organizing interaction between subjects and the level of autonomy [9].

A multi-level classification allows us to understand their potential place and role in the educational ecosystem. Firstly, we highlight such a basis for the classification of educational devices as the functional role of the technology used: applied (solving specific tasks, for example, machine learning) or infrastructural (ensuring the operation of other systems, for example, network platforms).

The nature of interaction with the physical world divides devices into those that work primarily with information and algorithms (cybernetic) and those that directly affect or are controlled by the physical environment (cyber-physical). In turn, the nature of data processing divides devices into those for data input/output (interface functions) and those for data processing (collection, analysis, transmission). Educational hardware and software tools are a striking example of the embodiment of educational devices [11].

Classification based on the network interaction model is based on the number and connection of subjects (users or devices) involved in communication through the device: one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many. This criterion reflects the role of the device in organizing the communication environment. The degree of activity of devices allows them to be divided into those capable of independent functioning and action or those that respond only to external commands or influences.

The most common criterion is the technological solution that determines the mode of use. The degree of mobility divides devices into stationary (often more powerful, with a fixed location) and mobile (portable, providing training without being tied to a specific location). This criterion directly determines the pedagogical possibilities and forms of organization of the educational process (for example, mobile learning).

The third type of digital support for the educational process is **digital educational content** — the informational and content core of the educational process,

which is a structured set of data designed to achieve specific learning objectives and develop competencies.

The classification system demonstrates the multifaceted nature of digital educational content and covers its essence, goal setting, technological implementation, and the nature of interaction with the user. At the same time, content is viewed as a product of a specific creation model and as a component of various levels in the digital architecture of education. This multifaceted approach allows content to be viewed as a dynamic element of the modern educational ecosystem, whose properties are determined by pedagogical, technological, and organizational factors.

The essential focus of content divides it according to its fundamental purpose and determines its pedagogical intent and structure. Content is also classified according to the level of education (e.g., secondary, higher, additional education) or the needs of a specific group of learners and takes into account the age, professional, and cognitive characteristics of users. Content varies in the number and type of media formats used, from simple, based on a single technology, to complex multimedia, combining different formats to enhance impact [7].

A criterion such as the nature of user interaction with the material divides content into passive (autonomous, for perception) and active (interactive, involving feedback and user actions) [8]. This parameter directly affects engagement and pedagogical effectiveness. Content, differentiated by production method, reflects current trends toward collaboration and openness in education [5]. Content is also viewed as an element of the hierarchy of digital systems: from a single application or service to a complex environment, ecosystem, or platform [10, 3].

Another classification is based on functional purpose in the pedagogical process. Content is distinguished for knowledge transfer (educational), for testing results (assessment), or for teacher support (methodological). In turn, didactic volume and structural completeness rank content according to scalability and systematicity, from a single element (file) to a complete course, library, or repository. The dominant media format and technological basis is a tactical criterion that determines the form of presentation of the material (text, graphic, game, adaptive, etc.).

Thus, the described typology is designed to promote the effective integration of modern digital technologies into the educational process by teaching staff, which, in turn, will require them to develop the appropriate professional competencies [6]. These include the following key aspects: technical literacy, the ability to transform traditional methods and didactic approaches into a digital environment, and the ability to build effective communication with students using digital communication channels.

The presented typology of digital tools for supporting the educational process is debatable and open to scientific discussion. Further research based on a systematic review of these tools will allow for the unification of the terminology used

in this field, as well as the development of criteria for assessing the quality of the tools and their compliance with basic pedagogical principles.

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